

Games-Based Construction Learning in Upper Primary Education

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Abstract

Within Scottish schools teachers are being encouraged to make more use of different styles of approaches to learning, one of which is the use of ICT to help develop children's digital literacy skills across the whole curriculum. Some suggested means of implementing this are using Glow – the Scottish schools' intranet system – or games-based learning (GBL). The curriculum encourages GBL by way of children constructing their own games, games-based construction learning (GBCL).

With applications like Scratch being easily available, game construction is becoming more accessible to a wider audience. However, from a teacher's perspective there are barriers to introducing GBCL in their classes from a lack of knowledge around GBCL and games construction to not knowing how best to implement this within their teaching. This thesis explores the use of game construction in primary school settings and aims to provide empirical evidence on the use of Scratch in primary education in Scotland

This thesis has reviewed the GBCL literature and identified that there is a lack of GBCL literature and a lack of implementation frameworks for GBCL within education. An initial framework for the implementation of GBCL within primary education has been developed and refined through empirical work with schools. This was undertaken during the school years 2011/12 and 2012/13. 384 children from 16 classes between Primary 4 and Primary 7 participated with their class teachers. Eight one-hour lessons on games construction using Scratch were delivered to each class either by the researcher or class teacher and evaluations of them by the children and teachers showed a mainly positive response. Teachers who participated gained confidence in their own skills of teaching with Scratch and were pleased with the progress their classes had made. Teachers also saw Scratch not only as a game construction tool but as a tool that allowed the children to problem solve and work together in teams.

During the study 178 games from all classes were constructed and these were analysed using a game coding scheme that was developed to capture the programming and design elements that the children had used in their games. Results showed that children could successfully use programming constructs such as User Interaction (key handling), Loops (iteration) and Conditional Statements to create their own simple games. This is important for teachers when considering the implications of not only using GBCL in their class but if they want to start looking at computational thinking and teaching programming in class.

This thesis has provided an original contribution to knowledge by showing how GBL/GBCL is being used in primary schools and what teachers feel about it. It has shown that through surveys and interviews teachers lack knowledge and possibly some confidence in delivering GBCL lessons. Additionally, this thesis provides empirical evidence on the use of GBCL within primary schools. As well as this, this thesis provides not only a framework for implementation that can be used in schools to undertake GBCL as well as a game coding scheme to assess Scratch games programming and design but lessons that have been trialled and still are being used by children and teachers in schools across Glasgow who now participate in an annual event known as the Mini Game Jam to showcase the skills they have learned through their Scratch lessons.

Declaration

The research presented in this thesis was carried out by the undersigned. No part of the research has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other University.

1 Introduction

Computer games are a popular medium, 66% of children between the ages of 5 to 15 own a games console (OFCOM, 2016). Given the popularity at home for games there are those who hope to utilise the benefits of computer games within the classroom (Beavis et al., 2009; Groff, Howells and Cranmer, 2010; Renton, 2015). This chapter discusses the problems with introducing games into teaching and proposes an approach that will be investigated in this thesis. The chapter concludes with an outline of the remaining chapters in this thesis.

1.1 Problems to be Addressed

Over the past few years the Scottish Government has reviewed the Scottish curriculum and, after much consultation, a new Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) has been implemented within Scottish schools (Priestley and Minty, 2012). This reform of education is one of the biggest Scotland has seen and intends to provide a coherent curriculum for children from 3 years through to 18 years (Scottish Executive, 2008). Similar curriculum changes have been implemented within schools in Northern Ireland (Department of Education, 2007), Wales (Welsh Government, 2007) and England (Qualifications and Curriculum Authority, 2014).

Previously ICT was one area of the curriculum that Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Education reported should be improved upon within the primary school sector in Scotland to provide children with increased opportunities to use computers (HMIE, 2009). The report also concluded that teachers should be taking the opportunities given in using ICT for more cross curricular learning. Teachers should be using ICT as approach to learning by embedding the skills learned in ICT in the other subject areas that they are teaching. Within the CfE, teachers are being encouraged to make more use of assorted styles of approaches to learning as well as cross curricular work, one of which is the use of ICT within learning. The use of ICT in learning is being encouraged to develop children's digital literacy skills and some suggested means of implementing this are through the use of Glow – the Scottish schools' intranet system – or games-based learning (GBL) (Education Scotland, 2011a), This is further enhanced within the Technologies curricular area that suggests children in primaries 5 to 7 should to be designing and creating their own games using interactive multimedia (Renton, 2015). However, from a teacher's perspective one of the barriers to introducing GBL is a lack of knowledge in using and implementing the technology and games (Pivec and Pivec, 2008; Groff, Howells and Crammer, 2010; Robertson, 2012).

Van Eck (2006) suggests from a review of the literature that there are three ways of introducing GBL into educational establishments either through the students creating their own games, through the students playing computer games that their teachers have created or using Commercial off the Shelf (COTS) games. While studies have been undertaken within primary, secondary and tertiary education, there is still insufficient empirical evidence to properly substantiate the use of computer games technology as a recognised educational approach (Meluso, Zheng, Spires and Lester, 2012; McClarty et al., 2012). (Connolly et al, 2012).

While there have been studies such as Adventure Author (Robertson and Good, 2005) and Storytelling Alice (Kelleher, Pausch and Kiesler, 2007) that enable children to create their own interactive stories that other children are then able to play, game construction has been relatively unexplored within the classroom (Earp, 2015).

With applications like Scratch (Resnick, Kafai and Maeda, 2003), game construction is becoming more accessible to children. Scratch is a program that takes its inspiration from Logo (Papert, 1980). It is a visual-based tool that uses blocks that are snapped together to create scripts. It is primarily aimed at children aged around eight, however, statistics from the Scratch site show that the average age of users is 12 (MIT, 2015) and there is a wide age range of users for this tool. It was envisaged from the outset that the aim of this project was to introduce children to computing at afterschool clubs within deprived areas, where schools had few technological resources and eventually the informal educational benefits of it would be studied at a later date (Resnick, Kafai and Maeda, 2003). Scratch has also been used at Harvard University as an introduction to programming for university students (Malan and Leitner, 2007; Malan, 2010), While Scratch is only one of many tools that can be utilised there are still very few published studies showing what is learned when children are making games (Denner, Werner and Ortiz 2011). This thesis explores the use of game construction in primary school settings and aims to provide empirical evidence on the use of Scratch in primary education in Scotland

1.2 Proposed Approach

This research investigates whether teachers use GBL within their classes and, if they do, what approaches they take, if there are any barriers to undertaking GBL in their classes and how these findings compare with the literature available. This will be achieved through an online

survey distributed to teachers within the Glasgow City council region. The results of this will also identify schools that would like to participate further with a game construction project. A literature search will be undertaken to identify any existing frameworks on introducing game construction within the primary classroom, while another literature search will be undertaken to identify if Scratch or similar game creation tools have been used within the primary classroom for game construction. If no suitable framework is found, then one will be developed from the literature and from the work undertaken in the initial stages of class participation. Teachers in the upper primary school will participate with their class and the researcher in a game construction project using Scratch. Upper primary is defined as the classes from Primary 4 through to Primary 7 (Kidner, 2011). During the project teachers will be interviewed at stages before, during and after to gather their views on how their class is coping with Scratch and their thoughts about the game construction approach. The research will also evaluate pupils' affective experiences of constructing games with Scratch. At the end of each lesson children will be asked to complete an evaluation to gauge their enjoyment of it. A game coding scheme will be developed from the literature to evaluate the final games that are constructed throughout the study. The final stage will involve teachers leading their own class in a game construction project and evaluating the success of this.

1.3 Structure of Thesis

The remainder of this thesis is split into the following chapters:

Chapter two will describe the methodologies used to answer the given research questions. It will detail the research objectives; the formation of the research questions; the secondary research procedures for the literature reviews performed; suitable methods to undertake the research within primary schools and analysis.

Chapter three will present the literature review for the use of games-based construction learning (GBCL) in primary education. It will discuss games-based learning within primary education. It will examine tools used to introduce GBCL and programming into primary education. It will then present a literature review on the use of Scratch in education for the use of GBCL.

Chapter four will present the results of a teacher survey undertaken within Glasgow City council in 2011 to gauge primary school teachers' use of games-based learning in their class.

Chapter five will present the results of Study 1. This study was conducted in 2011/2012 where the lessons were researcher led. This chapter will discuss the children's lesson evaluations and teacher interviews.

Chapter six will present the results of Study 2. This study was conducted in 2012/2013 where the lessons were researcher led. This chapter will discuss the children's lesson evaluations and teacher interviews.

Chapter seven will present an implementation framework based on literature and results of the studies conducted as well as the teacher questionnaire.

Chapter eight will present a game coding scheme to evaluate the games created within the research. It will then present the analysis of all games created by the children during Study 1 and Study 2.

Chapter nine will present an evaluation of the work performed in this research in terms of: the survey, the literature reviews, the work undertaken in both studies the development of the implementation framework for introducing Scratch into Primary Education, future evaluations and critical reflection.

Figure 1.1 provides a diagram representing the chapters and the relationship between chapters.

Figure 1.1 Diagram of related chapters

2 Methodology

As noted in the previous chapter, this thesis explores the use of game construction in primary school settings and aims to provide empirical evidence on the use of Scratch in primary education in Scotland. The purpose of this chapter is to examine the objectives of this study to identify the main research questions and to then select suitable research methodologies and methods to answer the research questions.

2.1 Key Research Objectives

The main objective of this research was to introduce primary education teachers to game construction with Scratch as part of class lessons. With GBL becoming more popular within education and game design/construction part of the CfE it is important to understand how game construction fits in with primary class lessons and how teachers feel about game making. It is also important to gain the views of the children participating within the lessons and feedback on their enjoyment will help to build a better understanding of how to implement game construction within the primary classroom. In addition, the games that children produce during the study will also be indicative of their understanding of the lessons. By analysing the games, it will show if the children have progressed from the starter lessons and how much effort they have put into creating their final games. This can be seen in how the children have constructed their games for example have they taken time to design their own sprites and backgrounds or have they used the ones that came with Scratch. The research also investigated whether teachers use games-based learning in their class and if so what have they done, and how this compares with the literature available.

2.2 Research Questions

The research questions are as follows:

Question 1: What empirical evidence is associated with games-based learning at Primary Education (PE) level and how does it compare with the views of PE level teachers in Scotland?

Question 2: What framework could be used to implement games construction using Scratch within the Curriculum for Excellence at upper school PE?

Question 3: How do the different levels of upper school PE make use of Scratch and how can their work be evaluated?

2.3 Research Methodologies

Teddlie and Tashakori (2009: 21) define a methodology as “*a broad approach to scientific inquiry specifying how research questions should be asked and answered. This includes worldview considerations, general preferences for designs, sampling logic, data collection and analytical strategies, guidelines for making inferences, and the criteria for assessing and improving quality.*” Bogdan and Biklen (2007) state that a methodology is “*a generic term that refers to the general logic and theoretical perspective for a research project*” and also that a methodology should not be confused with methods which they define as “*the specific techniques you use such as surveys, interviews, observation – the more technical aspects of the research*”.

Research methods can be classified as qualitative, quantitative or mixed. Myers (2009) states that qualitative research involves the study of social and cultural phenomena and that qualitative data sources include observation, interviews, documents and the researcher’s impressions and reactions. In contrast, quantitative research involves the collection of data for statistical analysis and uses data sources such as experiments and surveys (Creswell, 2003). Mixed methods research involves the use of both qualitative and quantitative approaches in a single study (Teddlie and Tashhakori, 2009).

The advantages and disadvantages of the main methodologies as that are used in research are adapted from Cohen and Mannion (2007), Cresswell (2003), Gravetter and Foranzo (2009) and Tisdall, Davis and Gallacher (2009) and shown in Table 2.1

Table 2.1: Research methodologies

Methodologies	Main characteristics	Advantages	Disadvantages
Case study	In-depth study used to investigate a phenomenon, typically within “real life” settings.	Studying people in their natural settings can help better understand behaviour.	Incorrect interpretations can be caused by interpreter bias.
Action Research	Usually a collaborative effort between practitioners and researcher through the	Bridges the gap between theory research and practise.	Possible conflicts between researcher and hierarchy within establishment.

	recurring process of action and critical reflection.		
Survey	To gather data from a time with a view to describing existing conditions.	Useful for obtaining the views of children who may not feel comfortable talking in focus groups.	Could exclude children with lower literacy levels (the researcher may help the child to complete).
Observation	Studying behaviours in their natural setting. Used to produce quantitative data.	Exploring what children do and say Less disruptive than other methods.	Can be seen as intrusive to children by their carers.
Creative methods	Using drawing, writing and photography to evaluate projects and activities.	May be appealing to children who would not otherwise respond well to other research methods.	Data analysis may be more difficult. More resource intensive.
Archival	Using existing articles, information and records to answer the research question.	Use of multiple sources to gather the literature.	Data within articles may not be complete or fully accurate.
Role-play	Participation in simulated social situations. Intended to throw light on the role/rule contexts governing real life social episodes.	Heightened excitement and interest in learning.	Time demanding activities.
Experiment	Controlled environment where active variables are manipulated by the researcher.	Conclusions can be drawn about behaviours by eliminating behaviour influencing factors.	People may behave differently in an artificial environment.
Quasi-experiment	Carried out in natural settings.	Predictable relationships can be identified.	Can be open to confounding. Extraneous variables may have an impact on the quasi-experiment as well as the independent variable.
Ethnography	Study taken over a prolonged period of time of an intact cultural group.	Useful to understand behaviours by observing them within their natural setting.	Highly dependent on researcher interpretations and observations and observer bias may be hard to eliminate.

2.4 Suitable Research Methodologies

To answer the research questions, the most appropriate methodologies must be used for this study. The study was conducted within a school setting, while working with teachers and pupils and therefore it required methodologies that accommodated collaborative working between the researcher and those within school. For that purpose, Action research and Case study have been examined and will be examined in more depth to determine the most appropriate methodology for this study.

2.4.1 Action Research

Action research was first defined by Kurt Lewin in the 1940's in relation to his research investigating social issues in America. Lewin's original definition of action research "*consisted in analysis, fact-finding, conceptualisation, planning, execution, more fact-finding or evaluation; and then a repetition of this whole circle of activities; indeed a spiral of such circles*" (Dickens and Watkins, 1999). While Hult and Lennug (1980) define action research as an approach that "*...simultaneously assists in practical problem solving and expands scientific knowledge, as well as enhancing the competencies of the respective actors, being performed collaboratively in an immediate situation using data feed back in a cyclical process aiming at an increased understanding of a given social situation, primarily applicable for the understanding of change processes in social systems and undertaken within a mutually acceptable ethical framework.*"

For this study, the Reason and Bradbury (2006) definition was adopted. They state that action research is an approach used in studies "*which seeks both to inform and influence practice*".

Action research is participatory in nature and aims to improve society (Teddlie and Tashhakori, 2009). Action research is like other methods of research in that it is concerned with the development of new knowledge and understanding (Lawson, 2009) and employs methods used in other types of research such as questionnaires, interviews, diaries and observation. Action research integrates research and action in a series of flexible cycles of planning, acting and reflecting, involving data collection, data analysis and planning and the introduction of strategies to bring about changes. Lewin's model of action research presented by Dickens and Watkins (1999) shows the different stages of the cycle (Figure 2.1) as does Kemmis and McTaggart's model (Figure 2.2) and O'Leary's (Koshy, 2009:7) cycles of research (Figure 2.3). These models of action research show that while they have many similarities they do vary

and Koshy (2009) states that they should not be followed rigidly as this may indeed impact on the “*unique opportunity offered by the emerging nature and flexibility*” of action research. For example, although the Kemmis and McTaggart model has the exact same stages as the O’Leary model they are performed at different times. For this research the spiral action research model proposed by Kemmis and McTaggart (Koshy, 2009:5) will be considered. This provides the best opportunity to plan before undertaking the research within the schools and then act and observe on the research before reflecting to make changes before the next cycle of research begins.

Figure 2.1 – Lewin’s Action Research Model

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is Kemmis and McTaggart's Action Research Model. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 2.2 – Kemmis and McTaggart’s Action Research Model

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Figure 2.3 O'Leary's Action Research model

Within an educational setting action research can cover whole school improvement to gain a deeper understanding of an element of classroom behaviour and requires collaboration from the research community as well. It can also give a voice to the other groups within school such as teaching assistants, pupils and parents. This can lead to educational development within the class or school.

2.4.2 Case Study

Within the literature there are many definitions of what a case study is. For example, Stenhouse (1985) cited in Bassey (1999:25) defines a case study as “*the collection and recording of data about a case or cases*” and defines three broad terms for educational action, namely evaluative single case study, educational case study and case study in action research. Case study research

consists of a detailed investigation with data collection over a period within the context of the phenomenon being investigated (Cassell and Symon, 2004). Sturman (1994:26) cited in Bassey (1999) defines case study as being a “*generic term for the investigation of an individual group or phenomenon. It may involve both quantitative and qualitative methods with a belief that human systems develop a characteristic wholeness or integrity and are not simply a loose collection of beliefs.*”

For this study, however, the views of Yin (2009:18) will be adopted whereby a case study be a twofold technical definition. The first part states that a case study “*Investigates a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident*”. He then states that a case study copes with “*...the technically distinctive situation in which there will be many more variables of interest than data points, and as a result relies on multiple sources of evidence, with data needing to converge in a triangulating fashion, and as another result benefits from the prior development of theoretical propositions to guide data collection and analysis*”.

The case study can expose variables, events and responses that may otherwise be overlooked in an experiment. However, the case study can be subject to researcher bias that may distort the results (Gravetter and Foranzo, 2009), though with planning beforehand and fully informing participants as well as triangulating data collected this can be overcome (Miles and Huberman 1984). A case study observes the characteristics of a unit (the case) or even multiple cases. The case can be a single person, a group, school or community (Cohen and Mannion, 2007). Selecting the case(s) is the most critical step within the case study (Yin, 2009). A common misconception according to Yin is that the case represents “*a formal sample from some larger universe and that generalising from your case depends on some statistical inference*”. Yin (2009) identifies four different types of case study design shown in the Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Case Study Design types

Type	Description
Single case holistic design	A single case study may be employed when the case represents a critical case in testing a well formulated theory, the case can then be used to determine if the theories propositions are indeed correct or if there are more relevant explanations.
Single case embedded design	Within the case study there is an ability to investigate sub-units. This can be useful as the data within subunits can be analysed separately (within case analysis) <i>between</i> the different subunits (between case analysis), or <i>across</i> all the subunits (cross-case analysis).
Multiple case holistic design	Studying and comparing multiple cases in their totality.
Multiple case embedded design	Studying various units within identifiable cases.

Single case study design is common and when the case is unique, critical or revelatory is justifiable. However, when using multiple case study design evidence gathered can be more persuasive and as such is seen to be more robust. Determining the unit of analysis (case) can be a challenge for researchers and Miles and Huberman (1994) define the case as “*a phenomenon of some sort occurring in a bounded context*”. Authors including Stake (1995) and Yin (2003) suggest that placing boundaries on the case will ensure the study remains within scope. Binding the case can be achieved by (a) by time and place (Creswell, 2003); (b) time and activity (Stake, 1995); and (c) by definition and context (Miles and Huberman, 1994).

2.4.3 Summary

Both action research and case study have been considered and Table 2.4 summarises both methodologies summarising their advantages and disadvantages.

Table 2.4 Summary of Case Study and Action Research methodologies

	Action Research	Case study
Definition	A process of facilitating change.	An in-depth examination of a case.
Main characteristics	<p>Allows the researcher to find better ways of doing something through solving problems.</p> <p>Usually a collaborative effort between practitioners and researcher through the recurring process of action and critical reflection.</p>	<p>Allows researcher to gather data and try to understand why things happened the way they did and how change can be then brought about.</p> <p>In-depth study used to investigate a phenomenon, typically within “real life” settings.</p>
Advantages	<p>Bridges the gap between theory research and practise.</p> <p>Action research is an ongoing and practical process that allows educators to experience problem solving and model it to their students and colleagues.</p>	<p>Studying people in their natural settings can help better understand behaviour.</p> <p>By seeking to understand as much as possible about a single subject or small group of subjects, case studies specialise in a “thick description”. This emphasis can help bridge the gap between abstract research and concrete practice by allowing researchers to compare their first-hand observations with the quantitative results obtained through other methods of research.</p>
Disadvantages	<p>Possible conflicts between researcher and hierarchy within establishment.</p> <p>Results are not generalisable.</p>	<p>Incorrect interpretations can be caused by interpreter bias.</p> <p>Case studies are often seen to provide little basis for generalisation since they use a small number of subjects. They are also seen to be time consuming and difficult to conduct.</p>

2.5 Chosen Methodology

Action research is the chosen methodology to answer the research questions posed in Section 2.2 Action research provides a method of bringing about change within an establishment which the research is looking to bring about change within ICT lessons in Upper Primary Education. Action research is a collaborative effort between the researcher and those they are working with. This will be achieved by undertaking the research in stages with different classes in the upper primary school; the upper primary school consists of classes between Primary 4 and Primary 7 and the aim is to work in collaboration with the class teacher to see how their class works with Scratch and then develop a framework that teachers will then be able to use for themselves to introduce game making into their class without the researcher being directly involved. Figure 2.4 is based on Kemmis and McTaggart's (1982) action research model cited in Howden (1998) and demonstrates how the research develops. Before any work is undertaken in the class lessons must be planned and with the advice of class teachers approved. Once the lessons start (Study 1) the researcher will be the lead with class teachers shadowing. After this study has been undertaken the results from that and the literature review will provide an implementation framework that class teachers can then go on to use within Study 2. The results from Study 2 will then form a revised implementation framework.

Figure 2.4 Proposed Action Research model

2.6 Methods to Support Action Research

While action research is the overall methodology this section details methods that were used to help answer the research questions. The methods that will be used to help answer the research questions are literature review, questionnaire, participant observation and interviews.

2.6.1 Teacher Questionnaire

The purpose of the teacher questionnaire within this study was to help inform the research that was undertaken within primary schools. The main aim of the questionnaire was to gauge the use of games-based learning and games-based construction learning (GBCL) within primary

education. A further aim was to find teachers who would like to participate in the study. The survey consists of closed questions with a few open-ended questions. The survey was available online for completion on SurveyMonkey and a link was distributed through email to head teachers of primary schools within Glasgow for them to pass on to their staff to complete. The questionnaires will be analysed by way of descriptive statistics and Mann-Whitney *U* tests.

2.6.2 Lesson Evaluations

Lesson evaluations were used with the children to evaluate their enjoyment of the lessons. This took the form of two statements based on a five-point Likert scale asking how they felt about their lessons. The evaluations were performed after every lesson for each participant. The aim of this was to gauge if children are enjoying the work they are doing with Scratch and to identify any differences in stages of the upper school with enjoyment of Scratch.

2.6.3 Teacher Interviews

Structured interviews took place with the teachers before, during and after the research study. The interviews were used to determine how teachers felt about the introduction of GBCL into their class and what benefits or drawbacks they see to using GBCL in the class. The interviews will determine whether their views change over the course of the research.

2.6.4 Observation

Observation will be used in class to determine how the children are progressing with the tasks given each week. It will be used to note if there are any problems with lessons either in delivery or understanding of them. This informed the next set of lessons and helped improve overall the delivery. It will also be used to determine how any teachers who lead the classes manage during their lessons. By having another method of collecting information about the class this can be used to further strengthen the triangulation of results gathered during the study. While deciding on what type of observation it is important to note the differences between participant observation and non-participant observation, each having advantages and disadvantages of being used. Table 2.4 (Cohen and Mannion, 2007) shows the types of observation and advantages and disadvantages of each. For this study overt participant observation was used when observing within the class.

Table 2.4 Observation Types

	Definition	Advantages	Disadvantages
Participant observation	Studying behaviours in their natural setting. Used to produce qualitative data.	Can assist children in their daily activities.	Developing strong relationships. Observing unacceptable behaviour.
Overt Participant Observation	The researcher becomes part of the group when studying and group members are aware of the researcher's identity.	Researcher gets first-hand experience within the group.	The researcher may be seen as intrusive.
Covert Participant Observation	The researcher becomes part of the group when studying while group members are unaware of the researcher's identity.	When information is given it can be recorded by the researcher.	Information given to the researcher may be private and therefore it cannot be reported on.
Non-participant Observation	The researcher sits in the background not interacting with the people being observed in their natural settings without their knowledge.	Can be useful for providing insights into real world behaviour.	Researcher must ensure they are not disrupting the behaviour they are observing.

2.6.5 Statistical Analysis Techniques

The statistical analysis techniques used to evaluate the data gathered from the questionnaires, children's evaluations and game coding included: descriptive statistics (N, mean, standard deviation, etc.) and inferential statistics which will either be parametric or non-parametric depending on the exploratory analysis performed. When deciding upon the statistical analysis techniques to use in a research study it is important to consider whether the data collected is parametric or non-parametric. Parametric tests assume three main things about the data: firstly, that each sample of scores is taken from a population distribution that is normal; secondly, the populations are assumed to have the same variance and thirdly the data must be measured at

an interval or ratio level. In comparison, non-parametric tests, make fewer and weaker assumptions and do not rely on random sampling of the population (Hunter and May, 1993). The statistical analysis techniques chosen for this research study project will depend on the results of the exploratory analysis and will be parametric if the data conforms to the three pieces of criteria for parametric tests described above or non-parametric if the data fails to conform to all three pieces of criteria. If the data conforms to the criteria for parametric tests, then dependent and independent *t*-tests will be used for analysis otherwise the non-parametric equivalents will be used; i.e. Mann-Whitney *U* tests.

2.7 Methods Selected to Answer Research Questions

2.7.1 Research Methodologies Selected to Answer Research Question 1

RQ1: What empirical evidence is associated with games-based learning at Primary Education (PE) level and how does it compare with the views of PE level teachers in Scotland?

The methodologies selected to answer Research Question 1 were: Archival and survey methods. A literature review was used to identify empirical evidence of games-based learning in primary schools using a number of electronic databases : ACM, Science Direct, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Computer Society Digital Library (CSDL), Taylor and Francis, Proquest (including Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts, Proquest Computing and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses AandI), EBSCO (including CINAHL PsycINFO, SocINDEX, Library, Information Science and Technology Abstracts), Cambridge Journals, ERIC, Ingenta, Infotrac and Web of Knowledge. The following search terms derived from a previous search on the evaluation of computer games will be used (Connolly, Stansfield and Hailey, 2007):

("computer games" OR "video games" OR "serious games" OR "simulation games" OR "games-based learning" OR "MMOG" OR "MMORPG" OR "M.U.D." OR "online games") AND (evaluation OR impacts OR outcomes OR effects OR learning OR education OR skills OR behaviour OR attitude OR engagement OR motivation OR affect)

A survey of primary school teachers was undertaken in the Glasgow City Council region of Scotland. It was distributed to head teachers of all primary schools in Glasgow for forwarding onto their teaching staff to complete the questionnaire at their leisure, if they wish. The aim of the survey is to identify if primary school teachers are using games or game making tools as part of their class lessons. The survey was designed to achieve the following objectives:

1. To gauge the current use of games-based learning (GBL) at primary schools in Scotland.
2. To identify GBL products that have been used in the classroom or are known to teachers.
3. To gauge teachers' opinions on using GBL.
4. To find teachers who are interested in participating in further evaluation.

The survey was split into the following sections:

1. Demographic information: age, gender, class year taught, school name
2. Use of computer games and game making tools in the classroom:
 - Games played in class
 - Game making tools used
 - Subject the game was used to help teach
 - Advantages and disadvantages of games and game making in the class.
3. Personal opinions on using GBL including:
 - Motivations for using GBL: Teachers were asked to state their agreement on factors that would motivate them to use a GBL approach in their class.
 - Reasons for playing games: Malone and Lepper's (1987) framework was used to examine the reasons for playing computer games.
 - Attitudes to computer games: Teachers were asked about their general attitudes to computer games and asked to rate as to how strongly they agreed with each attitude. A previous survey undertaken within higher education (Hailey, Connolly and Boyle 2009) included motivations, reasons and attitudes to playing games and this section of the survey has been adapted for use with primary teachers.
 - Benefits of GBL within the CfE: Teachers were asked about how suitable they felt GBL could be within the CfE.
 - Obstacles faced when using GBL: Teachers were asked about the obstacles they faced and how they rated them as a factor in delivering GBL.

The population had been identified as primary teachers within Glasgow. The collected results will be analysed using non-parametric tests namely Mann-Whitney *U* tests and descriptive statistics. These have been selected as the data collected will be ordinal.

2.7.2 Research Methodologies Selected to Answer Research Question 2

RQ2: What framework could be used to implement game construction using Scratch within the Curriculum for Excellence at upper school PE level?

The methodology selected to answer Research Question 3 was: Archival. A literature review was used to identify any existing frameworks for implementing game making with Scratch in primary schools using a number of electronic databases: ACM, Science Direct, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Computer Society Digital Library (CSDL), Taylor and Francis, Proquest (including Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts, Proquest Computing and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses AandI), EBSCO (including CINAHL PsycINFO, SocINDEX, Library, Information Science and Technology Abstracts), Cambridge Journals, ERIC, Ingenta, Infotrac and Web of Knowledge.

(making OR construction OR building OR design OR creation”) AND (game AND framework) AND Scratch

If any frameworks are found, then through the teacher interviews their suitability for implementing within school can be evaluated. The interviews would determine if schools had the capability to meet the needs whether it is technical, or skills related for the given framework. It will consider the teachers' views on exactly how feasible it would be to get implemented in their school, then it would be trialled in a pilot study. If no framework is found, then a framework will be developed from a further literature search surrounding game construction in upper primary education undertaken in Research Question 2 that will identify studies using Scratch in primary education along with the data gathered in Research Question 2.

2.7.3 Research Methodologies Selected to Answer Research Question 3

RQ3: How do the different levels of upper school PE make use of Scratch and how can their work be evaluated?

The methodology selected to answer Research Question 2 was Action Research using the design detailed in this section. The researcher engaged with interested schools and worked with classes within the upper primary school to help deliver lessons using Scratch. These lessons were incorporated into the classes' normal weekly timetable. The objectives of the lessons were:

1. To put game making into practise in the classroom setting by using materials designed specifically for the lessons. These lessons will be in collaboration with the teachers in the schools the researcher will be working in.
2. To evaluate the affective reactions of children and their use of game making tools, children were given a log sheet to complete at the end of each lesson with a five-point Likert scale. The collected results were analysed using non-parametric tests namely Mann-Whitney *U* tests and descriptive statistics. These were selected as the data collected will not be gathered from a random sampling of children as all children in the given classes will be participating.
3. To evaluate teachers' opinions of game making before, during and after use in the class, the class teachers will be interviewed. The class teachers from participating schools will be interviewed before, during (midway point) and after the lessons to gain their thoughts and expectations about the study. The interview before the lessons start was used to determine the teachers' thoughts on GBL in the class and what has already been done in class in the way of computing lessons and how or even if the CfE has changed this with the introduction of GBL into the curriculum. The second interview was held halfway through the lessons to gauge teachers' views about the progression of the lessons and if they are able to see any benefits/drawbacks to the lessons. The final interview took place after all lessons have been delivered. The teachers were questioned as to how they thought the lessons went and how they felt the children in the class performed in these lessons. It will also determine whether their opinions have changed over the course of the study.
4. A journal of all class visits will be kept by the researcher to record class activities.

The data that was collected during the class lessons will be teacher interviews, children's evaluations of the lessons, assessment of the games created throughout the study and a journal of each class lesson kept by the researcher. This was then be triangulated to build a picture of how Scratch is used in the class, not only to see if the children enjoy their lessons with it but also whether it is found to be of use by the class teacher in delivering lessons It was also used alongside Research Question 2 to develop an implementation framework. The teachers were interviewed before, during and after the lessons have taken place to gain their opinions of how they think the lessons are going, how their class is coping with them and how they could use Scratch in the future for their lessons to fit in with cross-curricular work. The children in the class were asked each week to evaluate the lessons to show how much they enjoyed them. While the researcher kept a journal of all class visits to determine how the class is progressing

and any problems or areas that are working well which can be further refined in following stages.

A literature review was carried out to identify previous game making educational research studies and how they were performed in PE. A number of electronic databases will be searched including: ACM, Science Direct, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Computer Society Digital Library (CSDL), Taylor and Francis, Proquest (including Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts, Proquest Computing and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses A and I), EBSCO (including CINAHL PsycINFO, SocINDEX, Library, Information Science and Technology Abstracts), Cambridge Journals, ERIC, Ingenta, Infotrac and Web of Knowledge. The following search terms will be used:

(making OR construction OR building OR design OR creation) AND

(game AND education)

To evaluate the games created during the study a game coding scheme was developed. A literature review was undertaken to identify any game coding schemes used when constructing games with Scratch. If none are found, then the search will be extended to other game construction environments and adapted for the Scratch environment. The game coding scheme will be used to evaluate the games based on the game's final design and will examine the programming concepts used within the game.

Alexandra Parade Primary, Carntyne Primary and Royston Primary schools participated in the study. Alexandra Parade had 8 classes in their upper school with around 160 children between Primary 4 and Primary 7. Royston Primary had 3 classes in their upper school participating with around 60 children between them. Carntyne Primary had one class in the upper school participating with 27 children. Within the second stage of the study both Royston Primary and Carntyne Primary participated. Children's evaluations of the lessons and the games produced by the children at the end of the study will also be important to validate the work undertaken by the class teacher.

2.8 Establishing Trustworthiness

Determining trustworthiness within the study is important to provide confidence that the research and related results are credible. Within a positivist research paradigm trustworthiness is achieved through:

- Internal validity is defined by Cook and Campbell (1979) as the “*approximate validity [the best available approximation of the truth or falsity of a statement] with which we infer that a relationship between two variables is casual or that the absence of a relationship implies the absence of a cause*”. Given a variety of factors may influence the outcome they should be controlled for or randomised within the design.
- External validity is defined as “*the approximate validity with which we infer that the presumed causal relationship can be generalised to and across alternate measures of the cause and effect across different types of person, settings and times*” (Cook and Campbell, 1979).
- Reliability according to Kerlinger (cited in Guba and Lincoln 1985:292) is synonymous with “*dependability, stability, consistency, predictably, accuracy*”. It is seen as a precondition to validity since measurements that are unreliable are not then valid (Guba and Lincoln, 1985). It is usually tested by replication for example by using the test-retest
- Objectivity according to Guba and Lincoln (1985) is “*if multiple observers can agree on a phenomenon their collective judgment can be said to be objective*”. By performing experiments objectivity can be established.

However, Guba and Lincoln (1985) argue that the positivist methods of establishing trustworthiness are not appropriate for research within a natural environment and they suggest four alternative criteria that should be addressed to achieve trustworthiness namely credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability. Table 2.5 adapted from (Guba and Lincoln 1985, Miles and Huberman 1994, Merriam 2009) examines techniques suitable for verifying the procedures. To establish trustworthiness within this study Table 2.6 shows the techniques that will be used.

Table 2.5 Techniques for Trustworthiness Verification

	Comparable to	Techniques for verification
Credibility	Internal validity	Triangulation – using multiple sources of data to confirm findings. Member checks – Taking data back to people involved within the study and determining if the data is plausible.
Transferability	External Validity	Thick description - contextualising the study for the reader to ascertain the extent to which the

		research content matches the situation, therefore determining if the findings can be transferred.
Dependability	Reliability	Peer review- The process of study is discussed with colleagues.
Confirmability	Objectivity	Audit trail – The methods, procedures and discussions in carrying out the study are provided in a detailed account

Table 2.6 Establishing Trustworthiness

	Technique to be used within study	How will this be achieved
Credibility	Member checks Triangulation	Checks will be done with the class teachers after then lessons to confirm the observations that were made during the lesson. By using the observations along with teacher interviews and children’s evaluations of the lessons.
Transferability	Thick description	To provide a rich, thick description of the research performed detailing characteristics such as the context of the study, the participants and research findings.
Dependability	Peer review	This will involve the researcher asking academic colleagues to review the work performed in this study and recommend whether the findings are credible based on the data.
Confirmability	Audit Trail	A clear explanation for the choices that were made throughout the duration of the study will be provided. In doing so, this will allow others to follow what was done.

2.9 Ethics

BERA (2011) offer ethical guidelines for undertaking research in education, these were consulted prior to and during the research study. Parts of the research study involve children and will be conducted in a school setting; therefore, it is extremely important to ensure that the process conforms to the guidelines offered with a focus on the qualitative methods and on questions of confidentiality, informed consent and minimization of harm. Prior to commencing the school fieldwork, ethical approval was sought for the research and given by the university (See Appendix 1). In addition to this ethical approval was sought from Glasgow City Council for the researcher to enter working with schools (See Appendix 2). The key ethical issues considered by the researcher prior to commencing the research were completed in an application form for ethical approval. When interacting with human subjects in any field of research it is important to ensure that ethical approval is granted (Wisker, 2008). The key ethical issues of anonymity, confidentiality, privacy of the respondent and how the data will be stored were addressed before contacting the school. A key area of research ethics is the concept of anonymity (Oliver, 2003). The respondents will remain anonymous during the research process and anonymisation procedures will be used throughout the research. Respondent names will be removed and will be referred to either by numbers, letters or fictional names. The data obtained during the research will remain confidential and will be stored and backed up on the researcher's computer. Access to these records will be password protected. In addition to ethical approval, membership of the Protection of Vulnerable Groups was obtained to be able to work with primary school children in Scotland (See Appendix 3).

2.10 Summary

This chapter has defined the objectives of the research and then defined the research questions that need to be answered. It covered various research methods to answer each of the research questions and then selected the most appropriate methods for answering those questions. The main methods selected to answer the questions are action research, archival and survey methods. Given that the research involves working with children ethical considerations were closely investigated and followed to ensure that the correct procedures are followed, and the research can go ahead within the schools. Finally given the different methods that are going to be undertaken a discussion on trustworthiness looks at ensuring the research is credible.

3 Literature Review

3.1 Games-Based Learning (GBL)

Playing computer games is a popular activity for children with almost 66% of 5 to 15-year olds playing games at home on a console (OFCOM, 2016). Using games within the classroom has the potential for supporting learning (Gee, 2003; Kirriemuir and MacFarlane, 2003). The most common reasons for using games in the class are motivation (Gee 2003; Klawe, 1994) and engagement (Williamson, 2009). Gee (2003) argues that when playing computer games people are learning and that good computer games can incorporate up to 36 learning principles. This approach to learning is known as games-based learning and defined by Tang, Hannegan and Rhalibi (2009) as “*the innovative learning approach derived from the use of computer games that possess educational value or different kinds of software applications that use games for learning and education purposes such as learning support, teaching enhancement, assessment and evaluation of learners*”.

While there has been an increase in the amount of literature on the use of games in the classroom there is little in the way of empirical evidence to support the use of games in the class as a recognised approach to learning (Connolly et al., 2012). Dondlinger (2007) discusses various learning theories for using game namely constructivism, situated learning and constructionism. Constructivist learning is viewed as learners reorganising previously acquired knowledge and constructing new skills and knowledge (De Corte, 2011). Learning with well designed video games can be viewed as a constructivist activity as researchers have found they adhere to the principles of constructivist learning (Dondlinger, 2007).

Situated learning provides learning in a meaningful context and Halverson, Shaffer, Squire and Steinkhueler (2006 cited in Dondlinger 2007) state that video games can engage players in an authentic environment.

Constructing mental models to help learners understand the world around them is the underlying principle of constructionist learning theory and Robertson and Good (2005), Robertson and Howells (2007) apply the constructionist approach to learning through their research by letting children design and develop their own games rather than learning through playing games.

Van Eck (2006) suggests from a review of the literature that there are three ways of introducing GBL into educational establishments either through the students creating their own games, through the students playing computer games that their teachers have created or using Commercial off the Shelf (COTS) games.

The focus of this thesis is on researching students creating their own games. For a review of the literature on GBL the reader is directed to Hainey, Connolly, Boyle, Wilson and Razak (2016) which showed that GBL had been used to teach a variety of subjects in PE with mathematics, science, language and social studies being the most popular. However, there was a lack of longitudinal studies as well as Randomised Controlled Trials (RCT) which should be carried out to ascertain if GBL is a suitable for teaching in PE.

3.2 Games-Based Construction Learning (GCBL)

Papert's theory of constructionism regards learning as a process in which the learner actively constructs his or her knowledge by interacting with the subject matter. The constructionist perspective puts game construction in the hands of children to encourage their knowledge through developing objects (Papert, 1991). In the game construction approach, the aim of the game construction tool is to support such an activity by providing an appropriate environment. Kafai (2006) suggested that constructionists have focused their efforts on providing students with greater opportunities to construct their own games and to construct new relationships with knowledge in the process, rather than embedding lessons directly in games. By adapting the definition of GBL given by Tang, Hannegan and Rhalibi (2009) (see Section 3.1), GBCL can be defined as "*an innovative learning approach that uses appropriate tools to allow games to be constructed to support learning and teaching*".

A literature review was carried out to identify previous game making educational research using a number of electronic databases: ACM, Science Direct, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Computer Society Digital Library (CSDL), Taylor and Francis, Proquest (including Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts, Proquest Computing and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses A and I), EBSCO (including CINAHL PsycINFO, SocINDEX, Library, Information Science and Technology Abstracts), Cambridge Journals, ERIC, Ingenta, Infotrac and Web of Knowledge. The following search terms were used:

(making OR construction OR building OR design OR creation) AND

(game AND education)

Kafai's *Minds in Play* (1995) is viewed as a notable piece of work within games construction. The study looked at children as game designers over a six-month period and investigated how they developed as learners during this time. Over this period for one hour a day, 16 children aged 9-10 years worked together with the researcher and their class teacher to create fraction games in Logo. Kafai argued that by using designing games children can start to construct their own knowledge and their relationship to it. By taking Kafai's ground-breaking research as a starting point the literature search started from 1995 onwards. The initial search collated 2,141 entries in total. By focusing on empirical work undertaken with games construction within education this reduced the search to 42 papers, which were then categorised into primary, secondary, further/higher and after school/summer camp. Table 3.2 provides an overview of the number of papers found relating to each educational setting and what games construction tools were used. It also gives a breakdown of the number of studies undertaken given that some papers covered different areas of the same study.

As can be seen, GBCL is still an emerging field in all areas of education, with after school settings/summer camps being the most popular setting for studies undertaken. The ten papers found (see Table 3.3) related to primary education cover seven studies and the games constructed within these papers fall into two categories: a) the children making the games are creating educational games for other children to use (Baytak, 2019; Baytak and Land 2011; Kafai, 1995; Kafai, Franke, Ching and Shih, 1998; Owston, 2009; Kafai and Ching, 1996; Vos, van der Meijden and Denessen, 2011; Koutsikos et al, 2012); b) the children are creating their own games (Robertson and Howells, 2008; Robertson, 2012).

Table 3.2 Empirical papers found

	Number of papers	Number of Studies	Tools used
Primary Education	10	6	Logo, Scratch, Adventure Author, Software created by De Digitale School, Kodu, Education Games Central
Secondary Education	8	7	Gamemaker, Neverwinter Nights, Microworlds EX, 7 Scenes, Unity, Agent sheets, Gamemaker, flip
Further/Higher Education	9	9	Alice, Gamemaker, C++/OpenGL, Unity, XNA, Agentsheets,

After-school or Summer camps	15	15	Alice, Scratch, Greenfoot, Unreal, Warcraft III, Gamemaker, devkitPro, Flash, Neverwinter Nights, Stagecast creator
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Table 3.3 GBCL literature

Authors	Software used	Age of children	Number of participants	Curricular Area
Kafai (1995)	Logo	10-11	16	Mathematics
Kafai, Franke, Ching and Shih (1998); Kafai and Ching (1996)	Logo	11-12	4	Mathematics
Robertson and Howells (2008)	Adventure Author	9-10	6	Technologies
Baytak and Land (2011); Baytak (2009)	Scratch	10-11	10	Science
Owston et al (2010)	Education Games Central	9-10	311	Languages
Vos, van der Meijden and Denessen (2011)	De Digitale School	10-12	235	Languages
Robertson (2012)	Adventure Author	11-12	25	Cross curricular
Koutsikos et al (2012)	Kodu	11-12	25	Social Studies

As can be seen from table 3.3 most of the studies undertaken did not involve large amounts of children participating and instead focused more on small groups working on creating their games over a period of time such as Kafai's (1995) study that investigated game design as a learning environment with a 4th grade (Primary 6) class creating fraction games for younger children. A similar smaller study with four 5th graders was then undertaken (Kafai and Ching, 1996; Kafai Franke, Ching and Shih, 1998) . While Baytak (2009) examined a case study of Scratch being used with ten 5th grade (Primary 7) children in a science class who spent a period of 23 school days creating science-based games to learn more about environmental studies. Both studies showed that children were able to create their own games, with more sophisticated games being developed over time.

While Robertson and Howells (2008) led a short term exploratory study into the use of game making within a class of 30 Primary 6 (9-10 year olds) children to develop aspects of the successful learner strand of the CfE (Section 3.6 explains this in more detail). The study used the Adventure Author software and was conducted over eight 2-hour lessons and was led by one of three researchers and supported by the class teacher along with the school's ICT teacher. Following on from this Robertson (2012) undertook a further study using Adventure Author over a 6-week period with a class of 11-12 year olds, which looked at the analysis of games created by children during the project and focused on gender issues within the class. The children's games were then analysed, and results showed that girls scored higher than boys in the storytelling aspects of their games. The results also demonstrated that children can construct their own games although more awareness of players' needs had to be recognised when constructing the games and teacher observations had shown the children had enjoyed working with Adventure Author.

Owston et al. (2009) conducted an experimental study using games design as a literacy activity. They investigated the use of Educational Games Central game shell, which children used to create their own quiz games for the study. Although unlike other games construction studies the children in this study did not have to learn any programming. Eighteen classes of children from nine schools participated in the study with two classes from each school (one being the experimental the other the control group). The study sought to investigate the benefits of using games design as a literacy activity with the experimental group using the game shell. The lessons were led by class teachers who were given half a day's training with the software before the study commenced. Children had to pick a type of game, for example tic tac toe or snakes and ladders, they then input a series of questions to the game shell that then were used during the game to help the player make moves. The children were given a standardised reading and a student written test before and after the study was conducted. While the results of the standardised reading test showed no significant difference between the experimental and control groups the students' written test did show a significant improvement for the experimental group.

Vos, van der Meijen and Denessen (2011) used an experimental approach within their study and compared game playing to game creating. The software used in the study was created specifically for it. One group of children used the software to create drag-and-drop games based on Dutch proverbs while the other group of children played drag-and-drop proverb games that had already been constructed for the study. The researcher took all lessons within four

elementary schools with 235 students from 9 classes split over 5th/6th grade aged 10-12 years. 5 classes constructed the games and 4 classes played the games. The study compared the motivation of students who played games with the motivations of students who created games. The study found that children who created games were more motivated in their learning than those who simply played the computer games.

Koutiskos et al. (2012) used Kodu within a pilot study of games design in a primary school with 25 children who were asked to design games based on an environmental theme. The objective of the pilot study was to introduce the principles of object-oriented programming to the children by using Kodu and to assess the satisfaction and interest generated through this. The study took place over a period of three months in the children's geography classes and they worked in groups of three, four or five. Children completed questionnaires and the results indicated that Kodu was very well received by the children and most would try it at home.

A lack of teacher led lessons for games construction in the class is apparent as the studies have shown that there has been a great deal of researcher involvement in facilitating lessons within the schools as most of the studies undertaken have been case studies or exploratory work.

3.3 Programming and Computational thinking

Seymour Papert's vision that children should be programming the computer rather than being programmed by the computer through computer aided learning (Papert, 1980). To some extent almost thirty years on the children are still being programmed by the computer. Children are being given drill and practice packages to work with that aren't engaging them in any way (Stuart, 2005) Since Logo was created many others have tried to get children programming with various other languages (Kahn, 2007). Papert himself said that Logo would be overtaken by other environments which will be first class (Papert, 1980) however none really seem to capture the imagination of that generation (Kahn, 2007; Kelleher, Pausch 2005; McNerney, 2004). Why then if this is so, should children be taught to program and what are the benefits they gain from taking part in programming?

According to Resnick et al (Resnick et al. 2009) programming offers mathematical, problem solving and more knowledge of how computers work. Programming also offers benefits to students including improved higher-order thinking skills and positive computing experiences at a younger age (Maya et al, 2015).

As well as programming skills, there has been a lot of discussions surrounding Computational thinking a phrase that was defined as “solving problems, designing systems and understanding of human behaviour, using the fundamental concepts of computer science” (Wing, 2006). Maya et al (2015) notes also that computational thinking concepts are fundamental to programming and this thesis shall use the term computational thinking as the authors Wing (2006 and Maya et al (2015) have done so seeing programming as part of computational thinking. Computational thinking and programming have become more popular within education across countries such as United Kingdom, Estonia and Finland (Sáez-López, Román-González, and Vázquez-Cano, 2016) and there is a growing interest in learning to code given the benefits of logical thinking to students.

While there are numerous tools available for teaching programming a lot of the block based visual programming, tools are based on Scratch. This thesis will focus on Scratch as the programming tool for use in schools. Scratch is based on the constructivist learning ideas (Sáez-López, Román-González, and Vázquez-Cano, 2016) and influences can be seen from Logo work (Papert, 1980). With the objectives of the lessons to have the children construct their own games it was also felt that Scratch was very suitable for taking a constructivist approach to learning. It is a freely available visual-based tool and children are encouraged to create programs by simply snapping together the blocks provided to create their own program or script, as it is known in Scratch. Figure 3.1 shows the Scratch interface.

Figure 3.1: Scratch

Brennan and Resnick (2012) have developed a computational thinking framework for Scratch and discuss how Scratch can provide context and opportunities for developing those skills.

Though it was noted that the authors felt that more had to be investigated to articulate their framework. They have identified seven key concepts that are extremely useful in Scratch projects, but which also map to other programming and non-programming concepts which are:

- Sequences: A task is expressed as a list of steps or instructions.
- Loops: A concept used to repeat a sequence of instructions as many times as needed.
- Parallelism (Threads): A concept that involves multiple actions happening at the same time e.g. two characters moving on screen at the same time.
- Events: A concept used when we want something to make another thing happen e.g. when this green flag is clicked the character will move.
- Conditionals: A concept that is based on a series of decisions based on any given condition.
- Operators: used to provide support for logical, mathematical and string expressions.
- Data (variables and lists): A way of storing, retrieving and updating values which can be done either through lists or variables e.g. creating a score variable that updates when objectives are met in the game.

3.4 GBCL with Scratch

Another literature search was undertaken to determine if Scratch has been used within educational settings. The search was carried out using the electronic databases ACM, IEEE and Science Direct and using the Scratch site itself, which contained research papers from authors within the Scratch project.

Scratch is primarily aimed at children aged around eight, however, statistics from the Scratch site show that the average age of users is 12 (MIT, 2015) and there is a wide age range of users for this tool. It was envisaged from the outset that while this project was to introduce computers to deprived areas eventually the informal educational benefits of it would be studied later (Resnick, Kafai and Maeda, 2003). Although Scratch has been used in formal education (Malan and Leitner, 2007; Malan, 2010), there is currently little published research on whether Scratch can be used as a tool for teaching programming concepts in a primary classroom setting. Research has focused on the community around Scratch that has been built up since its introduction. Brennan, Resnick and Monroy-Hernández (2010) discuss how Scratch is used by the online Scratch community with participants ranging from socialisers through to creators of projects while Monroy-Hernández and Resnick (2008) discuss the collaborative nature of the

community and how groups of users are starting to set up their own “miniature companies” to produce games of high quality. While Quan (2015) investigated how student teachers integrated Scratch into their teaching of a foreign language to their classes.

Adams (2010) looked at the use of Scratch during a five-day summer camp with 30 boys and 15 girls aged 13 and above. The children were given the chance to create either multimedia videos or games with Scratch and out of the 45 children who attended only three did not make games. The results showed that the children all reported that they thoroughly enjoyed working with Scratch with the girls scoring the camp either very good or good in their opinions of their camp enjoyment. Sivilotti and Laugel (2008) undertook out-of-school workshops with thirty 13-14 year olds to gauge their opinions on Scratch when learning to program. The results indicated that the students’ enjoyed working with Scratch and felt that they had come away from the workshop knowing more about programming and wanting to learn more by continuing to use Scratch outside of the workshop. Studies such as Maloney et al. (2008) focused on what blocks had used over an extended period in Scratch projects during an after-school computer clubhouse which was open to children aged 8-18 years. Over a period of 18 months children worked on games and animations in the clubhouse and Scratch was shown to be the most popular software for the children to use to create their projects. By analysing the projects created during this time the most common programming concepts used were User Interaction (key handling), Loops (iteration) and Conditional Statement and over time children started discovering more concepts to use in their projects namely variables, random numbers and Boolean logic.

Within educational establishments and during lesson time, projects such as those described by Wilson, Connolly, Hainey and Moffat (2011) show how Scratch can be used with young children aged 8-9 years to learn programming concepts through the introduction of game making. Children were given eight lessons to introduce them to programming and to gauge how much they enjoyed working with Scratch. The results indicated that even after a short period of time all children in the class could learn some programming concepts. Baytak and Land (2011) in their study focused on learning by design where 10-11 year old children planned and designed and then created their games with Scratch during a science project. The results showed that by undertaking this project not only did children learn how to create their own science games which also increased knowledge of science and gave them a new way of learning more about science facts. At Harvard University Scratch has been used as an introduction to programming for new undergraduate students (Malan and Leitner, 2007; Malan, 2010). This

entailed students developing Scratch projects as part of the introductory lessons to introduce programming concepts to help prepare them for using Java. For the students who had never programmed before, the results indicated that using Scratch was of benefit to them when they started undertaking programming in Java, however, for the students who had previous programming experience it was not as beneficial for them to use Scratch. Ferrer-Mico, Prats-Fernandez and Redo-Sanchez (2012) undertook a study with two groups of children aged 12-13 years in school to investigate self-directed learning through programming activities using Scratch as part of their maths lessons. The results showed that the students felt that by using Scratch over a period they could increase their confidence and knowledge in programming, however, the researchers did find that less than half of the students felt properly engaged with Scratch.

3.5 Difficulties & Attitudes in CS

The development of introductory computer science courses has been the subject of much research worldwide (Berge et al, 2003, Pears et al, 2007, Schulte, Bennedsen, 2006). Within introductory programming students face difficulties such as the abstract thinking involved within the introductory course (Lahtinen et al, 2005) This can lead to elevated levels of failure within introductory courses for programming (Gomes & Mendes, 2007, Lahtinen et al, 2005). However, with computers becoming more prevalent in schools it is not just at university level where the problems appear indeed many students come into these programs with prior experience (Lahtinen et al, 2005); after all programming is part of the school curriculum and should be familiar to them. Unfortunately depending on which Local authority the school is based in can depend on what children are taught and some leave it to individual schools. This is where problems can occur. Even from primary school when basic programming should be introduced some teachers lack the confidence with technology (Stuart, 2005) and rely on the packages they are given to work with. Other factors which may put the children off are also the equipment that they must use for their work sometimes not in the best of condition (Straker et al, 2000). This leads on to how students of all ages feel about computers. Most studies though on this are gender related and look at misconceptions that girls may have on computer science as a subject (Papastergiou, 2008, Siann et al, 1990). Rather than giving the bigger picture of how boys and girls are feeling about computers in general. They also show however that boys may be more confident with computers (Mumtaz, 2001) and that both genders spend longer time on different tasks, boys - games and girls – emails.

3.6 Game Construction Tools for Children

Since the development of Logo (the first programming language for children) in 1967, there have been many other programming tools attempting to encourage children/novice programmers. The Toontalk programming environment has a video game-like style (see Figure 3.2) with animations within it symbolising programming attributes; e.g. a house in Toontalk represents an object or actor in programming (Kahn, 1996) and has been used in a study with pre-school (3-5 years) children (Morgado, Cruz and Kahn, 2003) to introduce them to programming. The study investigated the use of a programming environment with very young children the results were shown to be inconclusive with more research needing to be undertaken. The research also showed at that age the children found concepts such as sequencing to be a challenging task.

Figure 3.2 Toontalk environment

Adventure Author (Figure 3.3) is another example of a programming tool designed to make games and is aimed at children aged 10-14 (Robertson and Good, 2005). The tool enables children to create their own interactive story, which other children are then able to play. This is also similar to Storytelling Alice, see Figure 3.4 (Kelleher, Pausch and Kiesler, 2007), which was used as an approach to try to encourage girls to develop an interest in computer programming and is based on Alice (a freeware object-oriented educational programming language). A between subjects' study was carried out with 88 girls (average age 12.6 years) in an out of school setting and the girls were given time on both Alice and then Storytelling Alice (or vice versa depending on the group they were assigned to). The results indicated that although both environments were beneficial for learning programming concepts the girls

showed more engagement with Storytelling Alice and were more likely to spend extra time programming with it than what they did when they were using Alice.

Figure 3.3 Adventure Author

Figure 3.4 Storytelling Alice

Kodu (Fowler, Fristoe and McLaurin 2012) is a game construction environment (Figure 3.5) that was created by Microsoft. It can be used either on Xboxes (for a small charge) or PC for free and games can be constructed easily with the use of the keyboard or a game controller and is designed for children aged 8 and older. Research has been limited to pilot studies (Koutiskos et al, 2012; Touretsky, 2014) that have demonstrated the use of Kodu in the primary classroom and the teaching of introductory programming. Both studies, however, found that even within limited time children were starting to pick up some simple programming concepts such as rule structure, syntax and conditions by using Kodu.

Figure 3.5 Kodu environment

3.7 Curriculum for Excellence

The Scottish Government has over the past few years reviewed the Scottish curriculum and a revised curriculum – the Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) was implemented in Scottish schools

in the 2010/2011 school session. This reform of education is one of the biggest Scotland has seen and intends to provide a coherent curriculum for children from 3 years through to 18 years (Scottish Executive, 2008). The intention of this new curriculum is to change the balance of content within the curriculum from one that is reliant on content and learning and teaching approaches to one that improves understanding of what is being taught to the pupils (Florian and Rouse, 2009).

The curriculum is built upon a set of experiences and outcomes that take into consideration all curriculum areas as well as interdisciplinary projects and includes the school and community as well to help develop them. However, these standards are self-evaluated by each educational establishment and children's progress does not seem to be measurable by any form of standardised tests, more so within early/primary education (Geddes, Frank and Haw, 2011). It is tailored to encompass the all-round needs of learners from the age of 3-18 years old and develop important skills for learning, work and life (Education Scotland, 2011a).

The skills are developed through the four capacities to ensure all children become:

1. Confident individuals
2. Effective contributors
3. Responsible citizens
4. Successful learners

These four capacities are expanded further to give outcomes of what children should be able to achieve through their education (Education Scotland, 2011b) and can be used by teachers to help in planning learning for the children through the eight curricular areas, namely, Languages, Mathematics, Science, Health and Wellbeing, Religious and Moral Education, Social Studies, Expressive Arts and Technologies. It intends to provide children the "knowing how" rather than the "knowing what" to build up these four capacities (Florian and Rouse, 2009).

3.8 Summary

While GBCL is becoming more popular within the primary education there is still a dearth of empirical evidence. A lack of research within GBCL at all levels of education has been identified and while there are many different tools available for use to teach GBCL not much research has been undertaken to show the benefits of them within school at PE level. Scratch

has been used in educational establishments and after-school/summer camps with some success, however, the studies have mainly focused on student enjoyment and what blocks their projects contained and not necessarily looked at the learning of programming or how their projects have been constructed. Although more now has been done by way of looking at how Scratch fits in with teaching programming and computational thinking. By not having enough research focused on using GBCL in PE teachers will find it difficult to implement within their own class if they are not sure of the benefits of using the tools and what learning will take place when they are being used in class.

4 Teacher Questionnaire

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the development and analysis of a survey to gather teacher views on GBL in PE within Glasgow. It will then present the findings from the literature on what teachers' views are on GBL in education before discussing both.

4.2 The Questionnaire

An online survey of teachers was created and distributed through email to the heads of 156 primary schools across the Glasgow City Council area in Scotland (see Appendix 4). The head teachers were asked to forward the link to all teaching staff within their school and it was noted that participation was voluntary, and the questionnaire was open between May and June 2011 for them to fill out at their convenience. The questionnaire intended to gather teachers' own opinions on where they felt GBL would fit with the new CfE and how they felt about GBL.

The questionnaire was split into the following sections:

1. Demographic information: age, gender, class year taught, school name
2. Use of computer games and game making tools in the classroom:
 - Games played in class
 - Game making tools used
 - Subject the game was used to help teach
 - Advantages and disadvantages of games and game making in the class.

3. Personal opinions on using GBL including:

- Motivations for using GBL: Teachers were asked to state their agreement on factors that would motivate them to use a GBL approach in their class.
- Reasons for playing games: Malone and Lepper's (1987) framework was used to examine the reasons for playing computer games.
- Attitudes to computer games: Teachers were asked about their general attitudes to computer games and asked to rate as to how strongly they agreed with each attitude.
- A previous survey undertaken within higher education (Hainey, Connolly and Boyle, 2009) included motivations, reasons and attitudes to playing games and this section of the survey has been adapted for use with primary teachers.
- Benefits of GBL within the CfE: Teachers were asked about how suitable they felt GBL could be within the CfE.
- Obstacles faced when using GBL: Teachers were asked about the obstacles they faced and how they rated them as a barrier in delivering GBL.

4.3 Participants

42 teachers completed the questionnaire from the Glasgow City Council area in Scotland. Out of a total of 156 schools, 31 schools responded (20%). 34 teachers (81%) were female and 8 (19%) were male. This is in line with the fact that much of primary school teachers in Scotland (92%) at that time were female (Scottish Government, 2011). The mean age of participating teachers was 39.31 years (SD = 10.57) with a range of 23 to 59.

4.4 Curriculum Areas

Primary 1 classes use games for all areas of the curriculum in line with the CfE since playing games is encouraged at the early/first level and later years of primary school the games decline in subject areas. As noted in Section 3.6, the CfE covers eight different areas Languages, Maths, Social Studies, Health and Wellbeing, Sciences, Technology and Religious and Moral Education (RME). Teachers were asked what areas of the curriculum they use games for and what year groups they used them with. Appendix 5 includes a full table of games used at each level of primary school by teachers.

83% of the participating teachers indicated that they had used computer games for teaching in the classroom before. Of the games used 83% of them are web based. 12% of them were CD-ROM based and 5% were console games. Figure 4.1 shows the different curricular areas and years that teachers have been using games with. Within the Expressive Arts, 14.3% of teachers stated that they used computer games and some of the games used were KidPix Deluxe 4, Compose World Junior, Wii Dance and games available at the British Council Website. Within Health and Wellbeing 21% of teachers stated that they used computer games such as Wii Fit and Just Dance, Grid Club and various health quizzes online. Within Languages 40.5% of teachers stated that they used computer games from sites such as Phonicsplay and Literactive. Within Maths 48% of teachers stated that they used computer games and some of the games used were from sites such as Maths Circus and TES Topmarks. Within RME 2% of teachers stated that they used computer games and the game that was used was Noah’s ark, a web-based game. Within Sciences 14% of teachers stated that they used computer games and some of the games used were on sites such as www.sciencemuseum.org.uk and www.educationcity.com/. Within Social Studies 7% of teachers stated that they used computer games and some of the games used were web-based such as online quizzes and games about ancient Egypt. Within Technology 7% of teachers stated that they used computer games and some of the games used were from the BBC and NGfL websites.

Figure 4.1: Number of teachers using games in all curriculum levels at different Primary Levels

4.5 Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Computer Games

Teachers were asked to comment on the advantages and disadvantages they found when using computer games within the class. The advantages that teachers cited when using games in the class had “engagement” and “motivation” being the most used words. Other reasons given were that it was a “fun way to learn”, “helps reinforce concepts”, “modern, interactive and fun way to do dance”. The disadvantages of using games in the class given by the teachers were mainly lack of technology available to them but other reasons given where “child already gets too much computer time”, “time spent working out if games where age and stage appropriate”.

4.6 Using Game Creation Tools

33 teachers answered the question of whether they had used a game creation tool in the classroom. Five (15%) stated that they had and 28 (85%) stated that they had not. From those five respondents, two teachers had used task magic, one teacher used Scratch and the other two did not provide a response. Figure 4.2 shows the curricular areas that the game creation tools were used for and what classes created their games.

Figure 4.2: Number of teachers using game creation tools in all areas at different Primary Levels

4.7 Teachers Creating their own Games for Educational Use

30 teachers answered the question of whether they had created their own games to use in class. Five (20%) of the teachers had made their own games for the children to use in class, two used Senteo, one used Task Magic and the other two did not respond. Figure 4.3 shows what curricular areas the teachers made the games for and what classes played them.

Figure 4.3: Number of teachers creating their own games in all areas at different Primary Levels

4.8 Curriculum Areas Suitability for GBL

Teachers were asked to rate the suitability of GBL for teaching different areas of the curriculum on a scale of 1 (very unsuitable) to 5 (very suitable). Teachers rated GBL most suitable for learning Languages (mean=4.78; SD=0.42) and Maths (mean=4.69; SD=0.47) and least suitable for learning about RME (mean=4.04; SD=0.86) and Expressive Arts (mean=3.73; SD=1.06). The results are shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Suitability of GBL for teaching different areas of the curriculum

<i>Subject</i>	<u>Ranking</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
Languages	1 st	4.78	0.42
Maths	2 nd	4.69	0.47
Technologies	3 rd	4.64	0.57
Sciences	4 th	4.48	0.64
Health and Wellbeing	5 th	4.38	0.70
Social Studies	6 th	4.31	0.68
RME	7 th	4.04	0.86
Expressive Arts	8 th	3.72	1.06

4.9 GBL within the Four Capacities of CfE

Teachers were asked their opinions with regards to GBL and if they felt it would be beneficial within the four capacities of CfE. The results are discussed in the subsections that follow.

4.9.1 Effective Contributors

25 participating teachers answered the question of whether they believed that GBL would be beneficial for building Effective Contributors with 21 (84%) believing that it would be. Those who believed that GBL would be beneficial gave some of the following reasons:

“When playing a game children are less likely to feel like they have a wrong answer and more likely to contribute to discussions.”

“Within our developing society, and in a bid to keep abreast of the fast and rapid changes in technology, GBL would be an effective tool for building upon all the capacities within a Curriculum for Excellence and not just as effective contributors.”

Those who believed it would not be beneficial for building Effective Contributors gave some of the following reasons:

“lack of interaction with fellow pupils”

“Many of our children only want to play games, usually the ones they want, not particularly teacher led.”

4.9.2 Responsible Citizens

Teachers were also asked if they believed that GBL would be beneficial for building responsible citizens and 18 (75%) of the 24 teachers who answered this question stated that it would be. Teachers who believed that GBL could be beneficial for building responsible citizens gave some of the following reasons:

“As I haven't done too much research in GBL I can't comment on specific examples but i am confident that apt, software pertaining to Health and wellbeing and citizenship contexts would obviously enhance opportunities for pupils to develop in this capacity.”

“If the games were backed up with real life scenarios.”

Teachers who believed that GBL would not be beneficial gave some of the following reasons:

“Many of the games they want to play, particularly the boys are of a violent nature. The girls tend to want to look at fashion and pop stars.”

“They would be taught co-operation and rules/responsibility but this is intrinsic throughout the curriculum.”

4.9.3 Successful Learners

Teachers were asked if they believed that GBL would be beneficial for building successful learners and 100% of the 22 teachers who answered this question stated that it would be. Teachers who believed that GBL could be beneficial for building successful learners gave some of the following reasons:

“Children feel a similar sense of achievement and accomplishment when they win a game as they do when they complete a task well.”

“Yes, children love being challenged and feeling successful when they've mastered a skill or technique and demonstrating it to others.”

“Children could feel individual success and achievement in a way that they have not previously experienced in the classroom.”

4.9.4 Confident Individuals

Teachers were also asked if they believed that GBL would be beneficial for building confident individuals and 18 (82%) of the 22 teachers who answered this question stated that it would be. Teachers who believed that GBL could be beneficial for building confident individuals gave some of the following reasons:

“Especially or children who have difficulty accessing the curriculum due to language limitations.”

“GBL could increase confidence if success was achieved.”

Teachers who believed that GBL would not be beneficial gave some of the following reasons:

“Could isolate even further the children who have low confidence already and don't want to interact. Would need to be as part of a balanced curriculum”

“I think they are becoming more and more isolated. They are beginning to lose some of their social skills.”

4.10 Obstacles to using GBL

Teachers were asked to rate the severity of the obstacles that may be faced when using GBL for teaching. A five-point scale was used with 1 being Strongly Disagree through to 5 Strongly Agree. The highest-ranking obstacle was the identification of a suitable game making tool and the lowest ranking obstacles were time and curriculum constraints indicating that the new curriculum is generally receptive to new learning approaches. These results differ from those of Razak, Hainey and Connolly (2012) in that teachers in Glasgow were more likely to strongly agree about the obstacles they faced when trying to implement GBL. Although the questions asked differed slightly most of the obstacles were similar between the two surveys and the main obstacle for Renfrewshire teachers was assessing the learning gains followed by lack of skills and training on GBL. This could also be attributed to the way that different local authorities have different set ups within them for dealing with general ICT provision for schools, including the management and distribution of hardware and software.

Table 4.4: Teachers ratings of the obstacles to the use of GBL

<i>Obstacle</i>	<u>Ranking</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
Difficulty in identifying a suitable game making tool	1 st	4.58	0.65
Lack of PCs and technology	2 nd	4.52	0.71
Lack of skills and training	3 rd	4.40	0.65
Difficulty in identifying a suitable game	4 th	4.20	0.87
Time and curriculum constraints	5 th	3.88	1.13

4.11 Benefits of GBL

Participating teachers were asked to rate how strongly they agreed with the benefits of using a GBL approach. A five-point scale was used with 1 being Strongly Disagree through to 5 Strongly Agree. The results show that while teachers feel that using GBL transforms learning they see it still as a solitary activity for learning. These results are similar to Razak, Connolly and Hainey (2012) with transforming learning into an engaging and fun experience being the main benefit of using GBL.

Table 4.5: The benefits of GBL

<i>Benefit</i>	<u>Ranking</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
Transforms learning into an engaging experience	1 st	4.40	0.65
Transforms learning into a fun experience	1 st	4.40	0.65
Transforms learning into a motivating experience	3 rd	4.32	0.69
Encourages students to take a problem-solving approach in learning	4 th	4.12	0.73
Promotes deep learning by arousing a student's curiosity on certain subjects	5 th	4.04	0.68
Fosters collaborative learning among peers	6 th	3.96	0.84

4.12 Motivations for using GBL for Teaching in Primary School

Teachers were asked what motivations they had for using GBL in school. A five-point scale was used with 1 being Strongly Disagree through to 5 Strongly Agree Table 4.6 shows motivational factors for teachers to incorporate GBL technologies, such as game play and game making, into teaching. Based on the teachers' ratings, the main motivation for teachers to use GBL technologies for teaching is because the students enjoy learning using computer games. Teachers agreed that they feel comfortable using computer games for learning. While teachers remained almost neutral on the point of children being able to create their own games, this could be attributed to teachers simply not having enough knowledge or experience of use of GBCL within their own classroom. These results differ slightly from Razak, Connolly and Hainey (2012), While both surveys showed that teachers felt the students always enjoyed learning using games, teachers within Renfrew were not comfortable using GBL for teaching unlike Glasgow teachers who did feel comfortable using GBL. However, by looking at the results of how many teachers within each local authority use GBL this result is not surprising given that 83% of teachers in Glasgow use GBL while only 50% of teachers in Renfrewshire sue GBL for learning.

Table 4.6: Motivations for teachers to use GBL technologies for teaching

<u>Motivation</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
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The students always enjoy learning using computer games.	4.33	0.62
I am very comfortable with using computer games for teaching.	3.92	1.00
Using a computer game for teaching is as convenient as other teaching approaches.	3.83	0.85
The students have the ability to create their own game using game creation tools.	2.83	1.21

4.13 Teacher Views from the Literature

From the literature search undertaken in 3.2 some publications were identified that discuss the views of teachers and GBL projects. Groff, Howells and Cranmer (2010) reported on the Consolarium's Impact of Games in the Classroom project. This report looked at how selected nursery, primary and secondary schools throughout Scotland had been using console games. They noted that through the case studies within this project teachers found the children to be motivated and engaged and found the projects fun. However, teachers were cautious of overuse and felt that games should not be linked with every aspect of the curriculum.

A report from Williamson (2009) surveyed teachers within England about their habits and attitudes towards GBL. Although this survey covered both primary and secondary schools within England there was no statistical breakdown of the results between both educational establishment settings. The survey looked at obstacles to using games with teachers citing hardware and software costs and licensing issues as two of the top reasons for not using games in the class. This report was a follow up to Sandford, Ulkisack, Facer and Rudd (2006) with comparable results across both studies.

In addition, the Games in Schools project (Wastiau, Kearney and Van den Berghe, 2009) looked at a selection of schools and teachers from across Europe. This report included teachers views on GBL and how they use in it the class. While also discussing obstacles faced by teacher in using GBL that included costs, lack of suitable games and timetabling issues. This report as like the Futurelab report in that no statistical breakdown was given in teacher responses to questions, although what was shown was how many of the respondents were from each sector of education and how many of them used games within their learning.

4.14 Discussion

The results indicate that while computer games are being used within the curriculum by teachers in Glasgow they are mainly web-based and very few console-based games are being used by the teachers. The results indicate that teachers feel GBL is most suitable for Languages followed by Maths with the least suitable curriculum areas being RME and Expressive Arts. This is also highlighted in the number of games used by teachers and what subject areas the teachers are currently using games for. It is also shown in the games that teachers made for their classes to play that language was the most popular curriculum area for doing so. This is similar to the findings in Joyce, Gerhard and Debry (2009) and Razak Connolly and Hainey (2012). The results also indicate that while teachers are aware of GBL they only focus on the playing games aspect with a few making games for their own classes to play. Games construction tools are not widely used at all by the teachers who were surveyed.

Teachers commented on the benefits and drawbacks of using games. One of the main benefits teachers stated was motivation. The drawbacks that teachers noted were finding the right game and overusing games in the class. This is similar to the findings of Groff, Howells and Crammer (2010). The main obstacles teachers face when considering using GBL in the class is a lack of PCs and technology along with skills and training. This finding is similar to that of Stuart (2004) and Sandford et al (2006).

4.15 Summary

Overall the survey shows that teachers in Glasgow are making use of computer games to teach. However, they are not using the game construction approach and feel that their students having the ability to create their own game is the least motivating factor for using GBL approach within the classroom, but they do feel that a GBL approach can lend itself to contributing to the four capacities of children's learning in a positive way. Teachers have also shown that they feel that while GBL is useful for learning many still identify it as a solitary activity. However, when asked for any other comments teachers wanted to learn more about creating their own games in class as they did not have enough information about how to do this or in some cases did not realise that it was part of the curriculum and so were interested to find out more. From previous studies it was known that within the authority Scratch was available on the school network and therefore schools who were interested in games construction were selected to be part of the study.

5 Study 1

5.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to present the study that was undertaken in schools in 2011/2012 to introduce GBCL. Three schools participated within the study, as detailed below.

5.2 Schools

5.2.1 School 1

Eight classes from School 1 participated in the study as detailed in Table 5.1, primarily because the school had a teacher solely responsible for teaching ICT who was eager to include all classes between P4 and P7. Given the school had an ICT teacher lessons were timetabled in advance and a full ICT plan was in place within the school although no provisions were in place for GBCL. The school has an ICT suite with 21 PCs. Classes 1-3 undertook their lessons alongside classes 4-7 from the 2 other schools at the same time, while classes 8-12 undertook their lessons the term after.

Table 5.1 School 1 classes

School 1	Boys	Girls
Class 1 – P6	13	12
Class 2 – P7	12	14
Class 3 – P7	9	15
Class 8 – P5	14	12
Class 9 – P4	12	14
Class 10 – P6	15	13
Class 11 – P4	6	19
Class 12 – P5	7	12

5.2.2 School 2

Three classes from School 2 participated, as detailed in Table 5.2. Two of these classes were composite classes – a composite class is defined in Scottish education as “*a class of pupils from two consecutive stages*” (Wilson, 2003). School 2 has an ICT suite with 9 PCs available for use. They also have the use of a few teacher laptops when required. Class teachers are

responsible for ICT lessons and the school had started working on an improved ICT plan at the beginning of the study.

Table 5.2 School 2 classes

School 2	Boys	Girls
Class 4 – P4	11	9
Class 5 – P5/6	11	10
Class 6 – P6/7	16	7

5.2.3 School 3

School 3 had one class (Table 5.3) and did not have an ICT suite; instead they had 2 PCs per class as well as access to all teachers' laptops.

Table 5.3 School 3 class

School 3	Boy	Girl
Class 7 – P7	14	12

5.3 Lessons

Over the course of eight weeks the children were given a one-hour lesson with Scratch with the researcher leading the lessons alongside the class teacher. They were structured so that for the first few weeks the researcher spoke for the first five minutes of the lesson to explain the work and then the children worked in pairs on their computers on their games. Towards the end of the project the children could start lessons straight away on the computers to keep working on their games. During lessons when children were on the computers they were working in pairs, this was in part due to the limited resources of the school; however, collaborative work is actively encouraged within the CfE. The class teacher was also actively encouraged to help and become more involved in the work as the weeks progressed. In this way, it is envisaged that the class teachers themselves will then go on to teach future classes game construction with Scratch. The lessons were planned to introduce the basic concepts of programming to children as detailed by Rusk (2009a). Given the short timeframe a selection of the concepts was focused upon namely:

- Sequence
- Iteration
- Conditions
- Coordination and Synchronisation.

As well as looking at the programming concepts children were going to be taught, it was important to match the lessons to CfE guidelines (Education Scotland, 2011c) for the class teachers to see how they can easily incorporate the use of game construction within their lessons. While the focus was on “*Using appropriate software, I can work collaboratively to design an interesting and entertaining game which incorporates a form of control technology or interactive multimedia*” (Education Scotland, 2011d) the following outcomes were also used:

1. I can create, capture and manipulate sounds, text and images to communicate experiences, ideas and information in creative and engaging ways.
2. Having evaluated my work, I can adapt and improve, where appropriate, through trial and error or by using feedback.
3. Through discovery, natural curiosity and imagination, I explore ways to construct models or solve problems.
4. I explore software and use what I learn to solve problems and present my ideas, thoughts, or information.

Over the eight lessons the children were first introduced Scratch then shown how to make a simple maze game (see Figure 5.1) before finally creating their own game. Table 5.4 provides a breakdown of the lesson plan.

Figure 5.1. Simple maze game.

5.3.1 Lesson breakdown

Week 1 Introduction to Scratch using Scratch cards (Rusk, 2009b). Children were given one of the twelve Scratch cards to work on. Once completed they could change cards and work their way through the set. Scratch cards are cards that have short exercises to show different features of Scratch and only once idea at a time is presented. They have a picture on the front with explanations on the back.

Week 2 -4 The children were given instructions in how to construct a basic maze game with one sprite and one background the maze was based around Brennans (2009) maze game worksheet with a timer. They were shown how to control the sprite through the maze using the arrow keys. Finally, they were shown how to add a timer and scoring to their game to increase the challenge. The lessons were devised so that the game came together in parts. Taking inspiration from the Scratch cards the children were shown the maze and the sprite see fig 5.2

Fig 5.2 Maze game introduction card

After designing those they were then shown how to add movement and interaction events. See fig 5.3

To move the sprite around

Place the sprite at the start point and from this take the x and y positions and use these within the block.

Make the sprite bounce off the walls

Send message when the end point is reached.

Fig 5.3 Instructions for movement and interactions

Once the basics of the maze were complete children were then shown how to create variables and add in a timer or scoring (see figures 5.4 and 5.5) – or have both. This gave the children enough concepts to be able to go on and create their own game.

Creating A Timer

Click on the variables section

Click on make a variable

Call it timer

When this box is ticked the timer will show on the stage

Add the following script in


```
when green flag clicked
  go to x: -213 y: 146
  set timer to 30
  repeat 30
    wait 1 secs
    change timer by -1
  if timer = 0
    say game over for 2 secs
  stop script
```

Fig 5.5 Creating a timer

Scoring

Add in some coloured block obstacles on the maze for your player to avoid.

Create a variable and call it score

In this [example](#) the player starts off with points and as they bump into objects they get points deducted.

[However](#) scoring can also be used to give the player points in which case the score would be set to **0** instead of **10** and the change score would be **1** instead of **-1**. [Finally](#) you need to decide on the winning score to substitute into the **if score= 0** block.

Figure 5.6 Scoring in Scratch

Weeks 5-8 -The children were then tasked with either adapting the maze game and making it more complicated than what they had been working on or they could start their own game using the concepts they had been shown in previous lessons.

5.4 Children's Evaluations of Lessons

The children were asked at the end of each lesson to complete an evaluation sheet that consisted of two statements each using a five-point Likert scale (see Appendix 5). Statement one asked "Today's lesson was" children then had to choose one of the following options: Lots of fun;

Fun; OK; Boring; or Very Boring. Statement two asked “It made me feel” and children picked from: Very Happy; Happy; OK; Sad; or Very Sad. At the start of the research both statements and the responses were clearly explained to the children and they were told to tick the response that they felt that day in the lesson.

5.4.1 Participants

Overall 284 children aged 7-11 years participated with 137 boys and 147 girls and were split over the class years groups as follows:

P4 (age 7-8) – 71 (29M 42F)

P5 (age 8-9) – 53 (25M 28F)

P6 (age 9-10) – 69 (38M 31F)

P7 (age 10-11) – 91 (45M 46F)

5.4.2 Classes 1-12 Results for Statement 1

Figure 5.2 shows that overall the children enjoyed their lessons with a small decrease in enjoyment between week 1 and 8. This shows that they enjoyed what they were doing despite there being an increase in the score for enjoyment before it decreased slightly towards the end.

Figure 5.2 Class 1 to 12 enjoyment of lessons

Boys’ and girls’ enjoyment mean score of the lessons as shown Figure 5.3 show a difference with boys starting off with higher enjoyment of the lessons than girls in figure 5.4 and it then

tailed off whereas girls' enjoyment score increased over the lessons. However, overall there was still an elevated level of enjoyment continuously throughout the lessons for both boys and girls.

Figure 5.3 Boys' enjoyment of lessons

Figure 5.4 Girls' enjoyment of lessons

5.4.3 Classes 1-12 Results for Statement 2

Figure 5.5 shows that overall the affective score results of the children started off well then dropped slightly each time. Most noticeably week 8 shows a noticeable drop of 28% from week

5 of those who felt very happy in undertaking the lessons and an increase of 19% in those who felt sad from week 5 to 8.

Figure 5.5 Classes 1 to 12 affective response to lessons

By looking individually at the boys' and girls' responses (see Figure 5.6 and 5.7) the boys' mean score response decreased, overall showing a drop in score from start to finish. While the girls' scores do not change much throughout.

Figure 5.6 Boys' affective response to lessons

Figure 5.7 Girls' affective response to lessons

5.4.4 Breakdown of Year Groups for all 12 Classes for Question 1

Figures 5.8, 5.9, 5.10 and 5.11 give year breakdowns of their enjoyment of the lessons. While overall it can be seen that there was lots of fun for primary 4, 5 and 6, the primary 7s scored more on the lessons just being fun. With the primary 6s also though showing that they did feel the lessons were boring and this increased between weeks 1 and 8 from 4% to 17%.

Figure 5.8 Primary 4 enjoyment of lessons

Figure 5.9 Primary 5 enjoyment of lessons

Figure 5.10 Primary 6 enjoyment of lessons

Figure 5.11 Primary 7 enjoyment of lessons

5.4.5 Breakdown of Year Groups for all 12 Classes for Question 2

Figures 5.12, 5.13, 5.14 and 5.15 give year breakdowns of their affective responses to lessons. While overall it can be seen that there was not much change in those who were very happy with the lessons in all years between weeks 1 and 8 there were some notable differences in other responses. Between weeks 1 and 3 there was an increase in all classes of those who found the lessons OK with primary 5s and 6s showing a bigger increase than the primary 4 while primary 7 had a decrease in those who found it OK during the same period.

Figure 5.12 Primary 4 affective response to lessons

Figure 5.13 Primary 5 affective response to lessons

Figure 5.14 Primary 6 affective response to lessons

Figure 5.15 Primary 7 affective response to lessons

5.5 Teacher Interviews

During the research, the class teachers were interviewed at three stages to give their views on the research and how it was impacting on their class. The following provides details of the participants followed by their answers to the questions at each stage of the research (see Appendix 7).

5.5.1 Participants

Overall five teachers participated with their classes during the study (see Table 5.7); four of the teachers were class teachers while Teacher 1 was a deputy head who was responsible for the school's ICT lessons and was therefore responsible for eight out of the twelve classes participating. Due to class commitments, no interviews were undertaken with Teacher 5. All teachers were interviewed individually, before during and after the research took place. The interviews will be used to determine how teachers are feeling about the introduction of games-based construction learning into their class and what benefits or drawbacks they see to using GBCL in the class.

Table 5.7 Participating teachers

	Age	Length of time teaching (years)
Teacher 1	45	20+
Teacher 2	60	30+
Teacher 3	44	20+
Teacher 4	55	10+
Teacher 5	40	20+

5.5.2 Use of GBCL

The teachers were asked about their previous use of GBL/GBCL and of the four teachers who participated in the interviews two had used GBL with previous classes. Teacher 4 had used online games to teach maths and science while Teacher 1 had used GBL to teach a variety of ICT skills and for use with cross curricular learning. While Teacher 3 had used GBCL with a previous class as part of a pilot study, the teacher was not the one leading the lessons. None of the teachers were fully aware of game construction being embedded within the CfE experiences and outcomes.

5.5.3 Advantages and Disadvantages of GBCL before Study 1

The teachers were asked if they felt that using GBCL would contribute to the four capacities detailed within the CfE. All teachers agreed that it would with three of the four teachers saying successful learners and confident individuals would be the capacities they felt it would benefit most while Teacher 1 felt it would contribute to all capacities.

The teachers were asked if they thought that there would be benefits of games construction in the class. All teachers felt that there are benefits to games construction including being able to give and follow instructions, using their higher order thinking skills, being able to work cooperatively, getting the chance to experiment and being responsible for their own learning. Teacher 1 also felt that it would possibly encourage home/school discussions.

Only Teacher 3 felt that there may be disadvantages to using GBCL and these were “not having up-to-date computer equipment” and “not having enough working computers for the children to use”.

5.5.4 Class Performance before participating in Study 1

The teachers were asked if they thought that the children would be able to make their own games during the eight lessons. Teachers 3 and 4 did not think their children would have any problems coming up with their own games, while Teachers 1 and 2 felt that possibly only some of the children would be able to manage the task. Teacher 2’s Primary 4 class was one of the youngest classes and the teacher was unsure of how the children would take to following the instructions and working together, this was like Teacher 1’s response as they had eight classes of children undertaking the project ranging from Primary 4 to Primary 7 with a range of abilities in each class. All teachers felt that the children would enjoy working in pairs although Teacher 1 noted that if children are left to pick their own pairings then it would not necessarily be the ones that they themselves would choose to put them in, while Teacher 3 said that it would have to be carefully chosen pairings to consider the needs of the children within the class.

5.5.5 Overall

The teachers were asked if they had any expectations about what was going to happen over the lessons. Teacher 2 did not have any expectations while the other 3 teachers had some expectations of the children and their learning. Teacher 1 “expected children’s confidence in their ICT skills as well as game construction skills to improve”, while Teacher 3 felt that it should “give the children a chance to become more effective in contributing to work and working together to become successful learners”, while Teacher 4 felt that “pupils understanding of programming may possibly be developed over the course of the lessons”.

5.5.6 During the Study

The teachers were asked about their enjoyment of the lessons. All teachers said that they were enjoying the lessons; Teacher 2 felt that she was learning new skills, which made the lessons more enjoyable for her. Teachers 1 and 3, while they were enjoying the lessons, felt slightly out of their depth technically and in being able to answer any questions that may have come up during the lessons. Teacher 1 felt that the children had gained more knowledge of Scratch during the first four weeks than she did as some of them had been using Scratch at home too. Teacher 4 was enjoying the lessons as she felt her class were fully engaged in each of the lessons.

5.5.7 Class Performance during study 1

The teachers felt that all the children were making great progress with the lessons so far and commented that the children were enjoying working together, although Teacher 1 noted some children did prefer to work alone. However, the teachers were seeing the benefits of them working in pairs commenting mainly on the cooperation going on between the children and adapting to working with someone else in the class. Teacher 2 commented that the children were “learning to be more cooperative and fair when working together in pairs so that both children got time to work on the computer rather than one person doing all the work”.

5.5.8 Advantages and Disadvantages of GBCL during Study 1

Teacher 1 commented that she was “starting to see the benefits of game construction through the four capacities even after four lessons”. The children were showing great confidence especially some who had not shown confidence in their ICT work previously. The children were not afraid to experiment and take risks with their game designs. The children were also showing signs of reciprocal learning and there are many examples of knowledge being shared within the classroom. Teacher 2 felt that the lessons were turning into a good team building exercise and the children are proving they have skills and they are gaining confidence in themselves too. Teachers 3 and 4 also felt that the children’s confidence in their own abilities was increasing as well.

When asked about the benefits of constructing games, Teacher 1 said that “it shows the children if they can do this then the possibilities they have are limitless”. By starting at this level and using their favourite games as a comparison they can start to make the links to the real world to see how games are created. When completing the maze game, it increased the children’s

confidence and by working together and further developing their knowledge is fantastic for them. Teacher 4 felt that “negotiation and cooperative skills were being developed during the process of constructing games especially since the children love working on their games”. Teacher 2 re-iterates the children are “learning to be fair and cooperate with each other during the game construction process” and Teacher 3 points out that the “benefits of constructing games such as cooperation and collaboration are not just confined to their game construction but in fact constitute transferable skills that will help them in other lessons”.

Only Teacher 1 and Teacher 3 felt that there were any drawbacks to constructing games with Teacher 1 saying she would like to incorporate it into the ICT program although timing may be an issue. Teacher 3 felt that the “children may only see the game and not the bigger picture of the process of making the game itself”.

5.5.9 After all 8 lessons

All teachers were asked if their views on game construction had changed over the course of the study. Teacher 4 felt that at the beginning she expected her pupils to be engaged in what they were doing as well as learn some programming and her views had not changed. Teacher 3 felt that her views had changed as the weeks progressed and she could envisage more potential for cross-curricular learning and language learning. Teacher 2 did not express any views and had “no expectations” at the start of the study, however, as the weeks progressed she could see the children were learning, cooperating and really enjoying the experience. On the other hand, Teacher 1 felt that her views had changed greatly, and she could see the thought processes that were taking place, the challenges the children were facing and the persistence in working things through. The freedom to design their sprites and stages were beyond what she was expecting, and she was overwhelmed by the children’s instincts to develop their games further and seeing them motivated.

All four teachers enjoyed the lessons with Teacher 3 saying that she did most of the time though she often had to seek help, while Teacher 1 felt that although she was apprehensive at first given it was a new area of ICT, she started to enjoy it as her knowledge increased over the course of the study.

5.5.10 Advantages and Disadvantages of GBCL after Study 1

Teachers 2, 3 and 4 felt that GBCL was beneficial for the children’s learning through cooperation and enjoyment while Teacher 3 also mentioned that it benefits problem solving

skills by using a structured approach. Teacher 1 felt that there were now many benefits to games construction, which included “problem solving skills, developing keyboard skills, perseverance, facing challenges, using appropriate dialogue, taking responsibility for own learning, increasing confidence, applying skills outside the classroom, stimulating curiosity of how games are made leading them to further research and now children come and leave ICT happy”.

All teachers felt that the children working in pairs was very advantageous. Teacher 2’s class worked in mixed ability pairs and the teacher felt that this gave the children who were less able a chance to feel that they have achieved too from creating their own game while Teacher 4 felt that interpersonal skills were developed while working together. Teacher 1 stated that the school encourages pair learning across the curriculum and that children learn so much from their peers not only from talking and listening, but from taking turns, explaining, demonstrating, sharing skills, making friendships and thereby extending their social circle, assessing their own work or their peer’s work and gaining confidence when working with a new partner.

5.6 Summary

This chapter has presented results from Study 1. It has shown how the classes that participated felt about each of the lessons they undertook by way of lesson evaluations as well as showing how the class teachers have also responded to the lessons through their interviews. Overall the children showed that they enjoyed the lessons with enjoyment and affective evaluations being positive for both boys and girls for all years. However, overall the boys’ enjoyment of the lessons decreased slightly over the 8 weeks whereas the girls’ enjoyment of the lessons increased slightly over the same period. Interestingly, while all were positive enjoyment of the lessons, results for Primary 6 and 7 started off high and then fell as the weeks progressed although not significantly, while the Primary 4 and 5 classes started lower and enjoyment increased as the weeks progressed. Class teachers also noticed that the children had enjoyed their lessons too and felt that the children had been engaged while working on their games. They also felt that working in pairs was a big advantage for the children as peer learning is very much encouraged in schools.

6 Study 2

The aim of this chapter is to present the study that was undertaken in schools in 2012/2013 to introduce GBCL. Two schools participated within the study, as detailed below.

6.1 Lessons

The children participated in the lessons which are detailed in Section 5.3.

6.2 Evaluation of Lessons

The children were asked at the end of each lesson to complete an evaluation sheet that consisted of two questions each using a five-point Likert scale as detailed in Section 5.4.

6.2.1 Participants

6.2.1 School 2

Three classes from School 2 participated, as detailed in Table 6.2. One of these classes were composite classes – a composite class is defined in Scottish education as “*a class of pupils from two consecutive stages*” (Wilson, 2003). School 2 has an ICT suite with 9 PCs available for use. They also have the use of a few teacher laptops when required. Class teachers are responsible for ICT lessons and the school had started working on an improved ICT plan at the beginning of the study.

Table 6.2 School 2 classes

School 2	Boys	Girls
Class 13 – P4.5	15	9
Class 14 – P5/6	6	19
Class 15 – P7	17	5

6.2.2 School 3

School 3 had one class (Table 6.3) and did not have an ICT suite; instead they had 2 PCs per class as well as access to all teachers’ laptops.

Table 6.3 School 3 class

School 3	Boy	Girl
Class 16 – P7	9	19

Overall 95 children age 7-11 participated with 47 boys and 48 girls, split over the class year groups as follows:

P4 (age 7-8) – 14 (8M 6F)

P5 (age 8-9) – 23 (10M 13F)

P6 (age 9-10) – 8 (3M 5F)

P7 (age 10-11) – 50 (26M 24F)

6.2.3 Classes 13 to 16 Results for Statement 1

By considering School 3's shorter number of lessons, (detailed in Section 7.3.5) weeks 1, 2, 5, 7 and 8 from the other schools were examined for children's enjoyment of their lessons. Figure 6.1 shows that overall the children had lots of fun during their lessons. Boys' opinions (see figure 6.2) change more than the girls (see figure 6.3) during the 8 weeks with more boys saying they had lots of fun whereas the girls had a balance between the lessons being fun and lots of fun. What is interesting to note from these is that in week 5 the children's enjoyment changes and this could be attributed to the change in lessons from working on the maze game to starting to work on their own game ideas and after that their enjoyment increases again.

Figure 6.1 All classes enjoyment of lessons

Figure 6.2 Boys' enjoyment of lessons

Figure 6.3 Girls' enjoyment of lessons

6.2.4 Classes 13 to 16 Results for Statement 2

Figure 6.4 shows that overall the children were happy during their lessons. Boys' opinions (see figure 6.5) of the lessons differ from girls (see figure 6.6) during the 8 weeks with more boys saying they were very happy whereas the girls had a balance between the lessons making them feel very happy and happy. What is interesting to note from these is that in week 5 the children's happiness during lessons shows that this is the week the least number of children felt very happy and this could be attributed to the change in lessons from working on the maze game to starting to work on their own game ideas and after that their enjoyment increases again.

Figure 6.4 All classes affective response to lessons

Figure 6.5 Boys’ affective response to lessons

Figure 6.6 Girls affective response to lessons

6.2.5 Breakdown of Year Groups for all 4 Classes for Statement 1

Figure 6.7 shows that overall the children in primary 4 had lots of fun during their lessons with more than 50% of children saying they had lots of fun each time. Figure 6.8 and 6.9 shows the primary 5 and 6 class enjoyment for all lessons with more than 60% of children either finding

the lessons either very fun or fun. Few children found the lessons to be boring. While figure 6.10 shows that the children did enjoy the lessons though more children from primary 7 felt sad or very sad during their lessons during all weeks whereas the other classes only had certain weeks where children were showing that they were feeling bored/very bored. This could be attributed to the fact that for these lessons both the primary 4s and primary 5/6 class both had their own class teacher running the lessons.

Figure 6.7 Primary 4 enjoyment of lessons

Figure 6.8 Primary 5 enjoyment of lessons

Figure 6.9 Primary 6 enjoyment of lessons

Figure 6.10 Primary 7 enjoyment of lessons

6.2.6 Breakdown of Year Groups for all 4 Classes for Statement 2

Figure 6.11 shows that overall the children in primary 4 felt their lessons made them feel very happy though in week 7 there was a substantial change from those feeling happy/very happy to those feeling OK about their lessons with 43% of children that week saying the lesson was OK. This could be attributed to the fact that children were now working on their own games in class and they were on the second last lesson and they were at times frustrated with how their games construction was going. Figure 6.12 and 6.13 shows the primary 5 and 6 class affective

response. Few children found the lessons made them feel sad or very sad and this is shown in week 5 of the lessons for primary 6. While figure 6.11 shows that the children did enjoy the lessons though more children from primary 7 felt sad or very sad during their lessons during all weeks whereas the other classes only had certain weeks where children were showing that they were feeling sad/very sad. This could be attributed to the fact that for these lessons both the primary 4s and primary 5/6 class both had their own class teacher running the lessons.

Figure 6.11 Primary 4 affective response to lessons

Figure 6.12 Primary 5 affective response to lessons

Figure 6.13 Primary 6 affective response to lessons

Figure 6.14 Primary 7 affective response to lessons

6.3 Teacher Interviews

6.3.1 Participants

Overall, four teachers participated with their classes within the study (see Table 6.1) and two teachers led their own classes during the lessons and the other two teachers participated within the lessons as observers. All teachers were interviewed individually, before, during and after the research took place. The interviews will be used to determine how teachers are feeling about the introduction of games-based construction learning into their class and what benefits or drawbacks they see to using GBCL in the class.

Table 6.1 Participants

	Age	Length of time teaching	Leading lessons or observing
Teacher 1	44	20+	Leading
Teacher 2	55	10+	Leading
Teacher 3	24	1	Observing
Teacher 4	60	30+	Observing

6.3.2 Use of GBCL

The teachers were asked about their previous use of GBCL and of the four, only Teacher 2 had used GBCL with their class. Teacher 1 had only participated within the lessons from the previous year's research and had not used any other forms of GBCL at all. The other two teachers were not aware of game construction being embedded within the CfE experiences and outcomes.

6.3.3 Advantages and Disadvantages of GBCL before Study 2

The teachers were asked if they felt by using GBCL it would contribute to the four capacities detailed within CfE. All teachers agreed that it would, especially within the successful earning strand. All teachers felt that using GBCL was advantageous to learning with Teacher 1 stating they thought that it would "deepen the children's understanding of the concepts that were taught to them during the lessons". Teacher 4 felt that it would "boost children's confidence by working in teams and being able to create something with others". The only disadvantages that were raised by the teachers were that Teacher 4 was not sure how easy it would be to integrate into the timetable and curriculum within the school.

6.3.4 Class Performance before Study 2

The teachers were asked if they thought that the children would be able to make their own games during the eight lessons. Teachers 2, 3 and 4 did not think their children would have any problems coming up with their own games while Teacher 1 felt that possibly only some of the children would be able to manage the task given to them. The teachers were asked about the children working in pairs/groups and Teachers 2, 3 and 4 believed the children would enjoy having someone else to work with while Teacher 1 thought that most children would enjoy pair working but there were some who would not.

6.3.5 Overall

The teachers were asked if they had any expectations about what was going to happen over the lessons. Teachers 1 and 2 did not have many expectations other than to be able to deliver the lessons well. Teachers 3 and 4 did not have any expectations as they were not sure what to expect from the lessons.

6.3.6 During the Study

The teachers were asked about their enjoyment of the lessons. All teachers said that they were enjoying the lessons; Teacher 2 felt that she was learning new skills which made the lessons more enjoyable for her. Teacher 4, while enjoying the lessons, felt a bit “out of her depth with the technical side of things and in being able to answer any questions that may have come up during the lessons”. Teacher 3 felt that the lessons were going well and her confidence in being able to help the children grew each week as she became more familiar with Scratch.

6.3.7 Class Performance during Study 2

The teachers commented that the children for most of the time were enjoying working together and it was great to see the progress that the children were making during the lessons. Overall, they could see the benefits of having children collaborating as it taught them about having to work with others and sometimes having to make compromises when working in a pair.

6.3.8 Advantages and Disadvantages of GBCL during Study 2

The teachers all felt that they could see more advantages now that they had been undertaking the lessons in class with Teacher 2 commenting that she can see how much confidence the children are gaining during the lessons by constructing their games and taking pride in what

they are doing. Teacher 2 also commented that the children's social skills are improving as well by working together regularly with a partner and it helps improve their cooperative skills.

6.3.9 After all 8 Lessons

All teachers were asked if their views on game construction had changed over the course of the study. Teacher 4 said no as she felt that at the beginning she expected her pupils to be engaged in what they were doing as well as learn some programming and her views had not changed. Teacher 3 felt that her views had changed as the weeks progressed and more opportunities were identified as she could envisage more potential for cross-curricular learning and language learning. Teacher 2 did not express any views and had no expectations at the start of the study, however, as the weeks progressed she could see the children were "learning, cooperating and really enjoying the experience". On the other hand, Teacher 1 felt that her views had changed greatly, and she could see the thought processes that were taking place in the children, the challenges they were facing and the persistence in working things through. "The freedom to design their sprites and stages were beyond what I had expected, and I was overwhelmed by the children's instincts to develop their games further and seeing them motivated".

All four teachers enjoyed the lessons with Teacher 3 saying that she did most of the time though she often had to seek help. Teacher 1 felt that although she was apprehensive at first given it was a new area of ICT, she started to enjoy it as her knowledge increased over the course of the study.

6.3.10 Advantages and Disadvantages of GBCL after Study 2

Teachers 2, 3 and 4 felt that GBCL was beneficial for the children's learning through cooperation and enjoyment while Teacher 3 also mentioned that it benefits problem solving skills by using a structured approach. Teacher 1 believed that there were now many benefits to games construction, which included "problem solving skills, developing keyboard skills, perseverance, facing challenges, using appropriate dialogue, taking responsibility for own learning, increasing confidence, applying skills outside the classroom, stimulating curiosity of how games are made leading them to further research and now children come and leave ICT happy".

All teachers felt that the children working in pairs was very advantageous. Teacher 2's class worked in mixed ability pairs and the teacher felt that this gave the children who were less able "a chance to achieve too from creating their own game". Teacher 4 believed that "interpersonal

skills” were developed while working together. Teacher 1 stated that the school encourages “pair learning across the curriculum and that children learn so much from their peers not only from talking and listening, but from taking turns, explaining, demonstrating, sharing skills, making friendships and thereby extending their social circle, assessing their own work or their peers work and gaining confidence when working with a new partner”.

6.4 Comparison of Study 1 and 2

6.4.1 Children’s Evaluations

Both studies showed that over 80% of the children thought the lessons were either fun or lots of fun from beginning to end. With the affective response to lessons this dropped to around 60% of children who were mostly happy or very happy and more children feeling sad rather than OK during lessons.

Figure 6.15 Overall enjoyment of lessons

Figure 6.16 Overall affective response to lessons

6.4.2 Teacher Interviews

Over the course of both studies the teachers who were interviewed all felt positive about using Scratch with their classes and would recommend the lessons to their colleagues. However, they commented that they would need more training and that lack of technology in class could also be a barrier to them achieving this. Two teachers taught lessons to their classes during the study and while one was more confident than the other in using the technology both used their own teaching styles to get the best out of the lessons without taking them completely out of their comfort zone.

7 Development of an Implementation Framework

7.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the development of an implementation framework for introducing GBCL into PE. This framework will provide a set of sequenced guidelines to help address the second research question “What framework would be suitable to implement Scratch within the Curriculum at upper school PE?” The framework presented in this chapter will act as a starting point for Head Teachers in PE who may wish to introduce Scratch into the curriculum but are unsure of where to start.

7.2 Findings from the Literature and Teacher Questionnaire

A literature review will be used to identify any existing suitable frameworks for implementing game construction in primary schools using a number of electronic databases: ACM, Science Direct, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Computer Society Digital Library (CSDL), Taylor and Francis, Proquest (including Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts, Proquest Computing and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses A and I), EBSCO (including CINAHL PsycINFO, SocINDEX, Library, Information Science and Technology Abstracts), Cambridge Journals, ERIC, Ingenta, Infotrac and Web of Knowledge. The search terms that will be used are the following:

(making OR construct OR build OR design OR creating) AND
(game AND education) AND
(implement OR integrate OR develop)

While an initial literature search performed did not provide any implementation frameworks for GBCL by extending it to include ICT. With the search terms refined as follows and searching the previously stated electronic databases:

(making OR construct OR build OR design OR creating OR ICT) AND
(game AND education) AND
(implement OR integrate OR develop)

The resulting search provided 10 articles as outlined in Table 6.1. This highlighted frameworks and models within ICT in education that may be a suitable starting point.

Table 7.1 – Implementation frameworks/models for ICT in education

Author	Framework/Model
Dipietro, Ferdig, Boyer and Black (2007)	Framework for understanding educational gaming
De Freitas and Oliver (2006)	Four-dimensional framework for GBL evaluation
Jimoyiannis (2010)	TPASK framework for ICT integration in Science lessons
Khan (2001)	A framework for web-based training
Loveless, Burton and Turvey (2006)	conceptual framework to investigate student teachers' classroom practises with their use of ICT to promote creativity
Minghat and Yasin (2010)	Framework for sustainable development in technical and vocational education
Sang, Valcke, Van Braak and Tondeur (2009)	Gender impact model on ICT use
Tearle (2004)	Theoretical framework for identifying factors important for ICT implementation
Vanderlinde and Braak (2010)	E-capacity model for integrating ICT for instructional purposes within schools
Warin, Kolsky and Sagar (2011)	Framework for evaluation of course modules

Khan's (2001) framework is designed to be used within education and training. It consists of eight dimensions: pedagogical, technological, interface design, evaluation, management, resource support and ethical, and each dimension will vary in use according to the scope of learning taking place.

The De Freitas and Oliver (2006) four-dimensional framework looks at how educators can evaluate games to incorporate them into their own learning contexts. This framework is designed for educators to use in advance of their lesson planning. By examining the context in which the learning is happening in the first dimension, the educator can consider factors that may affect the lessons such as their own knowledge, technical support and access to tools. The second dimension takes the learner into account and focuses on attributes such as age and what

stage of education they are at. Dimension three focuses on the game itself and the interactivity it has with the learner. Lastly the fourth dimension is pedagogical, and this relates to how the game is embedded in the teaching and supports the curriculum.

Tearle (2004) proposes a theoretical framework that covers the influences on implementation of ICT in a school, by examining the school considering leadership, staff and internal processes. The implementation process then is considered with factors such as timing of the implementation, resources available, knowledge of ICT and support and training, before considering the individuals involved within the implementation, which considers attitudes, belief and skills.

Dipetrio, Ferdig, Boyer and Black (2007) propose a framework for understanding research in educational gaming that looks at past, present and future work. The framework considers different areas of research surrounding game studies namely pedagogy, psychology, media effects, genre studies and game design and is intended to be an evolving framework to encompass innovative work through time.

Jimoyiannis (2010) presents a framework for the implementation of Technological, pedagogical and Science Knowledge (TPASK). This framework is used to guide the teachers' professional development and preparation for teaching science classes through the three overlapping areas of technology, pedagogy and science.

Warin, Kolsky and Sagar (2011) present a framework for the evolution of course modules in their paper. This seven-stage framework aims to bring about a change in improving students' quality of learning and considers learning situations by using the framework to evolve existing taught modules. The framework comprises seven stages that are: redefining the roles of teachers and students, introducing pedagogical mini-projects guided by cooperative learning, alternate individual work and group work, foster a shared understanding of the activities proposed to students, use of ICT to support teaching, evaluate the knowledge acquired by students regularly and finally analyse the teaching process.

Minghat and Yasin (2010) present a framework for sustainable development in Technical and Vocational Education. The framework was developed to determine the elements of subjects within Technical and Vocational education that are seen to be needed within the Sustainable Development for the community. Across the subjects 12 experts found 16 elements that should contribute to the framework, namely, creativity, innovation, networks and partnerships, staff development programme, teaching methods, generic skills, industrial relations and internships,

counselling, entrepreneurship, ICT skills, interest, recognition, knowledge, competency-based training, articulation and commitment of management.

Loveless, Burton and Turvey (2006) present a conceptual framework developed to investigate student teachers' classroom practises with their use of ICT to promote creativity. The framework describes the interaction on practises and incorporates ICT capability, features of ICT and the National Advisory Committee on Creative and Cultural Education (NACCCE) framework for creativity.

Sang, Valcke, Braak and Tondeur (2009) propose a model to indicate a teacher's prospective ICT integration into their teaching. The model looks at gender, constructivist beliefs, teacher efficacy, computer self-efficacy and educational ICT attitudes and how they affect a teacher's prospective ICT integration into their classroom.

Vanderlinde and Braak (2011) propose a conceptual model of e-capacity that they see will help schools foster change through the optimisation of sustainable ICT. The model encompasses four layers that look at Leadership; this is seen to be a crucial factor in the success of any ICT implementation. Following on ICT related school conditions are considered this takes into consideration school policies, schools vision for ICT, support for ICT (including technical support) and having coordination of ICT. The next layer incorporates ICT related teacher conditions which encompasses professional development and teachers' competence in ICT. Lastly the teachers' actual use of ICT is an extra layer and considers how teachers are making use of ICT in their classrooms.

7.3 Other Teacher Surveys

A survey of primary teachers undertaken within two local council areas in Scotland (Razak *et al*, 2012) shows that while teachers are making use of GBL they are not making as much use of GBCL with only 9% of the 104 teachers stating they used both GBL and GBCL and 3% stating they used GBCL only. The survey also highlighted obstacles that teachers in Scotland face when trying to implement GBL in their class, which were lack of skills and training, lack of PCs and technology, difficulty identifying a suitable game and time and curriculum constraints. Other surveys on teachers show similar obstacles that are faced when trying to implement GBL/GBCL (see Table 7.2). Given the lack of literature surrounding GBCL in the classroom environment and implementation of GBCL in the classroom an initial study was undertaken to better inform a framework of implementation.

Table 7.2 Obstacles faced by teachers

Obstacles	Authors
Lack of Technology	Williamson (2009)
Teacher Skills	Stuart (2005), Sandford et al (2006)
Suitability and Time constraints	Wastiau, Kearney and Van den Berghe (2009)

By reviewing the frameworks and models from 7.2 and considering the obstacles that teachers faced with GBCL implementation as well as the obstacles other key themes from the frameworks/models emerged. It should also be noted that none of the identified frameworks were developed for primary education but rather secondary or tertiary education however there are elements which could be identified as being of benefit to the primary sector as shown in table 7.3

Table 7.3 Obstacles covered in previous Frameworks/Models

Obstacles	Covered in framework/model
Lack of Technology	Tearle (2004), Vanderlinde and Braak (2010)
Teacher Skills	Minghat and Yasin (2010), Tearle (2004), Sang, Valcke, Van Braak and Tondeur (2009)
Suitability and Time constraints	Minghat and Yasin (2010), Sang, Valcke, Van Braak and Tondeur (2009)

Management/ Leadership is seen as integral to successful ICT implementation in schools (Minghat and Yasin (2010), Tearle (2004), Vanderlinde and Braak (2010)) by being supportive leaders can encourage staff which as shown in table one of the obstacles is teacher skills. Leaders can encourage and work with staff to ensure skills are updated and that staff have confidence in their abilities. Leaders also must take responsibility for the provision of technology within their own schools and again work with staff to ensure they are able to carry out the implementation.

With teachers finding suitability of using GBCL a barrier, pedagogy is significant within a framework Dipietrio, Ferdig, Boyer and Black (2007). De Freitas and Oliver (2006),

Jimoyiannis (2010), Warin, Kolsky and Sagar (2011). Teachers are unsure of how to use GBCL and what they should be doing. The survey carried out in chapter 4 showed very few teachers had attempted to use GBCL previously. On interviewing the teachers who participated they were also unaware of how GBCL could be used and even at that time were unaware of the fact that games design had been included within CfE.

Evaluating what is learned during lessons (Khan, 2001; Warin, Kolsky and Sagar, 2011) is important part of education and should be considered to show teachers the benefits of using GBCL within their classrooms.

A short interview was conducted with the head teacher of one of the schools to seek their views on implementation of GBCL. They were asked what factors impacted them with the main one being teacher reluctance to deliver such lessons. Other factors that can impact were stated as “HMI, finance, having outside expertise to help” all of which can determine if a piece of work goes ahead. The HT said on planning work a whole school approach is taken and suggestions may be made to teaches on things they could do with the class however ultimately it is up to the class teacher on how lessons run. Though the class teacher would have support from them if they felt that the lessons were going to be of value in school.

By reviewing these frameworks and models and discussing with the head teacher, key areas that should be included in an implementation framework are:

- Evaluation
- Leadership
- Infrastructure
- Professional development for teachers
- Pedagogy

7.4 Findings from Study 1

The first study was undertaken in three different schools that all had different ICT suites and different ways in which lessons were delivered. Table 7.4 provides an overview of each school and their differing ICT situations. Initial meetings with schools were set up with the school’s head teacher after interest shown through the questionnaire sent to teachers. The meetings were used as a way for the researcher to inform the head teacher about the research and to evaluate what the schools were currently doing in terms of ICT work. The framework aims to address

the barriers to implementation of GBCL and provide clear guidance on implementation lessons with Scratch in PE. From Study 1 it can be seen how these barriers can start to be addressed (see Table 7.5).

Table 7.4 Comparison of schools

	School 1	School 2	School 3
Does the school have an ICT suite?	Yes	Yes	No
How many PCs within the suite?	20	9	n/a
Do the classrooms have PCs?	Yes	Yes	Yes
How many PCs in each class?	1	2	2
Do teachers have access to laptops?	Yes	Yes	Yes
How many laptops does the school have?	14 – all teachers	9 – 2 in ICT room and 7 teachers	7 teachers
Class sizes	25	21	27
Does the school have a dedicated ICT teacher?	Yes	No	No
Who is responsible for ICT lessons?	ICT teacher	Class teacher	Class teacher
Does the school have timetabled ICT lessons?	Yes	No	No
Does the school have ICT lesson plans?	Yes	In progress	In progress
Are the teachers aware of CfE in relation to GBCL?	No	No	No
Have teachers had any experience of GBCL?	No	No	No
How does the head teacher feel about implementing GBCL?	Keen	Keen	Keen
How do teachers feel about implementing GBCL?	Keen	Keen – some reservations in teachers' confidence levels	Reservations due to lack of technology

Table 7.5 Addressing barriers to implementation

Barrier	Issues noted during Study 1	Overcoming the barrier
Lack of technology	3 different settings, gives good range to identify minimum requirements.	Audit of equipment available in school. Other schools manage with minimal equipment at their disposal. Technology available is not the best or fastest but it is still available none the less. Advanced planning.
Teacher skills	Confidence in abilities. Lack of knowledge of CfE with GBCL. Lack of knowledge of GBCL tools.	Staff meetings to discuss their feelings on technology. Possibly have a teacher that is more confident lead the way to show others and encourage them to become involved. CPD sessions to familiarise staff with CfE and GBCL and give them the chance to find out more about using it in their class. Guidelines for implementing Scratch. Schools only have offline access to Scratch and Kodu by starting off
Suitability	Curriculum requirements – planning with staff/management	School ICT plans.
Time Constraints	Schools with no timetable were flexible, school that was timetabled changed timetable to suit.	School ICT plans. Advanced Planning.

7.5 Year two of the study – School 2 participation

At the start of study 2 a meeting was held with the head teacher who was keen to proceed with implementing GBCL in their school with Scratch.

7.5.1 School Audit

Within School 2 it was agreed that three classes would participate in the research. By looking at the staff's skills it was agreed that two of the class teachers who had participated in the study detailed in Chapter 5 would lead the classes this time with the researcher taking a less active role in the class. Class 3 was going to be researcher led as the teacher had only started the school and had not had any experience with Scratch. The lessons were scheduled to be put in an eight-week block as part of the classes ICT plans for the year

7.5.2 GBCL Tools

The school did not have any other GBCL software on their network and with recent changes within the Local Authority to their schools' network management the school was not allowed to install any software. Therefore, the decision was made to keep using Scratch. The staff were not familiar with any other GBCL tools apart from Scratch.

7.5.3 Pedagogical

While all three classes were undertaking the same lessons, they were approached in slightly different ways. The P4 class teacher used a very structured approach to learning and had stops at various points to ensure children were making good progress with their games. With the P5/6 and P7 class the approach like previous lessons done before where the children were spoken to for five minutes and shown what was going to happen for that lesson then they were able to go spend time on the lessons.

7.5.4 Professional Development

Given that two of the staff members were planning on delivering the lessons themselves they requested some additional professional development sessions to improve upon their skills in making games. It was arranged that the sessions were open to all staff in the school for 4 after school sessions that way other members of staff could support the teacher's delivering the

lessons. Over four one- hour sessions the two class teachers along with two other teachers were shown exactly what the pupils were doing during the lesson and they got the chance to try it out and make their own game therefore giving them the confidence to be able to use Scratch themselves.

7.5.5. Implementation

Two teachers implemented the lessons themselves with the researcher still in class for mainly observational purposes, but also to answer any questions that the teachers felt they could not deal with at that time. Both teachers took slightly different approaches to the lessons, however, the outcomes remained the same. Teacher 1 gave demonstrations on the smartboard in her class and had set objectives for the children for each lesson to keep them on task. While Teacher 2 talked to the children for 5-10 minutes about what she expected from the lesson that day and then let the children move onto using Scratch. For the lessons with Teacher 3 the researcher led the lessons with the teacher observing and helping when possible with any problems that the children faced during the lessons.

7.5.6 Assessment

At the end of the eight sessions children got the chance to play each other's games and review how successful they had been in creating a working game.

7.5.7 Evaluation

Discussions were held in school with staff after the lessons had taken place and the children's evaluations had shown that they had enjoyed taking part in the lessons. The staff had benefitted from having support during the teacher-led lessons and were planning to implement GBCL further in the next school year to keep the work going and to build up their confidence in using Scratch in their teaching.

7.6 Year two of the study – School 3 participation

At the start of study 2 a meeting was held with the head teacher who was keen to proceed with implementing GBCL in their school with Scratch.

7.6.1 School Audit

During the previous session many difficulties had occurred with the laptops. The main problem was that due to the large class size even with all the laptops available children were still working in groups of 3 or 4. Other issues that occurred during the study with the laptops were that either they had not been charged properly and so the battery ran out during the lesson or staff still had their laptops logged on which meant time during the lesson was wasted having to go get the laptop logged off in order for the children to use.

By reviewing the research that had been undertaken during the previous school year it was agreed with the head of establishment that due to the number of difficulties in getting the laptops organised for a one-hour class

By working with the head teacher and considering the framework in Chapter 6 the researcher along with the head teacher identified that the previous year's process had not been successful and sought to find other viable options. This was done before the school year started and it was found that the local secondary school was close enough for the children to go there to participate in ICT lessons. By arrangement it was agreed that a classroom within the school could be used for five weeks for the lessons.

7.6.2 GBCL Tools

The school did not have any other GBCL software on their network and with recent changes within the Local Authority to their schools' network management the school was not allowed to install any software. Therefore, the decision was made to keep using Scratch. The staff were not familiar with any other GBCL tools apart from Scratch.

7.6.3 Pedagogical

The lessons for this class had to be altered slightly to take into account the different amount of lessons given, however, the same approach to learning was used within the lessons.

7.6.4 Professional Development

While only one class from the school was involved a whole school CPD morning session was arranged with staff for them to become familiar with Scratch. The morning was used to show staff what children would be doing during the research and gave them the chance to work

together to create their own games. It highlighted that even with minimal PCs, while not ideal lessons like this could still be done in school with enough forward planning.

7.6.5. Implementation

The lessons were held at the local secondary school as had been agreed previously. Due to timing, the school were only able to get five lessons, but they ran for 1 hour 30 minutes. This was to enable the children to have a similar amount of time as those participating in the 8 one-hour lessons. The lessons were implemented in the same way as all other lessons though halfway through the lesson there was a break to recap and see how the children were progressing. The only issue with the implementation was that the room the lessons took place in did not have networked computers and so the children had to ensure they were sitting at the same computers each time so that they could access their work.

7.6.6 Assessment

At the end of the eight sessions children got the chance to play each other's games and review how successful they had been in creating a working game.

7.6.7 Evaluation

Discussions were held in school with staff after the lessons had taken place and the children's evaluations had shown that they had enjoyed taking part in the lessons and benefitted as well from visiting the local secondary school to take part in lessons. It was agreed that the school should keep this link with the secondary school to build on the computing work.

7.7 GBCL Implementation Framework

Based on the work undertaken in study 1 and 2 a model and framework are now presented for the implementation of GBCL within the ICT curriculum as shown in Figure 7.7 and Table 7.6. This model shows the various stages for best practise when schools would like to introduce GBCL into the curriculum and represents a high-level summary of the framework presented in Table 7.6 which provides a more detailed view of implementation of GBCL within the ICT curriculum.

The model has five stages school audit, pedagogical, implement, assessment and review. However, this should be an iterative model and after lessons have been implemented and

reviewed the process should begin again – though some steps may not need as much attention as previous iterations.

The implementation is at the centre lead by the head teacher and they should be encouraging their staff at all stages throughout the implementation and helping if there are issues at any stage.

Figure 7.7 Revised GBCL Implementation model

During the school audit phase of the implementation as well as considering the hardware that the school had available to them the software was also considered and therefore the GBCL tools available was merged with the school audit phase for that to be taken into consideration during that process rather than it being something that was considered on its own after the audit had been done. Between study 1 finishing and study 2 starting there was a change to the way in which the primary school network was managed and schools were no longer able to install their own software. However, due to the previous work with Scratch in schools this was installed on the school network for all of Glasgow along with Kodu.

Schools may also be impacted upon by way of external influences during the Study 1. School 3 had been working on improvements to ICT as recommended by HMI and were building upon that in Study 2. Finance is also something that could play an important part within the delivery of GBCL in schools. This has two sides though one being if the school does not have enough finances then it can hinder the implementation – e.g. not enough money to improve the facilities or conversely if the school has been able to secure funding facilities can be improved upon though schools would need to know the best way to spend their funding to enable children's learning benefits. As well as this teacher skills need to be looked at – do the teachers have the skills to teach GBCL or will they require CPD for them to upskill and be able to teach. This should be well supported if staff require training to progress with lessons and getting them to feel confident in their abilities to teach with the tools they have been given. Both schools that took part in study 2 were well supported by their heads in getting CPD provided by the researcher, however, only two teachers out of four felt confident enough to deliver the lessons with their classes.

Step 2 considers the pedagogical aspects of implementation. Goals and objectives should be established from the start, ideally within the school's ICT plans with all staff having an input. Education Scotland sets out within the CfE experiences and outcomes which class teachers then use to create their lesson plans. Detailed lesson plans would consider the number of available PCs/laptops the number of children in the class and what goals the teacher has for the lessons as well as curricular outcomes; e.g. are they going to make games with a theme (a topic for instance they are working on); will it be for another class in the school or simply to develop skills (collaborative working in primary is greatly encouraged). The lesson plans would also consider the tool that is being used to implement GBCL as well in order that it meets the criteria the teacher is looking for in the lessons.

Once teachers have addressed this, the lessons can then be implemented (Step 3). Initial observations showed the confidence of teachers in their own abilities at the start of the researcher-led lessons was low. However, after a couple of lessons and observing the confidence the children were showing through their work and collaborative working skills this encouraged the teachers and they were more participative within the lessons from then on. Initially the researcher led lessons comprised of a five-minute talk from the researcher that then allowed the children around 40 minutes on the PC working on their game. From working alongside teachers of classes from Primary 4 through to Primary 7, teachers felt that this may not suit all classes particularly with the younger children and that possibly a more rigid approach was required, and different teaching styles were employed by both teachers who undertook the lessons to suit the needs of their class. With the Primary 4 class having a more structured approach to their lessons than the Primary 5 class

After the lessons have been implemented an assessment of the work should be undertaken. This is important to let teachers see how the children are progressing and if they are meeting their learning intentions. Assessment can be undertaken by the children themselves either by peer assessment of the games or by self-assessment. The assessments would be developed before any lessons take place and incorporate the learning intentions of the class teacher.

The final stage of the model after the lessons have taken place is to evaluate the implementation. This examines how teachers feel about the lessons and how the children did in the lessons. After Study 1 had been undertaken the teachers who had participated felt much more confident about their abilities. They felt that the children did get a lot out of the lessons though felt that lessons could be modified to suit the class that they were working with. Children also enjoyed the lessons and felt more confident in their abilities with game construction. The review by staff should also consider a review of the staff member's learning and if they feel that there are areas they would like to improve. During Study 2 Teacher 1 noted that although they taught the lessons they still did not feel entirely confident in being able to answer the children's queries about the work they were undertaking.

Table 7.6 GBCL Implementation Framework

1) School audit	Points to consider
Current ICT curriculum in school	It is important for all teachers to be aware of the CfE Experiences and Outcomes relating to ICT in particular game construction.
ICT infrastructure	Schools should be aware of what they have available to them hardware wise and if relevant what other facilities may be available to them if their school lacks adequate hardware.
Teachers ICT skills	It is important to discuss with teachers what skills they have and what skills they would like to develop. If teachers need to learn about new tools, then the HT should be arranging relevant CPD session to ensure teacher skills are kept up to date.
External influences	Are there going to be factors that influence the implementation of GBCL such as finance or school inspections.
Tools available	What tools do the schools have on their school network?
	Are there web-based tools that could be used to teach with?
2) Pedagogy	
Context	What tool is going to be used and how is it going to be embedded within the curriculum?
Detailed lesson plans	Teachers will have to produce lesson plans to consider tools they are using to ensure they will be able to meet the learning criteria of the lesson.
3) Implementation	
Teacher Engagement	While only one or two teachers from the school may be participating it is useful for other teachers to support their colleagues.
Lessons to suit age and stage	Teachers may need to adapt the lessons to suit the class they are working with.

Support of management	Head teacher should be encouraging teachers to ensure support for any teachers leading lessons this includes infrastructure problems and ensuring any problems are dealt with accordingly.
4) Assessment	
Game assessment	Clear learning intentions – are they being met when the final game has been constructed.
Peer assessment	Peer review of games – do they hold interest of the person playing
Self-assessment	Children assessing their own games by way of statements and providing their assessment of how they did
5) Evaluation	
Teacher feedback	Reviewing lessons and making changes as necessary for teaching again. Teachers' confidence in delivering lessons should be growing and skills continually improving.
Children's evaluations	Children evaluating lessons to help teachers make changes for future lessons.

7.8 Limitations of the framework

While the framework has been devised and partially tested within schools it was difficult during the second study to fully implement. In one school, there was an external factor influencing their decision to take part in the study however staff were not keen to participate and work with their leader co-operatively to ensure success. There was also the added limitation that teachers were never fully alone in implementing as study 1 was researcher led and though study 2 did have a couple of teachers leading they still were not fully involved within the whole process. Similarly, leaders in all schools took varying degrees of interest in implementing the framework from one leaving it to the class teacher to deal with everything to another being supportive of their staff and encouraging them through the process which worked well. With the other school having support of their leader but not the staff. However, given this study was

undertaken under an action research methodology the researcher was aware that there are disadvantages and that was one of them (see chapter 2 section).

While technology or lack of it is often cited as a limited it has been shown throughout the studies that despite not having the best set up GBCL lessons could still be undertaken however it needs teachers and their leaders to work together to ensure the success of the lessons.

7.9 Summary

This chapter has identified a shortage of implementation frameworks for GBCL within the literature, by widening the search to include ICT in education more were found. Using those as a starting point enabled an identification of points that were important across the implementation of ICT in education. Furthermore, by using the results of the questionnaire presented in Chapter 4 this enabled more key features to be identified. By auditing both schools at the start of study 2 it provided a starting point for teachers to get more involved in the study and allow them to lead their classes in Scratch lessons. Staff had full support from their head teacher for them to achieve this. This included ensuring teachers had access to CPD sessions to bring their skills up to date and ensuring that any technological problems were dealt with beforehand to ensure smooth running of the classes during this time. Children's evaluations of the lessons continued to show that they enjoyed using Scratch for making games and that generally they thought it was fun to use Scratch. The teachers who participated in this study also agreed that the children did enjoy the lessons and that they were motivated in their learning. These changes have led to a framework which head teachers are able to use to implement GCL within their school.

8 Presentation of Game Coding Scheme and Analysis of Children's Games

8.1 Introduction

This chapter will present a game coding scheme that will be used to analyse the games created during the study and help answer research question 4 "How ". It will then analyse the games that were created by all 16 classes of children during the study over the school years 2011/12 and 2012/13.

8.2 Game Coding Scheme

By reviewing the literature on games construction seven papers (see Table 8.1) had identified game coding schemes used to evaluate the games create during each study.

Table 8.1 Game Coding schemes

Author	Tool Used	Main elements of Coding Scheme
Denner, Werner and Ortiz (2011)	Stagecast creator	Coding scheme focused on programming, design and code documentation and organisation.
Habgood, Ainsworth and Benford (2005)	Stagecast creator	Games classified as intrinsic, extrinsic, not educational and having educational misconceptions.
Adams and Webster (2012)	Scratch and Storytelling Alice	Counts of different programming concepts e.g. if and loop.
Baytak and Land (2011)	Scratch	Use of programming concepts in Scratch.
Werner, Campe and Denner (2012)	Alice	Use of programming constructs.
Robertson (2012)	Adventure Author	9 categories covering story, visual design, player guidance, purpose, choice, characters, dialogue, imagination and player engagement.

Wu, Wang, Ruud and Zhang (2010)	Android	Elements used in games: collision detection, 2D or 3D, GUI's use of sound, graphics used.
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While there was one coding scheme designed for Scratch games this only considered the number of blocks that each game had used and did not consider the programming concepts as defined by Rusk (2009b) that can be learned when using Scratch. The purpose of creating a coding scheme was to examine two things: (i) what the children designed and (ii) how they programmed it. Denner, Werner and Ortiz (2011) devised a coding scheme to analyse games made with Stagecast Creator. While their scheme was specific to Stagecast the overall design of the coding scheme was transferable. Their scheme's overall coding categories covered programming, code organisation and designing for usability and were decomposed into twenty-four subcategories. The games were then coded for the presence of an aspect or, in some cases, to what extent an aspect was used. The subcategories within this were more specific to Stagecast itself, however, certain items such as character appearance and use of concepts such as conditions and variables were ones that Scratch used also. Therefore, the coding scheme that was produced kept the categories of programming and design. Code organisation within Scratch was determined by the presence of extraneous blocks and name changes, therefore, this section became part of the programming section as it impacted most on the programming of the games rather than the design.

This coding scheme shown in Table 8.2 is organised into two categories namely Games Programming and Games Design and then decomposed into 29 subcategories. Each game was coded for the presence of each element or in some cases the extent to which that element was used within the category. The coding scheme reflects the complexity of some of the concepts used as well as recognising that some concepts are easier to undertake than others within Scratch. For example, the use of Iteration is scored lower than the use of Conditional statements to reflect that by adding in that aspect requires a little less programming work on the students' part. The overall total that can be scored is 236 with 132 points for Game programming and 104 points for Game Design. Although there is not a significant difference between the scores for both sections there is still a difference and the game programming section has a higher weight than the game design section due to the complexity of the programming concepts that are used within that section.

Table 8.2 Full game coding scheme

Game Programming	
<i>1. Sequence – are the blocks in a logical order to execute the script correctly?</i>	
No	0
Yes	2
<i>2. Iteration – Use of forever/repeat to create iterations</i>	
None	0
Use forever	2
Use repeat	4
Use repeat until	6
<i>3. Conditional Statements – use of if or if/else statements to check for conditions</i>	
None	0
Use if	3
Use forever if	6
Use if/else	9
Use nested if/else	12
Use nested if/else correctly	15
<i>4. Variables – have the variables been created, then initialised within the scripts</i>	
None	0
Variable created	3
Variable created with meaningful name	6
Variable initialised in script	9
Variable works correctly within script	12
<i>5. Number of variables used in game</i>	
1	2
2	4
3	6
4	8
5+	10
<i>6. Lists (arrays) – Allows for storing and accessing lists of strings and numbers</i>	
None	0
List created	3
List created with meaningful name	6
List initialised in script	9
List works correctly within script	12
<i>7. Event handling – Responding to events triggered by either the user or another script e.g. Do the keys/mouse react to input by the user?</i>	
None	0
Mouse assigned	2
Keys assigned	4

Two-player game keys assigned	6
Keys/mouse react as expected (e.g. when you press up arrow you move up)	8
Two-player Keys/mouse react as expected (e.g. when you press up arrow you move up)	10
<i>8. Threads – launching two scripts at the same time creates two independent threads that execute in parallel</i>	
None	0
Threads in program	2.5
Threads work correctly when launched	5
<i>9. Coordination and Synchronisation – using blocks such as wait, broadcast, ‘when I receive’, to coordinate the actions of multiple sprites</i>	
None	0
Wait /wait until	1
Broadcast message created	5
‘When I receive’ message block initialised	10
<i>10. Keyboard Input – Using blocks such as ask and wait to prompt users to type in answers</i>	
None	0
Ask questions	3
Respond to user input	6
Responds correctly to used input	9
<i>11. Random Numbers – used to select random numbers within a given range</i>	
Not used	0
Used	5
<i>12. Boolean Logic – Use of AND OR NOT</i>	
Not used	0
Used	5
<i>13. Dynamic Interaction – using mouse x and y or volume to create dynamic input for real time interaction</i>	
None	0
Used	5
<i>14. User Interface Design – using the when sprite clicked block can create interactive user interfaces</i>	
None	0
Used	5
<i>15. Extraneous blocks – are there any blocks attached to sprites or backgrounds which are not initiated</i>	
No extra blocks	4
One extra block	2

Two or more extra blocks	0
<i>16. Sprite names – Are the default names overridden?</i>	
Default	0
Changed name	2
<i>17. Functionality – Does anything happen when the game is run?</i>	
No, nothing happens	0
Yes, but not as expected	5
Yes, expected but with minor faults	10
Yes, all scripts run correctly	15
<u>Game Design</u>	
<i>18. Goal – Does the game have a clear starting point/end point?</i>	
No, nothing obvious	0
Yes, sprite moves to starting point when game is run	1
Yes, clear start and finish points in game	2
<i>19. Sprite customisation - Is the sprite used a predefined sprite or has the sprite been customised and to what extent?</i>	
Scratch Cat (Default)	0
One that comes with Scratch	2
Simple shape	4
Edited pre-made Sprite	6
Simple shape (using square or circle – changed to be more of a character)	8
Student designed sprite based on popular characters (e.g. Doctor Who, Daleks)	10
Original student designed sprite	12
<i>20. Stage customisation - Is the stage used a predefined stage or has the stage been customised and to what extent?</i>	
Plain white background (Default)	0
One that comes with Scratch	3
Plain colour background	6
White/colour background with the worksheet maze design	9
White/colour background with student designed line maze	12
White/colour background with student designed shape maze	15
Scenery background (e.g. wall/grass/sky) designed by student	18
<i>21. Game originality – students were asked to create a maze game to give them the grounding in basic skills that were required. However, when it came to creating their own game students chose one of the following options:</i>	
Stick with maze game (basic maze game)	0
Stick with maze game (basic maze game and timer)	2
Stick with maze game (basic maze game, timer and scoring)	4
Stick with maze game (basic maze game, timer and scoring, two player)	6
Adapt maze game (change background)	8

Adapt maze game (change background, have timer)	10
Adapt maze game (change background, have timer & score)	12
Adapt maze game (change background and sprite)	14
Adapt maze game (change background and sprite, have timer)	16
Adapt maze game (change background and sprite, have timer and score)	18
Adapt maze game (change background adapt game to two player)	20
Adapt maze game (change background adapt game to two player with timer)	22
Adapt maze game (change background adapt game to two player with timer and scoring)	24
Create new game (come up with another idea other than maze game)	26
Create new two player game (come up with another idea other than maze game)	28
<i>22. Number of Sprites within Game. How many sprites have been created for the game?</i>	
0	0
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5+	5
<i>23. Number of Active Sprites within a game. How many of the sprites created for the game are playable or have actions associated with them?</i>	
0	0
1	2
2	4
3	6
4	8
5+	10
<i>24. Average number of costumes per sprite. How many costumes does each sprite have?</i>	
0	0
1	1
2	2
3	3
4+	4
<i>25. Sprite costume changes on interacting with other sprites/background - Does the sprite change costume in reaction to an event being triggered?</i>	
No changes	0
One change	2
Two changes	4
<i>26. Number of Backgrounds within a game – How many backgrounds have been created for the game?</i>	
0	0

1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5+	5
<i>27. Background Interactivity – is the background part of the game or is it there to set the scene?</i>	
No interaction at all	0
Use of background colours to interact with Sprites	3
Background reacts to events	6
<i>28. Players – How many players is the game designed for?</i>	
One player	2
Two player	4
<i>29. Sounds - Does the game have any sounds included? This may be either a continuous sound or sounds that occur when events are triggered.</i>	
No sounds	0
Continuous sounds	3
Sounds on event interaction	6

8.3 Participants

384 children aged between 8 and 11 participated in the study during the school terms in 2011/12 and 2012/13. They were from sixteen classes from Royston Primary School (RP), Carntyne Primary School (CP) and Alexandra Parade Primary School (AP) in Glasgow. The classes that participated in the study are shown in Table 8.3. The children worked mainly in pairs though, where necessary, some groups of three had to be formed due to limited numbers of PCs available. These comprised of 51 boy groups, 62 girl groups and 65 mixed gender groups. Each school had a different ICT environment: Alexandra Parade had a full suite of 20 PCs available; Royston Primary had a suite with nine PCs and two laptops while Carntyne Primary did not have an ICT suite. Class 7 from Carntyne had the lessons in their own classroom using the two class PCs and seven teacher laptops while Class 16s lessons were moved to the local secondary school who provided an ICT room with 20 PCs for the children to undertake their lessons in.

Table 8.3 Participants

Class	Year	Boys	Girls	School	Who led the lessons
1	P6	13	12	AP	Researcher
2	P7	12	14	AP	Researcher
3	P7	9	15	AP	Researcher
4	P4	11	9	RP	Researcher
5	P5/6	11	10	RP	Researcher
6	P6/7	16	7	RP	Researcher
7	P7	14	12	CP	Researcher
8	P5	14	12	AP	Researcher
9	P4	12	14	AP	Researcher
10	P6	15	13	AP	Researcher
11	P4	6	19	AP	Researcher
12	P5	7	12	AP	Researcher
13	P4/5	15	9	RP	Class teacher
14	P5/6	6	15	RP	Class teacher
15	P7	17	5	RP	Researcher
16	P7	9	19	CP	Researcher

8.4 Results

This section will discuss the results from the games that were developed during the studies and analyse them using the game coding scheme that has been presented.

8.4.1 Original Maze Game

During the research, the children were given eight lessons with Scratch. The purpose of these lessons was to let the children see they could construct their own games; programming was included in the games process within the lessons although it was never explicitly mentioned that the children were learning to program during these lessons despite them being shown elements of programming to make their games functional. The first four lessons were to show the children how to create a simple maze game with a timer and scoring. The children were

then given the choice for the next four lessons to extend the game they had made or create a new game.

The maze game that children were shown was a simple game with one active sprite and one background. The main concepts that were included within the maze game were:

- Sequence
- Iteration
- Conditions
- Coordination and Synchronisation
- Keyboard Input
- Variables.

Using the proposed coding scheme, the maze game scored 38%, which can be used as a baseline to determine how the games children created compare to it. The game scored 44% for programming and 26% for design. By comparing the games created during the research only 12% of games created scored higher than the original game for programming and 99% of games created scored higher than the original game for design. While this seems an extremely high percentage for the design aspect it shows that all games created have their own individual design and they are not all simply clones of the maze game. With regards to the programming scores this was more complex hence the number of games who scored higher than the game that the children were shown how to create. The most frequently used programming concepts implemented by children in their games were like those found in Maloney *et al* (2008), namely User Interaction (key handling), Loops (iteration) and Conditional Statements.

8.4.2 Overall Game Scoring

Within classes the children were mostly working in pairs, however, there were also some groups of three and children working on their own. Each game was scored in all coding categories and an overall percentage given. The mean game score overall was 39%, slightly above the baseline score of 38%. Table 8.4 provides a breakdown of mean total game scores by class. By comparing the mean ranks for the groupings (both gender and year) the results showed that boys working together scored higher than girl or mixed gender groups (Table 8.5). The results also showed that Primary 7 children scored higher than the other classes overall (Table 8.6). However, a Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis of variance test showed no significant difference in game scores between class groups ($\chi^2 = 1.677$, $p < 0.642$) or between

gender groupings ($\chi^2 = 1.335$, $p < 0.513$). Given that all the children from Primary 5, 6 and 7 are working towards the second level of CfE it is not surprising that their results are similar, however, the Primary 4 children are working towards the end of the first level of CfE and have made just as satisfactory progress as the rest of the classes.

Table 8.4 Total mean scores for all classes

Class	Mean total score (%)	Std deviation
Class 13 – P4/5	46.96	6.41
Class 14 – P5/6	44.45	7.63
Class 5 – P5/6	44.09	5.53
Class 2 – P7	43.86	9.72
Class 15 – P7	43.51	12.92
Class 4 – P4	42.84	5.24
Class 7 – P7	42.18	11.15
Class 8 – P5	40.96	5.83
Class 3 – P7	40.27	13.51
Class 6 – P6/7	39.41	11.4
Class 1 – P6	36.02	8.11
Class 16 – P7	34.86	9.28
Class 12 – P5	33.79	14.52
Class 10 – P6	33.69	10.78
Class 9 – P4	33.58	6.5
Class 11 – P4	32.84	8.94

Table 8.5 Ranks by gender grouping

Gender	N	Mean Rank
Boys	51	96.46
Girls	62	85.90
Mixed group	65	87.48
Total	178	

Table 8.6 Ranks by class year group

Primary Year Group	N	Mean Rank
4	43	83.56
5	37	93.61
6	39	84.73
7	59	94.41
Total	178	

8.5 Game Programming Scoring

This section will discuss firstly the results of the game programming scores for all games and then decompose the game programming section of the coding scheme to further analyse the games produced.

8.5.1 Overall Game Programming Score

The mean game programming score overall was 30%, lower than the baseline score of 44% although given that programming was not taught explicitly, this is a good outcome. Table 8.7 provides a breakdown of mean game programming scores by class. By comparing the mean ranks for the groupings (both gender and year) the results indicated that boys working together scored higher than girls or mixed gender groups (Table 8.8). The results also showed that Primary 5 children scored higher than the other classes in the programming category (Table 8.9). However, a Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis of variance test showed no significant difference in game programming scores between class groups ($\chi^2 = 1.108$, $p < 0.775$) or between gender groupings ($\chi^2 = 1.206$, $p < 0.547$). Given that all the children from Primary 5, 6 and 7 are working towards the second level of CfE it is not surprising that their results are similar, however, the Primary 4s are working towards the end of the first level of CfE and have made just as satisfactory progress as the rest of the classes, so this could be seen as surprising. A brief discussion about the results with a couple of the teachers showed that they agree while it is surprising they have comparable results it could be explained by the fact that this is the first time they have all undertaken the activity. If this was to continue, then by the time Primary 4s became Primary 7s then they would expect a much bigger difference in results.

Table 8.7 Mean Game Programming scores for all classes

Class	Mean Game Programming score (%)	Std deviation
Class 13 – P4/5	40.49	2.54
Class 8 – P5	36.36	6.5
Class 15 – P7	36.13	15.95
Class 7 – P7	34.34	14.37
Class 14 – P5/6	34.32	10.96
Class 5 – P5/6	33.37	9.89
Class 4 – P4	33.33	5.34
Class 2 – P7	30.75	12
Class 6 – P6/7	30.23	12.89
Class 10 – P6	29.17	15.57
Class 1 – P6	28.21	13.91
Class 11 – P4	27.59	12.34
Class 16 – P7	26.35	13.97
Class 3 – P7	25.24	16.6
Class 9 – P4	24.87	13.03
Class 12 – P5	21.84	15.64

Table 8.8 Ranks by gender grouping

Gender Grouping	N	Mean Rank
Boys	51	95.60
Girls	62	84.94
Mixed group	65	89.07
Total	178	

Table 8.9 Ranks by class year group

Primary Year Grouping	N	Mean Rank
4	43	89.03
5	37	96.80
6	39	84.72
7	59	88.42
Total	178	

8.5.2 Game Functionality

From 178 games, 12 (7%) were non-functional, which could have been attributed to the amount of time children spent designing their game or indeed the actual working partnerships that may not have all produced a working game. Figure 8.1 provides a breakdown of the games functionality by gender grouping, which shows overall that mixed gender groupings had the most success at creating fully functional games with girls' pairings not far behind and both had twice as many as boy pairings. Figure 8.2 provides a breakdown by year grouping, which shows that Primary 7 classes were the most successful in creating fully functional games followed by Primary 5 classes. 68 (38%) games created were fully functional and worked as intended while the remaining 98 (55%) games worked but to varying degrees. While most of the games were designed to be one player, 23 (13%) of them were functional two-player games using both the arrow keys and W,A,S,D keys to play. What can be seen from both these figures is that 93% of children from P4 through to P7 regardless of gender grouping were able to produce a game with varying degrees of functionality.

Figure 8.1 Gender scores for functionality

Figure 8.2 Class year scores

8.5.3 Concepts within Games

The games developed by the students varied in their complexity, with 160 (90%) games using keyboard or mouse control to play the game. The games that did not use event handling either did not have any scripts attached to the sprite or they used keyboard input and had the user answering questions to progress in the game. While 114 (64%) games contained coordination and synchronisation most of these used the wait block; 24 (13%) of these games implemented a broadcasting message to synchronise between sprites, which were not fully implemented correctly in 6 of the games as it was attached to the wrong sprites. Conditional statements within games consisted of an event being raised if a sprite touched an object when it was moving around; e.g. sprites bouncing off walls or changing scores. Table 8.10 shows the percentage of games that include each programming element (only elements that were found in games are included in the table).

Table 8.10: Concepts found in the games

Programming Concept	Number of games	% of games including concept
Sequence	165	93
Event Handling	151	90
Conditional Statements	135	76
Threads	126	71
Variables	105	59
Co-ordination and Synchronisation	106	60
Iteration	83	47
Keyboard input	8	6
Random Numbers	6	3
User interface design	2	1

8.5.4 Event Handling and Keyboard Input

151 (85%) games had control of some sort, which can be broken down into various categories of whether the children had assigned a form of control and then if they had taken that further to make sure the control worked correctly for use of either the keyboard or mouse. Figures 8.3 and 8.4 show the usage of this feature with Figure 8.3 showing gender groupings and Figure 8.4 showing breakdown by year groups. All gender groupings had created games with event handling to different degrees and all classes apart from Primary 6 had working two-player games.

A pair of girls from Primary 4 created a two-player game under the (sea) maze type of game (Figure 8.5). The aim of the game is to be the first player to reach the red square while navigating your way through the blue circles before the time runs out. This is a good example of how players can control sprites during the game, as the game uses two different types of event handling. The children were shown how to use the keyboard to control the player during the lessons, however, this pair had taken time to investigate other methods of controlling sprites and discovered how to have the sprite follow the mouse. Player 1 is the diver and is controlled by the up, down, left and right arrow keys while player 2 is the fish and is controlled by the mouse.

Figure 8.3 Gender grouping scores for event handling

Figure 8.4 Gender grouping scores for event handling

Figure 8.5 Maze type game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

8.5.5 Conditional Statements

135 (76%) games used conditional statements. There were four different types of conditional statements that could have been used: if, Forever if, nested if/else and nested if/else working correctly. 90% of games used the Forever if condition game to control events. This condition was used alongside the background colours to control what sprites touched during the game. Figure 8.6 shows what groups used the conditions noting that only girl pairs or mixed gender pairs attempted to use the nested if/else statement. From examining the class groupings in Figure 8.7, it can be seen that all groups apart from P4 attempted to use the nested if/else statements.

Figure 8.6 Gender pair scores for conditionals

Figure 8.7: Gender pair scores for conditionals

The games that used the nested if/else statements were games that asked the users to respond to a series of questions. The game shown in Figure 8.8 was created by a pair of Primary 5 girls and is based on a series of questions. This game was an original idea by the girls and exceeded what was expected of the children as they had extended their work by using a new concept that was not taught during the original lessons. However, from the start of lesson 5 they had a very clear plan of how they wanted their game to work. Getting the girls to write down how they thought the questioning should work helped them to understand their game before being made aware of the nested if/else statement. It is a very good example of how to use nested if/else statements correctly to create a game. The figure shows their self-designed sprite and stage and Appendix 8 shows the single script to make the game run. It is a complex script that must be thought through for the game to work correctly – if a question is answered correctly the player moves on to the next question otherwise the game ends.

The game did require a lot of testing of correct and incorrect answers to ensure it ran properly and the pair took this on board to be successful. They had started to add in sound effects when a correct answer was given, however, it was not incorporated into every question. The game also shows effective use of adding in sounds as they found a sound that was in the Scratch library that, when played, asked the player to “Come and play”. Sounds were not something that was mentioned in any lessons and it was through curiosity that the children discovered they could add sounds to enhance their game. Adding in sounds only when particular events

occurred, helped the children develop the game and showed the pairs programming skills as well.

Figure 8.8 Quiz created by two P5 girls

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

8.5.6 Iteration

83 (47%) of the games used iteration, either through using the forever block or the repeat or repeat until blocks. Most games that used iteration had used the repeat block. Iteration was generally used when the game had the timer or scoring variable, as the countdown action required it to be counted a certain number of times to score or time correctly. Figure 8.9 shows the usage by gender and, while all gender groupings used the repeat block, it was only girls or mixed gender pairs who used the repeat until block and defined what actions had to happen for the loop to stop. Figure 8.10 shows the usage of iteration between class groups and again shows that the repeat block was most used by all classes, with only the Primary 5 and Primary 7 classes using the Repeat until block. However, this correlates with the data previously shown that the Primary 7 classes followed by Primary 5 classes were the highest scoring classes within the programming section.

Figure 8.9 Iteration used by gender grouping

Figure 8.10 Iteration used by class grouping

The shoot the wotsit game (Figure 8.11) is an original game created by a mixed gender group from Primary 7 and demonstrates how they used the repeat until block within their game. The aim of the game is to shoot all the wotsits before the timer runs out. The game has a sprite that is a simple crosshair. It is programmed to move randomly around the stage when the green flag is clicked. The sprite will only stop once the space bar is pressed, if the crosshairs then happens to be on a wotsit sprite when space is pressed, it will then create an interaction between those two sprites (Figure 8.12 shows the scripts for the crosshair sprite). This interaction will cause the wotsit sprite to change costume (Figure 8.13) and show that it has been hit (Figure 8.14).

As well as changing the costume it triggers a sound as well. Changing costumes within the game and having sounds on interactions were not part of the lessons given and this shows that the children have thought a bit more about their game and spent time on the programming to have these features working.

Figure 8.11 Hit the Wotsits game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.12 Crosshair sprite script

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.13 Wotsit sprite script

Figure 8.14 After the Wotsits have been hit

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

8.5.7 Variables

Variables were used in 105 (59%) of the games created. Figure 8.15 shows variable use by gender with girl groupings using variables correctly slightly more than boy or mixed gender groupings. Figure 8.16 shows how the different year groups used variables with Primary 7 classes followed by Primary 4 classes having the most correctly used variables within their games. While not surprising for the Primary 7 classes this is surprising for the Primary 4 classes, however, this could be attributed to them using the variables correctly that they were taught during the first four lessons, namely timers and scoring. Figures 8.17 and 8.18 break down the number of variables used by groupings and class groupings and shows that pairs from all year groups were successful in implementing variables within their games with more than 50% of games containing more than one variable. By looking at the number of variables created it can be seen that Primary 7s used the most variables per game and some even went on to use three variables within their game.

Figure 8.15 Variable use by gender grouping

Figure 8.16 Variable use by Class grouping

Figure 8.17 Number of variables used by gender grouping

Figure 8.18 Number of variables by Class grouping

The main variables that teams used within their games were scoring and timer, which were taught during the initial lessons for the maze game. However, some games took this a stage further and created a two-player game scoring system that is demonstrated within a football game (Figure 8.19) created by a mixed gender group from Primary 7. The game is an original idea by the children that has two players and a football that the players must stop from hitting their goal. This game is a very good example of using not only variables but also having more than one active sprite on the stage. There are three active sprites within this game and two of them are player controlled while the third is the ball, which moves on its own across the stage in a random pattern. When the game starts the ball automatically moves across the stage from side to side and the players can move their goalkeepers up and down to then hit the ball back in the other direction, so it avoids hitting the goal area. A score has been assigned to each player as well as the game having a timer (Figure 8.20)

Figure 8.19 Football game with 3 variables

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.20 Scripts for football game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

8.5.8 Threads in Games

Threads within Scratch games are described as scripts that run simultaneously. 126 (71%) games had threads of which 109 (61%) executed correctly and the other 17 (10%) did not. Figures 8.21 and 8.22 provide a breakdown of the gender grouping and year groupings with all classes and all groupings with their usage of threads. Figure 8.21 shows that mixed gender groupings used threads correctly as well as having more threads in their games than girl or boy groupings. Figure 8.22 shows that Primary 7s then Primary 4s have used threads correctly and have more threads in their games than the other classes. This is not surprising for the Primary 4 classes given that their games were mainly adaptations of the maze game and therefore they did not introduce many more new features unlike the Primary 7 classes who had a lot of original ideas rather than sticking with the maze game. Of the threads that did not work this was due to there being more than one stack of code being placed on the same object

Figure 8.21 Threads used in games by gender groupings

Figure 8.22 Threads used in games by class groupings

An example of a game that had threads within it that worked correctly is one created by a boy pair from a Primary 7 class. The game shown in Figure 8.23 is an adapted maze game where the game background has been changed to one that has shapes to make a maze type path for the sprite to follow. Figure 8.24 shows the scripts that the game uses, showing that when the game starts by clicking on the green flag the sprite then has a couple of actions running at the same time namely moving to a start point, setting the score and then looking out for different colours to avoid.

Figure 8.23 Adapted maze game with threads working

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.24 Scripts for maze type game to show working threads

An example of a game that had threads within it that did not work correctly was a maze type game shown in Figure 8.25, created by a pair of girls from Primary 4. The game has conflicts due to two different threads being set up on the same touching colour action (see Figure 8.26) thus, while the sprite may bounce off the green blocks, the scoring does not work at times due to this conflict.

Figure 8.25 Maze game with partially working threads

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.26 Scripts for maze game showing the conflicting threads

8.5.9 Co-ordination and Synchronisation

106 (60%) games that were created had co-ordination and synchronisation within them with the main block used being wait or wait until. The wait block was used primarily within variables such as timer. The timer would have a countdown and wait would be used to make this countdown work (Figure 8.27)

Figure 8.27 Example of how the wait block can be used to create a game timer

Figures 8.28 and 8.29 show that all gender groupings who had used coordination had made most use of the wait block. However, there was also use of the broadcast and ‘when I receive’ blocks. For those groups who had used the broadcast message block it indicated that they had attempted to start creating coordination of sprites within their games, however, without using the ‘when I receive’ block too it would affect how the final game worked as both are needed for the coordination to function correctly.

Figure 8.28 Use of coordination by gender groupings

Figure 8.29 Use of coordination by class groupings

A simple game created by a mixed gender pair from Primary 4 (Figure 8.30) illustrates the use of the ‘when I receive’ message. They have created a frog sprite that has to get to the princess and once the sprite touches the frog then it turns into a prince (Figure 8.31). There is another sprite, a dragon, and given more time the game would probably have had the dragon trying to stop the frog reaching the princess.

Figure 8.30 Princess & frog game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.31 Scripts for Frog sprite to change costume

8.5.10 Random Numbers

Random numbers are used within games when the user wants to select from a wide range of numbers. For example, the turn 15-degree block (Figure 8.32) can be changed to any number, however, by adding in the random number it then provides more scope for sprites to move around the stage. This is useful for allowing sprites to be able to move in different directions all over the stage without having to create different scripts for movement.

Figure 8.32 Using the random numbers block within another block

Figures 8.33 and 8.34 show how it was used by gender groupings and year groupings. All years apart from Primary 4s had groupings use the concept within their games as well as this there was an even split between all gender groupings who used the concept even though very few groups had used it. A game created by a mixed gender group from a Primary 6 class used the random numbers concept on the ball sprite of their bat and ball game (Figure 8.35). By using the random number, it allows the ball to freely bounce in different directions over the screen, there was also interaction with the bat as the ball was able to bounce off the bat (Figure 8.36). However, it does look like this game still had more work to be done as there had been variables for scoring and timing created that were not included in any of the scripts in the game.

Figure 8.33 Use of random numbers by gender grouping

Figure 8.34 Use of random numbers by class grouping

Figure 8.35 Bat and ball game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.36 Script for the bat in the game using random numbers

8.5.11 User Interface Design

Only 2 (1%) of the 178 games created used clickable sprites within their games to trigger events. Figure 8.37 shows that they were created by a boy pair and a girl pair from Primary 7.

The game made by the P7 girls starts with a screen (Figure 8.37) asking the player to pick a character (the sprite). Once the sprite is clicked, in this instance the horse sprite called Winter was clicked on, the next event was triggered to change the background to one of a field (Figure 8.38). The player can then select an option to feed, brush or play ball with the horse. By selecting the food option, the horse commented about “wanting a sammich” (Figure 8.39) and then making a neighing sound (Figure 8.40). This game was not fully finished, as selecting one animal should have made the others disappear. However, it is a good example of showing how sprites can be used to interact by using the broadcast blocks as has been done in this game. The broadcast feature is more complex than many other features and was not taught during the class lessons, however, if children asked and could explain what they wanted to happen within their game then they were shown how the broadcast message can work.

Figure 8.37 Games by gender grouping that used UI Design

Figure 8.38 Selection game using UI design

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.39 Once a sprite is clicked the game moves on to the next part

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.40 Result of selecting the food sprite to click on

```

when Winter clicked
broadcast field

when I receive brush
say im feeling dirty time for a brush for 2 secs
say i feel nice and clean for 2 secs
play sound Horse

when I receive ball
say time to play for 5 secs
say that was fun for 2 secs
play sound Horse

when I receive hay
say im hungry for 5 secs
say yum yum for 2 secs
play sound Horse

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Figure 8.41 using sounds within the game to help

8.5.12 Concepts that were never used

While the game coding scheme was designed to cover the concepts that could be taught with Scratch, not all of these were covered within the lessons that the children were given. Children did make use of broadcast messages, random numbers, clickable sprites and keyboard input, which were not explicitly taught, however, they were shown if they had asked when wanting to add a feature to their game. Lists, Boolean logic and dynamic interaction were the only three concepts as defined by Rusk (2009b) that the children were not taught or shown at any time during the lessons and were therefore never used at all.

8.6 Game Design Scoring

This section will discuss firstly the results of the game design scores for all games and then decompose the game design section of the coding scheme to further analyse the games produced.

8.6.1 Overall Game Design Scores

The mean game design score overall was 50%. Table 8.11 provides a breakdown of mean game design scores by class. Kruskal-Wallis tests showed no significant difference in design scores between the four class groups ($\chi^2 = 5.616$, $p < 0.132$) or between gender groupings ($\chi^2 = 1.524$, $p < 0.467$). While the Kruskal-Wallis test showed no significant difference between class groupings or gender pairs, it did show that boys working together scored higher than girl or mixed gender groups (Table 8.12). The results also showed that Primary 7 children scored higher than the other classes in the design category (Table 8.13).

Table 8.11 Mean Game Design scores for all classes

Class	Mean Game Design score (%)	Std deviation
Class 2 – P7	60.5	10.05
Class 3 – P7	59.35	13.87
Class 5 – P5/6	57.69	13.01
Class 14 – P5/6	57.31	16.7
Class 13 – P4/5	55.16	15.49
Class 4 – P4	54.91	6.27
Class 15 – P7	52.89	13.42
Class 7 – P7	52.14	14.61
Class 6 – P6/7	51.06	12.74
Class 12 – P5	48.96	16.73
Class 8 – P5	46.8	9.08
Class 1 – P6	45.93	10.28
Class 16 – P7	45.67	13.96
Class 9 – P4	44.64	4.99
Class 11 – P4	39.5	8.18
Class 10 – P6	39.42	6.86

Table 8.12 Ranks by gender grouping

		N	Mean Rank
Game design score	Boys	51	94.53
	Girls	62	91.77
	Mixed group	65	83.38
	Total	178	

Table 8.13 Ranks by class year group

		N	Mean Rank
Game design score	4	43	80.26
	5	37	88.45
	6	39	82.01
	7	59	101.85
	Total	178	

8.6.2 Game Types

There were 178 games created by the groups during the study. Table 8.14 provides an overview of the games created by each class. Overall there were three types of game that the children used: either they used the game that they were taught, they adapted the game they were taught, or they created a brand-new game. Figures 8.42 and 8.43 provide a breakdown of gender groupings and class groups respectively for each type of game created.

Table 8.14 Game types by class

Class	Use basic maze game	Adapt maze game	Create new game (come up with another idea other than maze game)
Class 1 – P6	0	8	5
Class 2 – P7	0	3	9
Class 3 – P7	0	3	8
Class 4 – P4	0	6	3
Class 5 – P5/6	0	4	6
Class 6 – P6/7	0	6	4
Class 7 – P7	0	4	5
Class 8 – P5	0	6	3
Class 9 – P4	0	7	7
Class 10 – P6	0	11	1
Class 11 – P4	0	10	2
Class 12 – P5	0	4	8
Class 13 – P4/5	2	7	2
Class 14 – P5/6	1	2	7
Class 15 – P7	0	2	6
Class 16 – P7	3	2	11

Figure 8.42 Design of games by gender grouping

Figure 8.43 Design of games by class grouping

8.6.3 Game Design Features

Table 8.15 shows the game design features which the coding scheme aims to identify how children designed their games by either making their own designs or using pre-made sprites and backgrounds that come with Scratch. It also shows whether the children constructed original games or used the game already provided during the first four lessons. The following sections will look at each aspect of the features in more detail.

Table 8.15 Game design features

Game Design	% of games
Sprite customisation	70
Stage customisation	84
Game originality	49
Goal	62
Sounds	7

8.6.4 Sprite Customisation

Of the games created only three did not change the default sprite that loads when a new project is created. 49 (28%) games had sprites that were available from the built-in templates folder that comes with Scratch. The remaining games were all variations on either shapes or student-drawn sprites. Figures 8.44 and 8.45 show the breakdown of sprite customisation by gender and class, respectively. From Figure 8.44 Primary 7 children were more likely to come up with their own sprites or use ones that come with Scratch, while the other classes were more likely to use simple shapes and ones that came with Scratch. There was not much difference in gender pairing for sprite design (see Figure 8.45) though only mixed gender groupings were the only ones to use the original Scratch cat.

A game created by a pair of P7 boys used a Doctor Who theme where the Tardis and Daleks face each other. The player controls the Tardis and the aim of the game is to hit the Daleks with the ball. If the Daleks are hit it causes them to change costume to reflect this, similarly if the Tardis is hit, then the costume changes (Figure 8.46). To add more complexity to the game at points the Daleks will also fire at the Tardis at times.

Figure 8.44 Design of sprites by gender grouping

Figure 8.45 Design of sprites by class grouping

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.46 Doctor Who themed game showing costume changes

8.6.5 Background customisation

Out of the games created only eight did not change the default background that loads when a new project is created. 20 (11%) games had backgrounds that were available from the built-in templates folder that comes with Scratch. The remainder of games were all variations on either plain colour backgrounds, maze type backgrounds or student-designed backgrounds. Figures 8.47 and 8.48 show the breakdown of background customisation by gender and class, respectively. Figure 8.47 shows overall that girls were more likely to create their own background for their game or use one that came with Scratch, which is similar to the results of the sprite customisation for girl groupings. From Figure 8.48 Primary 7 children were more likely to come up with their own background or use one that came with Scratch, which is like the results of the sprite customisation for Primary 7 classes. Primary 4 classes did try always to change their background as can be seen in Figure 8.48. Overall the Primary 4 classes adopted a background that uses shapes to give a maze game.

Figure 8.47 Stage customisation by gender grouping

Figure 8.48 Stage customisation by class grouping

8.6.6 Use of Sounds

Sounds were not explicitly taught throughout the first four lessons and this was something that all the children who worked with Scratch discovered on their own through experimenting. There were two ways of sounds being incorporated into games: either the sound ran continuously throughout the whole game or the sound only occurred on event interaction. 12 (7%) of games included sound, with event interaction being the most common way for having sounds in a game, as shown in Figures 8.49 and 8.50 respectively. Figure 8.49 shows that all gender groupings have added sounds that react to events while only girl and mixed gender groupings have added continuous sounds to their games. Figure 8.50 shows all classes using the sounds reacting to events with Primary 4 and 7 classes being the only ones to use continuous sounds within their games.

Figure 8.49 Games that made use of sound by gender grouping

Figure 8.50 Games that made use of sound by class groupings

8.6.7 Game Goal

67 (38%) games did not have any clear goal. The rest of the games either had a sprite that moved to a fixed starting point in the game or there was a clear start and end point for games when they were run. Figures 8.51 and 8.52 show the gender and class groupings for the use of goals in games, respectively. There was an almost even balance of gender groupings having games with clear start and end points though mixed gender groups had more games that had a fixed starting point in their game. Primary 7 classes had the most games with a clear start and end point and there were no Primary 4 games that had this feature, although Primary 4 games did have the most number of fixed starting point games.

Figure 8.51 Goal of games by gender grouping

Figure 8.52 Goal of games by class grouping

8.7 In-depth Game Examples

To illustrate the findings this section will present an in-depth discussion of six games created during the research. The games presented are ones whose score of games design and games programming combined using the coding scheme are of high, medium or low scoring.

8.7.1 Game 1 High Scoring

The first high scoring game is a fully functional maze game created by a boy/girl pair from the Primary 5/6 class (Figure 8.53). This was an original game design with the children creating their own backgrounds and a simple shaped sprite. The object of the game is to get the sprite from the start point in the top left-hand corner through the maze to the end red point before the timer runs out. This game demonstrates effective use of programming concepts. The sprite in the game is controlled by the arrow keys, which are all programmed correctly (Figure 8.54)

and uses conditions such as: if the green walls are touched the pink sprite will bounce off them and when the red end point is touched it signals the end of the game (see Figure 8.54). This game has one variable initialised within it as the timer illustrates (see Figure 8.54). If the end point is reached before the timer runs out then the game ends with a sound playing and message stating “you win”, however if not, then the timer ends the game with a “good try play again” message. The timing itself has a minor fault as the calculations used are not correct and stops when it reaches -5 rather than 0.

Figure 8.53: original maze game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.54: Game controls, conditionals and variables used in the game.

8.7.2 Game 2 High Scoring

The second high scoring game is from a group of boys in the Primary 4 class. Their game was based on the maze game; however, the background was re-designed (see Figure 8.55) and it was adapted into a two-player game. The aim of the game is to get the sprite from the start point in the top left-hand corner through the maze to the end orange square on the upper right-hand side before the timer runs out. This game demonstrates effective use of programming concepts. The sprites in the game are controlled by the arrow keys for player 1 and player 2 used the W, A, S and D keys, which are all programmed correctly (see Figure 8.56). The game uses conditions such as if the red shapes are touched the sprites will bounce off them and when the orange end point is touched the game ends. This game has two variables initialised with a timer and a scoring system. While the timer works correctly – the players have 30 seconds to complete their game – the scoring system needs changed as it runs like the timer.

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.56: Controls for both players

8.7.3 Game 3 Medium Scoring

This medium scoring game was created by a boy/girl pair in a Primary 5/6 class. Their game was an original game with the background and sprites being designed by the pair (see Figure 8.57). The aim of the game is to rescue the princess from the tower by controlling the prince to move to the tower and cut through the thorns. The game demonstrates originality in terms of creativity and thinking of an idea other than a maze. The game, however, was not finished. The prince could be controlled by using the arrow keys and the game ended when the prince reached the princess, using conditions when this happened the pair had added sound to the game (see Figure 8.58). However, no more functionality was added to the game to increase the difficulty of it.

Figure 8.57: Pair 19's original save the princess game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.58: Scripts for control of the prince sprite

8.7.4 Game 4 Medium Scoring

This medium scoring game was created by a pair of boys from a Primary 7 class. It is based on the maze game; however, they adapted the game into one that has a baby looking for its bottle (Figure 8.59). While the background was designed by the pupils the baby sprite was one that is pre-made in Scratch. The game did have added sound that was appropriate for the theme - a baby crying when the player moved the baby (Figure 8.60). However, there was no end point to the game and no use of variables unlike the higher scoring maze games.

Figure 8.59: Baby wants a bottle game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.60: Controls for baby sprite with added sounds

8.7.5 Game 5 Low Scoring

This low scoring game was created by a boy/girl pair in a Primary 4 class. They had based their game on the maze game. However, while they had designed the background they did not design the sprite which the player controlled (Figure 8.61). This sprite is one that comes with Scratch

and this sprite also has some pre-loaded scripts already attached to it to make it move (Figure 8.62). The sprite did not interact with the background in the way that the high scoring maze game did. Timing and scoring variables were created by the pair but not initialised within the game itself.

Figure 8.61: adapted maze game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.62: Scripts to control sprite in adapted maze game

8.7.6 Game 6 Low Scoring

This low scoring game was created by a pair of boys from the Primary 6/7 class. The aim of this two-player game was for one sprite to chase and catch another sprite (Figure 8.63). Both sprites have been taken from the Scratch sprites library and instead of creating a background the pair created another sprite to make that the background. There was little use of scripts within this game (Figure 8.64), although rather than use the arrow keys to control the sprite the mouse was used instead. Only one sprite was movable and therefore the game had little functionality with no conditions or variables added to it.

Figure 8.63: Two-player chasing game

Figure created by children. Formal consent was given by the parents to reproduce the artistic works created by children.

Figure 8.64: Script to control one of the sprites using the mouse to move them

8.8 Summary

This chapter has presented a coding scheme that was used to analyse the games created by children during the study. The eight lessons covered four lessons on the basics of game making with Scratch and then another four to progress themselves by either adapting the maze game or creating something new from what they had been taught. Given the timeframe and the age of the children this was a basic introduction. If more time had been available, then the children may have been able to progress making more complex games and learning more programming concepts. Most groups were successful in their attempts to create their game whether it was a maze game or original creation.

By examining the scores allocated to the games, overall 69% of games scored higher than the game that was taught in the first four lessons. Breaking this down into the two categories of the coding scheme, only 12% of games scored higher than the original game for programming. For the design part of the scoring scheme, 99% of games scored higher than the original maze

game. This shows that children can design their own game and with even just four lessons of being taught some concepts they can use them and develop a working game to an extent. While there were not any significant differences between gender groupings or class groupings it was evident there was some minor differences between them. Primary 4 classes did just as well as Primary 5, 6 and 7 which could be surprising given the different stages they should be working at, however, given this was the first time for all of them to be working on the lessons then that could explain the similarities in scores. With the gender groupings, what could be seen was that although not significantly different boys scored higher in overall score and in both games design and programming categories. However, within these categories the girls and mixed gender groupings did well also and indeed in some elements scored better than the boys. Girls created more of their own sprites and backgrounds than boys however due to other elements not being as well defined within their games they then scored less overall.

As well as this class teachers could have had an impact on the games. Two classes out of the research were taught by their own class teacher and not the researcher. Both teachers had different methods of teaching with teacher A having the younger P4 class who went for a very structured approach to learning Scratch and had children follow the lessons meticulously. Lessons were also stopped at various point to re-iterate and then move forward with the next section of learning. This happened for the first four weeks of lessons then children worked on their own game – this class did have a high proportion of working maze games that were all designed differently. Whereas the other class was taught by a teacher who followed more the researchers style of teaching the lessons.

The most frequently used programming concepts implemented by children in their games were like those found in Maloney *et al* (2008), namely User Interaction (key handling), Loops (iteration) and Conditional Statements. Variables were taught however there were many games that had variable within them but not used correctly which would indicate that the children had not picked up this concept as easily as the others. The use of random numbers was the lowest used programming concept; however, this was not a concept that was explicitly taught to the children during the lessons and therefore the children had done well to create games using this.

Overall the children did manage to learn some programming concepts over the eight-week period. The study has shown that even within eight hours of lessons, children were able to make progress with Scratch and their learning of programming. This was like the results of Baytak and Land (2011) where the children, after 10 Scratch lessons or 6 for their experienced children, had developed games. It was also like the game construction work of Robertson and Howells

(2008) with the Neverwinter Nights project. To help children in future learn more concepts that Scratch has more class time would be needed to explain and work on using variables and other more difficult concepts.

9 Conclusions, Reflections and Future Directions

9.1 Introduction

This chapter will detail the conclusions, reflections and future directions of this research study. The next section will revisit the original research questions and will reflect on whether they have been answered by the research. Next, the overall contribution to knowledge will be discussed and then each question as an individual will also be discussed in terms of the work performed, any limitations and its originality. Finally, the chapter will discuss the lasting impact the research has had on schools in Glasgow as well as the future directions of the research.

9.2 Conclusions

Four research questions were posed at the start of this thesis namely:

Question 1: What empirical evidence is associated with games-based learning at Primary Education (PE) level and how does it compare with the views of PE level teachers in Scotland?

Question 2: What framework could be used to implement games construction using Scratch within the Curriculum for Excellence at upper school PE?

Question 3: How do the different levels of upper school PE make use of Scratch and how can their work be evaluated?

9.2.1 RQ1: Evidence of GBL/GBCL within Primary Education (PE)

The first research question was posed to find out more about the current situation of GBL/GBCL in primary education within the literature and how widely it was used within Scottish primary schools. An extensive literature search indicated there is a lack of empirical evidence within PE to support GBL and, in particular, GBLC. The literature also highlighted problems that teachers faced when trying to implement GBL/GBCL in the class. The teacher survey that was conducted in Glasgow showed that 83% of teachers were using games in their teaching with Primary 1 teachers covering all eight curricular areas although, in later years of primary school, fewer curricular areas were being covered when playing games. However, when it came to using games construction tools only 15% of teachers had used them with their classes.

When questioned about what obstacles hindered them from using GBL/GBLC teachers felt that the main obstacle was that they were unsure about what tools they should be using with their

classes and this was closely followed by a lack of technology in the classes to then implement GBCL. Despite these obstacles, teachers were optimistic and considered that the use of GBL/GBCL could be very beneficial in building the four capacities (Confident individuals, Effective contributors, Responsible citizens and Successful learners) in a positive way with all the teachers questioned agreeing that it would benefit the successful learner strand of the capacities with reasons such as “*children love being challenged and feeling successful when they have mastered a skill*”. For the other three capacities over 75% of teachers believed that GBL could engage and motivate the children, although reasons for not seeing GBL as beneficial were that teachers felt children do not want to play the games that the teachers want to use or that children may become more isolated. However, teachers were unsure of children’s abilities to make their own games and this was last on the list of reasons for them to use GBL/GBCL in their teaching.

In summary, it is believed this question was generally well answered and was a strength of the research as the extensive nature of the literature review, covering various well-known electronic databases, returned thousands of articles from which the empirical work in PE was extracted. One limitation from this question, however, was the survey and the distribution to primary teachers within only one region within Scotland. The survey was also limited as it was more focused on GBL than GBCL and it should have done more to look at GBCL within schools and teachers’ attitudes towards games construction rather than being more about games playing.

9.2.2 Frameworks for the Use of GBCL in Primary Education

The second research question was posed firstly to determine if any frameworks existed that could be used to implement GBCL into PE and secondly to then implement the framework. By undertaking a literature review of GBCL it was shown that there were very few examples of its use within PE and that there were no suitable frameworks for implementing games construction within PE. It was therefore necessary to extend the literature search to cover both GBL and ICT implementation frameworks in education and compare them to produce an initial framework.

By drawing from the frameworks that were discovered and by utilising the study one presented in Chapter 5 that was conducted as well as the teacher survey a first draft of an implementation framework was devised. The overarching premise of the framework was that it was supported by the head teachers who would oversee what was happening at each stage and support their

staff when implementing GBCL. The framework considered what technology was available to the school and any limitations on hardware/software. The teacher's knowledge of GBCL was also a feature of the framework as well as ensuring teachers' skills were current as well as having up-to-date ICT plans within the school. Once the lessons had been undertaken, feedback was then obtained to assess the lessons and how staff and children felt about them, which was fed back into the framework to start the cycle again. Given the three schools in the first study had different ICT equipment available to them, ranging from having very little equipment to having enough equipment for each child in the class, provided a solid foundation of how schools can utilise what equipment they have, to undertake lessons in ICT. That said, staff in all three schools were unsure as to how to implement GBCL.

The first study was beneficial for all schools in showing them that they could undertake games construction lessons and that irrespective of how much ICT equipment schools had successful lessons could still take place. It was also beneficial in highlighting to the class teachers that incorporating GBCL into their ICT timetable could be achieved, that the children enjoyed the lessons even after a short period of time and that children were able to construct their own games.

In the second study, the framework was used in two schools both with differing ICT situations. While School 3 undertook the implementation of the framework the researcher still had to lead the lessons due to the class teacher not being confident in their abilities to deliver the lessons. This could be an issue if schools were undertaking the work themselves and did not have a researcher to work with, it could then leave either a teacher teaching a lesson which they are not confident in or not teaching the lessons at all.

In terms of the question being answered firstly there were no given frameworks for the implementation of GBCL in PE. One was derived from the available literature on ICT in PE and from the work undertaken in the first study. A limitation of this question was that the framework was not fully tested in a school just with teacher involvement. Although study 2 was conducted in two schools based on an initial framework and then modified the complete process was not completed by any one person as the teachers were not fully engaged with the framework.

9.2.3 Use of GBCL in the Upper School

Research question three was posed to determine if there was a particular stage in school that Scratch would be more beneficial for and how to evaluate what the children then created from those lessons. To assess this, action research was undertaken in classes within three schools, with children in Primary 4 through to Primary 7. By delivering eight one-hour lessons within schools at each primary level, the research showed how the children all managed and how they felt about the lessons. While the children worked in pairs/groups during the research each lesson was evaluated by each child and this provided insights into how children felt about taking part in the lessons. The lessons enabled teachers to become familiar with the environment and showed them exactly what the children could achieve during a short period of time. Children from all groups were overall successful in being able to make their own game with 93% of games created having some basic functionality. One of the most surprising results from the game coding was that children from Primary 4 were just as able as the Primary 7 classes in creating their own game. However, there were differences in the types of games that the Primary 4 class made as they tended to stick with making adaptations to the maze game rather than creating a brand-new game. By looking at the overall scoring while there were no noteworthy results the findings did suggest that boys scored higher than girls from programming and girls scored better than boys for design. Teams that had mixed gender pairings did well with more balanced games. Children's evaluations of the lessons at all stages were overall positive, however, the results suggested P5 children enjoyed the lessons the most. A limitation though on the evaluations would be how they were worded, although it was explained well to the children why the questions were being asked the wording for the affective question could have been modified to show different feelings about school. Children could possibly have been asked to compare their enjoyment of the Scratch lessons to that of other lessons in school that they have to take and so by doing so find out where in the school curriculum does computing sit within enjoyment of all school lessons.

A strength of this question was that the research was undertaken with 16 classes of children (384 children), which gave a good representation of all groups between Primary 4 and Primary 7, although a limitation of the study was that there was not an equal distribution across the different groups with more Primary 7 classes involved in the study with the other groups being almost equal. Another strength in answering this question was the creation of the game coding scheme to assess the games that had been created during the project. The coding scheme examined programming concepts children used based on what concepts Scratch supports and

it also looked at the design aspect of their games and how much of the game was designed by themselves or if they had used assets that came with Scratch. Children could use the concepts taught to them during the first four lessons and some pairings went further and managed to add other concepts into their games that were more difficult to learn in the time given. Children were also creating their own variables to use as scoring mechanisms and timers although due to the age of some of the children they had difficulty in dealing with the concept of negative numbers in setting up the negative one to ensure the timer or scores would count in the right way.

The final research question was posed to investigate how class teachers could integrate games construction into their cross curricular lessons. By taking the opportunity to teach the lessons themselves, the teachers could see how games construction could fit into their curriculum. One of the issues raised from the surveys and teacher interviews was that teachers were unsure as to how they could utilise games construction and how they would introduce it. Of the teachers who participated, only two led lessons and more teachers would be needed to answer the question more fully. However, all teachers who participated whether observing or leading lessons were interviewed at key points during the study and felt that using Scratch had been very enjoyable for them and the children. Teachers also stated that they could see how they could integrate GBCL into their lessons after only a few lessons and were able to envisage what curricular areas it would be useful for. Some teachers were unsure about the benefits of using it for lessons at the start of the study, however, as the lessons progressed the teachers could see that the children were enjoying it and that the children were also making satisfactory progress in their game construction.

Teachers identified many advantages to using Scratch such as children gaining problem solving skills, perseverance, facing challenges, using appropriate dialogue, taking responsibility for own learning, increasing confidence, applying skills outside the classroom, stimulating curiosity of how games are made leading them to further research and now children come and leave ICT happy. Working in pairs/groups is widely encouraged in schools although teachers commented that possibly one disadvantage was that it would be good for the children to construct their own game, however, lessons would need to be altered in some classes for that to happen due to the shortage of PCs available.

The two teachers who led their own lessons felt that they could confidently deliver the lessons having previously observed lessons and undertaken CPD to gain more skills using Scratch. When interviewed, the teachers believed Scratch would be useful for constructing games

relating to projects that the children were undertaking in class. They both agreed that Scratch was a valuable tool for introducing the children to games construction and that they would continue to use Scratch in their teaching.

This question has been reasonably well answered in that teachers can see the potential in their classes and some have now had first-hand experience at implementing it. A strength of the research is that teachers have been able to implement the lessons themselves with support and their classes have had just as much enjoyment as the other classes who took part in the research as well as producing similar quality games to the other classes. One limitation of the study was that not enough teachers have seen Scratch being used in lessons.

9.2.4 Supporting Computational thinking

In chapter 3 the literature discussed how Brennan & Resnick (2012) have shown that Scratch can support computational thinking and provided seven concepts as a starting point. By undertaking the work in class and evaluating the children's' games it can be seen that the children have used six out of the seven concepts defined.

9.2.5 Generalisability

This research has shown that games construction can be implemented into the ICT curriculum within primary education. Action research was adopted as the methodology to investigate the use of Scratch within the classroom. The definition of action research that was adopted was one that "*seeks both to inform and influence practice*" (Reason and Bradbury, 2006). The research undertaken has informed educators how they can implement GBCL within their establishments and to an extent influenced schools who participated as they are continuing with the work that was started in their schools. However, while action research is generally considered not to be generalisable the research can be of benefit to researchers, education departments and other schools.

9.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This thesis has provided a significant contribution to knowledge in four areas:

- it has shown how GBL/GBCL is being used in schools and what teachers feel about it;
- it has provided a framework for implementation that can be used in schools to undertake GBCL;
- empirical evidence on the use of GBCL in schools;

- a game coding scheme to assess Scratch games programming and design;

9.3.1 Use of GBL/GBCL in Primary Education

This thesis has investigated the use of GBL/GBCL in primary education. It has shown that while it is being used, it is still not a widely recognised approach for teachers to use in class. This is attributed to factors such as lack of technology and training for teachers in implementing this kind of project. It has provided the starting point of a literature search for other researchers to use to investigate GBL/GBCL within PE. It has also undertaken a survey of teachers. Despite it only covering one region within Scotland, as Razak, Connolly and Hainey (2012) had undertaken a similar survey within another two regions in Scotland with comparable results to the views of the teachers in Glasgow, it was felt there was no further need to replicate the survey in other areas.

9.3.2 Implementation Framework for GBCL in Primary Education

This thesis has provided an implementation framework for primary schools to use when implementing GBCL. Throughout the study various classroom/ICT labs were utilised and this has helped to improve the framework and has demonstrated how easily lessons can take place without having to have a computer for every child. Children benefitted from working either in pairs or groups and teachers commented on the social skills that their students were gaining through the study and that they had to learn to co-operate with others to make their game.

This thesis has provided a starting point for schools who wish to use GBCL in the class. The framework developed has provided a practical way for schools to be guided on how to implement GBCL within their schools.

9.3.3 Empirical Evidence of the use of GBCL in Primary Education

This thesis has shown that GBCL can be implemented successfully within the curriculum in primary education. By undertaking practical lessons in school, it has contributed to the empirical work in this field. The lessons were undertaken with 16 classes between Primary 4 and Primary 7 either in ICT suites or classrooms. The lessons have shown that most children enjoyed working with Scratch and that they were all able to create their own games. The teachers' views were also considered, and their opinions gathered at set points throughout the research namely before, during and after lessons. Generally, teachers were unsure at the start of the lessons what they thought GBCL could do and they did not feel confident about the

lessons. However, even after four lessons attitudes were changing and teachers could see more benefits in using GBCL and by the end of the study teachers were keen to use Scratch again and to recommend using Scratch to others as they could see how engaged and motivated the children were when using it.

9.3.4 Game Coding Scheme

This thesis has developed a coding scheme that was used to assess the games that had been created during the study. The game coding scheme covers both design and programming. This coding scheme was created as there were no Scratch coding schemes available and therefore this scheme can be used as a starting point for other researchers who wish to assess games constructed with Scratch (and tools with similar constructs).

9.4 Originality of the Research

The areas of originality that this research has produced are empirical work in primary schools investigating an area of research that is relatively unexplored, a coding scheme for assessing games created with Scratch and a framework for the implementation of GBCL in primary education.

9.4.1 Empirical Evidence of GBCL in the Primary Classroom

This research has produced empirical evidence of GBCL being used in 3 schools with over 350 children aged 8-12 years participating in the study. From the literature detailed in Section 3.4 it is one of the largest studies undertaken with children in primary education as well as one that investigates a broader age range of primary children's game construction in school with most studies between the age of 10-12 and this research looking at children from aged 8-12 years old.

9.4.2 Game Coding Scheme for Scratch

This research has produced a detailed game coding scheme that can be used when assessing games created by Scratch. From the literature detailed in Section 8.2 it was shown that there were no coding schemes that analysed Scratch games to the detail provided in the scheme that was developed by focusing on the programming and design elements of the games created. The studies from the literature focused on what blocks within Scratch students had used in their programs and therefore this coding scheme offers a new way to analyse games that have been

created using Scratch to see what concepts have been used or how the game has been put together design wise as well.

9.4.3 A Framework for Implementing GBCL in Primary Education

This research has produced a framework for schools to implement GBCL within them. As well as producing the framework it was trialled in school and adapted based on findings from the study to provide a revised framework that has been shown to be applicable to the use of GBCL in primary schools under the Scottish Curriculum for Excellence.

9.5 Publications

The contribution to the body of knowledge is supported by the following publications:

- Wilson, A., Hainey, T., Connolly, T. M. (2013). Using Scratch with Primary School children: An Evaluation of Games constructed to gauge understanding of Programming Concepts. *International Journal of Game-Based Learning*, 3(1), 93–109
- Hainey T., Connolly T.M., Boyle E.,Azadegan A.,Wilson. A, Razak A. and Gray G. (2014). A Systematic Literature Review to Identify Empirical Evidence on the use of Games-Based Learning in Primary Education for Knowledge Acquisition and Content Understanding. In *Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Games-based Learning (ECGBL)*, 9th-10th October 2014, Berlin, Germany
- Wilson, A., Hainey, T., Connolly, T. M. (2013). Development of an Implementation framework for Games-based Construction Learning using Scratch in Primary Education. In *Proceedings of the 7th European Conference on Games-based Learning (ECGBL)*, 3-4th October 2013, Porto, Portugal.
- Wilson, A., Hainey, T., Connolly, T. M. (2012). Evaluation of Computer Games Developed by Primary School Children to Gauge Understanding of Programming Concepts. In *Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Games-based Learning (ECGBL)*, 4-5 October 2012, Cork, Ireland.
- Razak, A. A., Connolly, T. M., Baxter, G. J., Hainey, T., Wilson, A. (2012). The Use of Games-based- Learning at Primary Education Level within the Curriculum for Excellence: A Combined Result of Two Regional Teacher Surveys. In *Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Games-based Learning (ECGBL)*, 4-5 October 2012, Cork, Ireland.
- Van Rosmalen, P., Wilson, A., & Hummel, H. G. K. (2012). *Games For and By Teachers and Learners*. In T. M. Connolly, E. Boyle, T. Hainey, G. Baxter, & P. Moreno-Ger (Eds.), *Psychology, Pedagogy and Assessment in Serious Games*.

9.6 Implications for Schools

Because of the research undertaken more schools within Glasgow are now investigating how to incorporate Scratch into their ICT lessons. An event was held towards the end of the research based in schools and this incorporated two classes getting together to take part in a Mini Game Jam. The jam was organised to allow the children to spend time working in teams to create games using the skills they had learned from undertaking their Scratch lessons in school. Following on from the success of the first event held in June 2013 more schools were encouraged by the Head Teacher of Royston Primary (Ford & Kelly, 2016) also see appendix 9 and it has led to more teachers wanting to get their children making games with Scratch (See appendix 10). With more interest being shown for coding in schools Glasgow City Council Education department have now been active in getting more teachers teaching GBCL in primary and taking part in Mini Game Jams across the city. This could lead to more teachers having a go at Scratch themselves and letting their classes work on their own games in preparation for taking part in a game jam event. It would build confidence in teachers when they realise that other teachers who were just as nervous about teaching with Scratch were able to manage the lessons and it is not as daunting as they think it is. With the events held at a local secondary school this could also be used by the computing departments as a way of gauging skills across schools and possibly help shape lessons going into secondary if all children are coming in with a basic knowledge of Scratch. As teachers during the interviews had stated that the children did learn a lot more than just programming throughout the study and there were valuable skills such as problem solving and teamwork which they felt to be very important.

The research has been an extensive piece of work of which there has been few looking at GBCL within PE and has shown that using an action research methodology can have great benefits not only by creating new empirical data but also by impacting on schools and their delivery of part of the curriculum. It has also impacted on how some learning communities in Glasgow work together now that the game jams are running regularly and is building better relationships between both primary and secondary schools while giving the children a chance to learn and have fun at the same time.

9.7 Future Research Directions

There are many directions that could be explored in future studies, however, five that will form the immediate focus of research will be discussed, namely, longer use of Scratch in school over

the school year; using other games construction tools; extending the teacher survey; extended evaluation of the revised framework; and using Scratch at other levels in education.

9.7.1 Long Term use of Scratch in the Classroom

One of the limitations of the study was the short amount of time that was available for giving the lessons. This was imposed by the schools to incorporate the lessons into their ICT plans. The study investigated the use of Scratch to construct games over an eight-hour period. One probable future direction would be to extend this time with the class and give the children time to build a few different games and develop their skills over the academic year.

9.7.2 Using Other Games Construction Tools in Primary Education

While the study used Scratch as the tool for games construction there are other tools available on tablet devices as well as on PCs. One possible future direction would be to study the use of other games construction tools and compare these results with the findings from this study. Applications such as Kodu, Touch Develop, Stencyl, Gamemaker, Hopscotch and Alice could all be potentially utilised to construct games. This would then allow for comparisons to be made between game constructions tools and which ones would be suitable for PE. While this study was limited by what game construction tool had to be used due to the network management of schools within the local authority, other local authorities may not be as restrictive as to what tools schools can use for games construction or possibly what device the games construction takes place on.

9.7.3 Using Scratch at Other Levels of Education

This study focused on using Scratch to construct games within PE, however, from the literature Scratch has been used at other levels of education to teach introductory programming. By using the lessons developed during the research, a study could be conducted with students of other ages whether in secondary or tertiary education to teach them how to construct their own games. Comparisons could then be made to investigate what sector of education Scratch is best suited for introducing games construction.

9.7.4 Extending the Survey

Results from the teacher survey indicated that while GBL was being used in school, GBCL was not. Although the survey of teachers in this study was limited to teachers within one local

authority in Scotland other surveys have been undertaken in other regions with comparable results. However, for future research the survey could be extended to different areas within the UK or further afield to compare how, and if, teachers in PE are using GBCL.

9.7.5 Framework

Although the first implementation framework was limited in that only one school was able to fully utilise the framework with full staff participation another school used most of the stages thereby enabling a revision of the framework. Future research could entail the revised framework being implemented within other PE establishments within Scotland or even further afield. The revised framework could also be further adapted to suit various levels of education who wished to implement GBCL into their curriculum.

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Appendix 1 Ethical Approval Letter from University

Amanda Wilson
PhD Research Student
School of Computing
Room H332B
Elles Building South
Paisley Campus

Paisley Campus
Paisley
PA1 2BF
Scotland

Tel +44 (0)141 848 3680
Fax +44 (0)141 848 3734

18th October 2011

Dear Amanda

REF. EC/150611/Wilson

The University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee has considered the application for your project: Games Based Learning in the Upper Primary School.

I am pleased to inform you that ethical approval has been granted.

Please keep the Committee informed should there be any changes to your study which may require further ethical consideration.

Charlie Fielding
Secretary to the University Ethics Committee
Innovation and Research Office

Personal details withheld.

Innovation and Research Office
Ian Bishop, Director

Appendix 2 Ethical Approval Letter from Glasgow City Council

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

Education Services
Glasgow City Council
Wheatley House
25 Cochrane Street
Merchant City
Glasgow G1 1HL

[Redacted]

Website www.glasgow.gov.uk
Our Ref JS/Rsrch
Date 9 May 2011

[Redacted]

Ms Amanda Wilson
c/o School of Computing
University of West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
PAISLEY
PA1 2BE

Dear Ms Wilson

Proposed Research Project – Games Based Learning in Schools.

Thank you for your completed research application form in respect of the above.

I now write to advise you that this department has no objection to you seeking assistance with your project from our primary schools. I would confirm however that it is very much up to the Headteachers to decide whether or not their schools participate and assist you in your research.

A copy of this letter should be sent to the Headteachers when contacting the appropriate schools.

This approval is also on the condition that as there are young people involved regarding this project, and they are less than 16 years of age, parental/carers consent **must be requested, and given**, before such involvement. All researchers must have recently approved Disclosure Scotland (or equivalent) checks.

I hope that this is helpful and that you have success with your project.

[Redacted]

Personal details withheld.

Glasgow—Proud Host City of the 2014 Commonwealth Games
Glasgow City Council is an equal opportunities employer

Appendix 3 Disclosure Scotland Certificate

Personal details withheld. Original document is a Scotland Disclosure Form.
Please contact the author for more information.

Appendix 4 Teacher Questionnaire

The Study

Games-based learning (GBL) is the use of computer games in the classroom. We are trying to study the use of GBL to enhance teaching and learning in primary school education under the Curriculum for Excellence. In particular the research will focus on:

- A constructivist approach to games-based learning that allows students to develop their own GBL applications using appropriate toolkits.

Who are we?

We are a group of researchers from the University of the West of Scotland.

What is this questionnaire for?

This questionnaire is designed to achieve the following objectives:

1. To gauge the current use of games-based learning at primary schools in Scotland.
2. To find teachers who are interested in participating in further evaluation.

We would be grateful if you could complete this questionnaire as the research could have an effect on how we learn in the future and hopefully will make the learning process more interesting for us all.

Thank you for your time.

*** School name:**

*** Year Taught:**

Gender:

 Male Female

*** Age:**

Have you ever used any computer games for teaching?

No

Yes

What game(s) did you use and what area of the curriculum did you use them for?

Expressive arts	<input type="text"/>
Health and wellbeing	<input type="text"/>
Languages	<input type="text"/>
Maths	<input type="text"/>
RME	<input type="text"/>
Sciences	<input type="text"/>
Social Studies	<input type="text"/>
Technologies	<input type="text"/>

What year group(s) was the game used with?

- P1
- P2
- P3
- P4
- P5
- P6
- P7

What do you think were the benefits of the game for teaching?

What do you think were the drawbacks of the game for teaching?

Have you ever used a game creation tool for teaching?

No

Yes

What game making tool did you use and what area of the curriculum did you use it for?

Expressive arts	<input type="text"/>
Health and wellbeing	<input type="text"/>
Languages	<input type="text"/>
Maths	<input type="text"/>
RME	<input type="text"/>
Sciences	<input type="text"/>
Social Studies	<input type="text"/>
Technologies	<input type="text"/>

What year group(s) was the game used with?

- P1
- P2
- P3
- P4
- P5
- P6
- P7

What do you think were the benefits of the game for teaching?

What do you think were the drawbacks of the game for teaching?

Have you ever developed your own educational game using a game creation tool for teaching?

No

Yes

What game did you make and area of the curriculum did you use it for?

Expressive arts	<input type="text"/>
Health and wellbeing	<input type="text"/>
Languages	<input type="text"/>
Maths	<input type="text"/>
RME	<input type="text"/>
Sciences	<input type="text"/>
Social Studies	<input type="text"/>
Technologies	<input type="text"/>

Can you give a brief description of the game you created?

What year group(s) was the game used with?

- P1
- P2
- P3
- P4
- P5
- P6
- P7

What do you think were the benefits of the game for teaching?

What do you think were the drawbacks of the game for teaching?

For each of the curriculum areas below, please rate how suitable you think GBL would be for teaching.

	Very Suitable	Suitable	Neutral	Unsuitable	Very unsuitable
Expressive arts	<input type="radio"/>				
Health and wellbeing	<input type="radio"/>				
Languages	<input type="radio"/>				
Maths	<input type="radio"/>				
RME	<input type="radio"/>				
Sciences	<input type="radio"/>				
Social Studies	<input type="radio"/>				
Technologies	<input type="radio"/>				

Do you feel using GBL would be beneficial for building Effective Contributors?

- No
 Yes

Please explain:

Do you feel using GBL would be beneficial for building Successful Learners?

- No
 Yes

Please explain:

Do you feel using GBL would be beneficial for building Confident Individuals?

- No
 Yes

Please explain:

Do you feel using GBL would be beneficial for building Responsible Citizens?

- No
 Yes

Please explain:

Please rate how strongly you agree with the following statements:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Using a computer game for teaching is as convenient as other teaching approaches	<input type="radio"/>				
I am very comfortable with using computer games for teaching.	<input type="radio"/>				
The students always enjoy learning using computer games.	<input type="radio"/>				
The students have the ability to create their own game using game creation tools.	<input type="radio"/>				

Based on your experience with your students, how would you rate each of the following reasons in terms of importance for learning?

	Very Important	Important	Neutral	Un-Important	Very Un-Important	Dont Know
Playing computer games provides my students with a challenge	<input type="radio"/>					
Playing computer games allows my students to compete	<input type="radio"/>					
Playing computer games allows my students to cooperate	<input type="radio"/>					
Playing computer games allows my students to enter a fantasy world.	<input type="radio"/>					
Playing computer games stimulates my students curiosity	<input type="radio"/>					
Playing computer games gives my students pleasure.	<input type="radio"/>					
Playing computer games helps my students to relax.	<input type="radio"/>					

The table below shows general attitudes to playing computer games. Please rate each attitude with respect to how strongly you agree with it.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Playing games is exciting	<input type="radio"/>				
Playing games helps develop useful skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Playing games is time consuming	<input type="radio"/>				
Playing games is interesting	<input type="radio"/>				
Playing games is a worthwhile activity	<input type="radio"/>				
Playing games is enjoyable	<input type="radio"/>				
Playing games is a sociable activity	<input type="radio"/>				

Please rate the severity of the obstacles that may be faced when using GBL approach for teaching.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Lack of PCs and technology.	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of skill and training.	<input type="radio"/>				
Time and curriculum constraints.	<input type="radio"/>				
Difficulty in identifying a suitable game.	<input type="radio"/>				
Difficulty in identifying a suitable game making tool.	<input type="radio"/>				

Are there any other obstacles not mentioned in the list above? Please explain:

Are you aware of any initiative/projects to introduce GBL into the class?:-

No

Yes

If yes please give details:

Please rate your agreement on the benefits of using a GBL approach:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Promotes deep learning by arousing a student's curiosity on certain subjects	<input type="radio"/>				
Encourages students to take a problem solving approach in learning.	<input type="radio"/>				
Fosters collaborative learning among peers.	<input type="radio"/>				
Transforms learning into a fun experience.	<input type="radio"/>				
Transforms learning into a motivating experience.	<input type="radio"/>				
Transforms learning into an engaging experience	<input type="radio"/>				
Others	<input type="radio"/>				

If other please specify:

Do you have any other comments you would like to add?

We are looking for volunteers among teachers to participate in the evaluation that will compare the use of games-based learning to other approaches to teaching and learning. This will include learning through designing/creating computer games.

Would you be interested in attending a twilight session at the beginning of the next school year (August/September 2011) for more information on the project?

No

Yes

If yes please enter the following:

Name

Email address

Thank you for your time and participation.

Appendix 5 Games Used by Class Teachers at Each Stage/Curriculum Area

	RME	Technologies	Social Studies	Expressive arts	Sciences	Health and wellbeing	Languages	Maths
P1	Noahs Ark	NGFL Websites, Primary Resources	Lots depending on what we're doing	Kid pix; British Council Websites; KidPix Deluxe 4; Compose World Junior	www.sciencemus eum.org.uk/online stuff.aspx	kidshealth.org ; health quizzes online	Phonic games, spelling games; Roy the Zebra; education city, task magic and other websites like ictgames.com; games from the topmarks website; Starfall, Literactive.; various CD-ROMS, e.g. fairytale sequencing; Task Magic; Primary Games hangman; websites, e.g. Phonicsplay; Smart Board games created by teacher	various games from TES Topmarks,etc; maths circus, games from the topmarks website; school games websites, lots of different ones, coolmaths etc.; Education city; Maths Circus; Primary Games; various CD-ROMS; websites e.g. Crickweb
P2				Wii Dance; Kid pix/ kid pix Deluxe 4; Compose World Junior	www.sciencemus eum.org.uk/online stuff.aspx; Forces / materials	kidshealth.org ; Wii fit and Just Dance for the Wii; grid club; health quizzes online	BBC games; Phonic games, spelling games; education city, task magic and other websites like ictgames.com; games from the topmarks website; grid club; French; various CD-ROMS, e.g. fairytale sequencing; Task Magic; Primary Games hangman; websites, e.g. Phonicsplay; Smart Board games created by teacher	Bulletpoint Games Maths Packs; education city, bullet point and other websites like ictgames.com; maths circus, games from the topmarks website; grid club; Education city; various CD-ROMS; websites e.g. Crickweb
P3			ancient Egypt	Kid pix	functions of a plant; www.sciencemus eum.org.uk/online stuff.aspx	road safety; games on websites such as kidshealth.org	BBC games; Phonic games, spelling games; education city, task magic and other websites like ictgames.com	Bulletpoint Games Maths Packs; education city, bullet point and other websites like ictgames.com ; Education city; Maths Circus; Primary Games;
P4				Kid pix; KidPix Deluxe 4; Compose World Junior	www.sciencemus eum.org.uk/online stuff.aspx; Electricity games	kidshealth.org ; health quizzes online	BBC games; Phonic games, spelling games; education city, task magic and other websites like ictgames.com; Spell City - great for less able and EAL pupils.; Education City; various CD-ROMS, e.g. fairytale sequencing; Task Magic; Primary Games hangman; websites, e.g. Phonicsplay; Smart Board games created by teacher	Bulletpoint Games Maths Packs; education city, bullet point and other websites like ictgames.com; Many different games mostly from Maths Circus or the curriculum resources supplied by Glasgow City Council.; Education City Maths Pack; Education city; Maths Circus; Primary Games; various CD-ROMS; websites e.g. Crickweb
P5				Kid pix; KidPix Deluxe 4; Compose World Junior	www.sciencemus eum.org.uk/online stuff.aspx; Electricity games	kidshealth.org ; Wii fit , Just Dance for the Wii; health quizzes online	BBC games; Phonic games, spelling games; education city, task magic and other websites like ictgames.com; Spell City - great for less able and EAL pupils.; Education City; various CD-ROMS, e.g. fairytale sequencing; Task Magic; Primary Games hangman; websites, e.g. Phonicsplay; Smart Board games created by teacher	Bulletpoint Games Maths Packs; education city, bullet point and other websites like ictgames.com; Many different games mostly from Maths Circus or the curriculum resources supplied by Glasgow City Council.; Education City Maths Pack; Education city; Maths Circus; Primary Games; various CD-ROMS; websites e.g. Crickweb

P6		BBC website		Kid pix; music; KidPix Deluxe 4; Compose World Junior	BBC Bitesize games, Education City; www.sciencemus eum.org.uk/online stuff.aspx; sound and light electricity; Electricity games	kidshealth.org ; Wii fit and Just Dance for the Wii	BBC games; Education City; BBC website; Phonic games, spelling games; education city, task magic and other websites like ictgames.com; spelling; Education City; various CD-ROMS, e.g. fairytale sequencing; Task Magic; Primary Games hangman; websites, e.g. Phonicsplay; Smart Board games created by teacher	Bulletpoint Games Maths Packs; education city, bullet point ;Zoombinis (The Logical Journey of); Primary games - maths circus; Variety of maths games mostly from GCC network; education city, bullet point and other websites like ictgames.com; all areas; Education City Maths Pack; Education city; various CD-ROMs; websites e.g. Crickweb
P7			different web-sites with quizzes			Think u know internet safety disc	Phonic games, spelling games; internet based game; games from the topmarks website	Zoombinis (The Logical Journey of); internet based game; maths circus, games from the topmarks website; Education city

Appendix 6 Children's Evaluation Form

The children were given these short evaluations to complete after each lesson.

Name:

Date:

Today's lesson was

Lots of fun	Fun	Ok	Boring	Very boring
-------------	-----	----	--------	-------------

It made me feel

Very happy	Happy	Ok	Sad	Very sad
---------------	-------	----	-----	----------

Appendix 7 Teacher Interview Questions

Teacher interview before the lessons take place.

1. What are your expectations from this research study?
2. Do you use any computer games to teach with your class at present or have you done so before?
3. What subjects do you use them for?
4. Have you undertaken any game making before?
5. Do you feel using game making would be beneficial for building the four capacities?
6. What subjects do you think game making would be suitable to help teach?
7. Do you think the children would be able to make their own games with a game making tool?
8. Do you think the children will enjoy making their own games?
9. Do you think the children will enjoy working in pairs?
10. Do you see any benefits to the children working in pairs?
11. Can you think of any benefits of making games?
12. Can you think of any drawbacks to making games?
13. Is there anything else you would like to add?

Teacher interview questions halfway through study

1. How do you feel the research is going?
2. Are you enjoying the lessons?
3. Can you see how game making would be beneficial for building the four capacities?
4. What subjects do you think game making would be suitable to help teach?
5. Do you think the children are enjoying the lessons?
6. Do you think the children are making progress with the lessons?
7. Are the children enjoying working in pairs?
8. Do you see any benefits to the children working in pairs?
9. Can you think of any benefits of making games?
10. Can you think of any drawbacks to making games?
11. Is there anything else you would like to add?

Teacher interview questions after all 8 lessons have taken place.

1. Thinking back what were your expectations from this research study?
2. Over the course of the project did your views change about game making?
3. Can you see how game making would be beneficial for building the four capacities?
4. What subjects do you think game making would be suitable to help teach?
5. Did you enjoy the lessons?
6. How do you think the lessons went with the children?
7. Did you feel the children made progress with the lessons?
8. Do you think the children enjoyed the lessons?
9. Did you see any benefits to the children working in pairs?
10. Can you think of any benefits of making games?
11. Can you think of any drawbacks to making games?
12. Would you recommend game making to your colleagues as a tool to use to teach computing?
13. Will you continue to make games with your class?
14. What subjects would you use scratch with to make games?
15. Do you have anything else to add?

Appendix 8 Conditional Script from P5/6 game

Appendix 9 Letter from Head Teacher

12th February 2016

When I first took up my position as Head teacher at Royston Primary I had been made aware that the school had been participating within a research project that was investigating the use of Scratch in upper primary. With staff participating as well as the researcher who was assisting with the teaching of Scratch and also was responsible for providing staff with support an CPD it was a worthwhile project to keep going in the school as it was providing the children with opportunities to learn new skills in their ICT lessons. By working closely with the researcher we were able to use the lessons that had been undertaken and see how they could be incorporated into the schools ICT plans (see attached). Once the research had come to an end the researcher had discussed ideas as to how to keep up the momentum of Scratch being used by the class teachers who had been trained and she had mentioned the idea of an event for the two schools that had been involved in the second year of the research. The idea was to have both P7 classes come together and work in teams to create a game using Scratch based on the Global Game jam which lasts for 48 hours however condensed into a school day.

The expectations from the first Mini Game Jam were low – will this be an enjoyable, meaningful experience and will the children be able to demonstrate their skills. These expectations still remain but have now been added to – how do the children get on with their peers?; are their skills being challenged in unfamiliar contexts? To this end, I enjoy hearing from the children and staff on their return. From speaking with them I always find out that the Game Jams have met the expectations that we set out at the start.

Planning across CfE has evolved in recent years, trying to take account of meaningful opportunities to apply newly acquired skills. The Mini Game Jam has allowed staff to work backwards from an event and plan the sessions required to get the skills taught. In the first year it was trial and error, trying to get staff CPD sessions linked to allow them to feel confident and comfortable in supporting the delivery of the sessions by the Mini Game Jam organiser.

Over the years we have been better at preparing and planning for this in class. The biggest barrier to getting involved in the Mini Game Jam was ensuring that transport could be arranged to the venue. All the information was shared in plenty of time and staff knew clearly what was expected of them. In some cases CPD sessions had to be arranged to get staff up to speed on what was required, especially in confidently delivering the sessions. However, there was an eagerness on staff behalf to move forward with this area. The children enjoyed designing their games during their class work and the chance to expand these opportunities into a Mini Game Jam were widely accepted. The pupils also saw the fun of working both in mixed teams and getting the chance to make friends ahead of moving to Secondary School. The chance to hear from Games Industry workers were also commented on by pupils returning from the Mini Game Jam last year.

In recent years my expectations have changed about the Mini Game Jam. Initially the event was seen as a chance for the children to demonstrate their learning in Games design. This was the “relevant” part of the Curriculum for Excellence, applying skills in a different way. Now 3 years down the road it has changed in a number of ways. The event is still linked to the original theme of relevant learning but is now coupled with our transition to Secondary School events. In addition to looking at skills for life and a possible future career in Games Design.

There are many benefits from taking part in the Mini Game Jam and have been previously discussed. However, the main benefit that the children got from the Mini Game Jam is the chance to make meaningful links between what they learn in class and how these skills are applied in real life contexts. There is also the benefit of staff skills in ICT being increased through the engagement of the professionals who deliver the CPD sessions. The school keeps their involvement in the Mini Game Jam because the children ask every year if it is on! This request from pupils allows us to facilitate the Mini Game Jam through the support of the Mini Game Jam organiser.

While I have now moved to take up the position of Head teacher in another primary school I am still looking at ways in which to incorporate the work that has been done previously into the school I am in now. The Mini Game Jam has now been supported by Glasgow City Council Education Services and more schools across the city are now getting the chance to participate and I will

maintain my schools engagement in this area because I feel it is a truly meaningful way to showcase the skills being learning in other curricular areas – the main thrust of CfE.

**Simon Kelly
Head Teacher**

Appendix 10 Letter from Teacher who is teaching with Scratch

I ran a 'Computer Game Design' Elective, one period a week in the 2013/14 & the 2014/15 school terms. Without Amanda's assistance this would not have been possible. Amanda introduced me to using Scratch software when she visited the school working with some Primary classes. We installed Scratch on all the system in our Music ICT suite and I soon became intrigued with what it could do.

The elective class is a fairly recent initiative in our timetable and it gives learners a chance to learn about a specialist subject – one which does not feature as part of the regular curriculum. I decided to switch from the 'Podcasting' Elective I had been running for 2 years, to an elective class based on what Amanda had shown me. Amanda helped by providing me with numerous resources which aided me in the delivery of the lessons and she was always available via email if I needed to ask about anything regarding Scratch etc.

The culmination of the elective programme was the Game Jam. Using learners who had been prepared for the event by myself in Smithycroft or by Amanda in some of our feeder primary schools, we gave a large group of approximately 100 P6 - S2 students an opportunity to participate in a day long creative project. The children not only learned how to work as a team and developed technical expertise, but they were also given the opportunity to rub shoulders with some professional Game Designers/Coders from the Scottish industry. None of this would have happened without Amanda who organised the entire event incredibly effectively. She put all of the children into differentiated groups, timetabled the whole day, and provided numerous prizes and rewards for the children's participation amongst other things!

The Game Jam is now into its third year and we look forward to running it again this session. It is a fantastic opportunity to broaden the horizons of our young people and many of them now want to pursue careers in the game industry and have a realistic perspective on what is required for them to fulfil this ambition.

Stephen Gallagher
Smithycroft Secondary